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UNIVERSITY OF THE
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Access to Business Loans by Ethnic Minority
Owners of Small Business in Scotland

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Dedication

I will like to first of all thank God for making one of my dream come through. This thesis is dedicated to my dear wife Mrs Ewoni Udeme Jonah, whose love and patience has encouraged me through this journey. My gratitude goes to my Father, Mother and Sisters for all their prayers and support. I will never forget my Director of Studies Dr Ahmed Beloucif and my supervisory team who took time to supervise this thesis. I am forever grateful.

Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another research degree

Signed: _____ *Udeme Jonah* _____

Date: _____ 7/01/2022 _____

Contents

Dedication	ii
Declaration	iii
Contents	iv
List of Figures	xi
List of Tables	x
Abstract	xii
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 Overview	1
1.1 Statement of the Problem	1
1.2 Definition of Terms	3
1.3 Research Aim and Objectives	4
1.3.1 Research Aim	4
1.3.2 Research Objectives	4
1.4 Research Questions	5
1.5 Research Rationale	5
1.6 History of Asian Immigration to Scotland	6
1.7 Research Strategy and Data Collection Access and Ethics	7
1.7.1 Qualitative Research	7
1.8. Structure of the Research Project	8
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	9
2.0 Introduction	9
2.1 Access to Business Loans	11
2.2.0 Types of Lenders	13
2.2.1 Family and Friends	13
2.2.2 Owners as Lenders	14
2.2.3 Commercial Lenders	14
2.3 Process of Loans	15
2.3.1 Term of Loans	16
2.3.2 Fully Amortized Term Loans	16
2.3.3 Evergreen Bsuiness Lines	17
2.3.4 Revolving Business Line-Annual Renewal	17
2.4.0 Ethnic Minorities	17
2.4.1 Ethnic Minorities Trends	19
2.5 Small Business In Scotland	21
2.6 Types of Small Business Loan	22
2.6.1 Credit Cards	23

2.6.2 Operating Line	23
2.6.3 Commercial Loans	24
2.6.4 Seasonal Loan	24
2.6.5 Overdraft Checking	24
2.6.6 Bank Loans	25
2.6.7 Letter of Credit	25
2.6.8 Factoring	26
2.6.9 Credit Union	26
2.7 Theories and Concepts	26
2.7.1 The Theory of Entrepreneurship	26
2.7.2 The Theory of Ethnic Entrepreneurship	28
2.7.3.0 Asymmetric Information.....	30
2.7.3.1 The Principles of Asymmetric Information.....	33
2.7.3.2 The Purpose of Asymmetric Information.....	34
2.7.3.3 How Asymmetric Information Works Between Lenders and Borrowers	35
2.7.3.4 Prior Related Work on Asymmetric Information.....	36
2.7.4.0 Theory of Contract.....	37
2.7.4.1 The Principles of Contract.....	38
2.7.4.2 The Purpose of Contract.....	39
2.7.4.3 How Contracts Works Between Lenders and Borrowers.....	40
2.7.4.4 Prior Related Work on Contract	41
2.7.5.0 Agency Theory	41
2.7.5.1 The Principles of Agency Theory.....	43
2.7.5.2 The Purpose of Agency	44
2.7.5.3 How Agency Works Between Lenders and Borrowers.....	45
2.7.5.4 Prior Related Work on Agency	46
2.8 Chapter Summary	47
CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	48
3.0 Introduction	48
3.1 Research Questions	48
3.2 Research Approach	49
3.3 Research Paradigm	51
3.4 Research Philosophy.....	51
3.5 Research Methods.....	53
3.6 Qualitative Research Methodology Justification	53
3.7 Similar Studies Using Qualitative Methods.....	54
3.8. Research Design.....	56

3.8.1 Types Research Design	56
3.8.2 Methods Use to Collect Data	57
3.8.3 Interview	57
3.8.4 Types of Interview	58
3.8.5 Semi-Structured Interview	58
3.8.6 Validity of the Research	58
3.9 Defining the Population and Obtaining a Sampling	59
3.9.1 Population	59
3.9.2 Sampling	59
3.9.3 Types of Sampling Technique	60
3.9.4 Snowballing Sampling	60
3.9.5 Profile of Participants	60
3.10 Process of Planning and Development of Qualitative Interview	61
3.10.1 Pilot Study	65
3.10.2 The Field Expirence	66
3.11 Qualitative Data Analysis	69
3.11.1 Thematic Dana Analysis	70
3.12 Coding Procedures	71
3.12.1 Open Coding	73
3.12.2 Axial Coding	75
3.12.3 Selective Coding	76
3.13. Good Practice Guidelines for Data Analysis	77
3.13.1 Credibility	77
3.13.2 Dependability	78
3.13.3 Conformability	79
3.13.4 Transferability	79
3.13.5 Ethical Considerations	80
3.13.6 Autonomy, Veracity and Informed Consent	81
3.13.7 Privacy and Confidentiality	82
3.13.8 Justice and Inclusivenes	83
3.13.9 Benefits and Harms	83
3.14. Reserach Direction	84
3.15 Chapter Summary	86
CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS	87
4.1 Theme 1: Business Loans	87
4.1.1 Credit Notes	88
4.1.2 Buy Now Pay Later	90

4.1.3 Hire Purchase	92
4.1.4 Reason Behind the Loan.....	94
4.2 Theme 2: Business Challenges	96
4.2.1 Accountants Fees or Agency Fees.....	96
4.2.2 Relationship with Bankers.....	98
4.2.3 Lack of Information	100
4.3 Theme 3: Sources of Funds	102
4.3.1 Family and Friends	102
4.3.2 Credit Agency.....	104
4.3.3 Grants	105
4.3.4 Banks	106
4.4 Theme 4: Terms and Conditions	109
4.4.1 Contract Documents	109
4.4.2 Payment Period.....	110
4.4.3 Charges or Fees	111
4.4.4 Sensitization	113
4.5 Theme 5: Scotland	115
4.5.1 Environment	116
4.5.2 Government	117
4.5.3 Support	120
4.5.4 Role of Job Centres	123
4.6 Theme 6: Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minorities	124
4.6.1 Language	125
4.6.2 Staffing	126
4.6.3 Trustworthiness	127
4.6.4 Other Barriers	128
4.7 Chapter Summary	130
CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	132
5.1 Reserach Question One	133
5.2 Reserach Question Two	134
5.3 Reserach Question Three	134
5.4 Reserach Question Four	135
5.5 Recommendations.....	136
5.6 Reserach Contribution	138
5.7 Future Study.....	139
5.8 Reserach Limitation	139
REFERENCES	141

APPENDICES	158
Appendix 1: SLR Table	158
Appendix 2: Interview guide	209
Appendix 3: Interview question	212
Appendix 4: Sample invitation letter to participants	214
Appendix 5: Individual consent form	216
Appendix 6: Pilot Interview Sample	218
Appendix 7: Sample of Main Interview Question	227
Appendix 8:Qualitative Data Analysis Template	231

List of Figures

Figure 2.1 Most Common Non-British Nationalities in Scotland 2020.....	20
Figure 3.1 Research Layers.....	49
Figure 3.2 Qualitative Field Investigation Map.....	62
Figure 3.3 Coding Techniques.....	72
Figure 3.4 Annotated Transcripts	73
Figure 3.5 Procedure for Analysing Interview	84

List of Tables

Table 2.1 Agency Theory Overview	42
Table 3.1 Research Approach	50
Table 3.2 Positivism and Interpretivism Comparison.....	51
Table 3.3 Research Philosohy	52
Table 3.4 Qualitative Method Employed in Access to Business Loan and Ethnic Minorities	55
Table 3.5 Profile of the Participants	61
Table 3.6 Relationship Between Research Objectives and Interview Guide.....	63
Table 3.7 The Main Interview Challeneges	66
Table 3.8 Pilot Study Fieldwork Experince	67
Table 3.9 Qualitative Data Analysis Selection	69
Table 3.10 Framework for Doing a Thematic Analysis	71
Table 3.11 Open Coding	74
Table 3.12 Axial Coding.....	75
Table 3.13 Selective Coding	77
Table 3.14 Research Direction Table	85
Table 4.1 Credit Note.....	90
Table 4.2 Buy Now Pay Later.....	92
Table 4.3 Hire Purchase	94
Table 4.4 Reasons Behind the Loan	95
Table 4.5 Business Loan	96
Table 4.6 Accountants Fee or Agency Fee	98
Table 4.7 Relationship with Bankers	99
Table 4.8 Lack of Information	101
Table 4.9 Business Challenges	101
Table 4.10 Family and Friends	103
Table 4.11 Credit Agency	105
Table 4.12 Grant	106
Table 4.13 Bank	108
Table 4.14 Sources of Funds	108
Table 4.15 Contract Document	110
Table 4.16 Payment Period	111
Table 4.17 Charges or Fees.....	113
Table 4.18 Sensitization.....	115
Table 4.19 Terms and Condition	115
Table 4.20 Environment.....	117
Table 4.21 Government	120

Table 4.22 Support.....123
Table 4.23 Role of Job Centre124
Table 4.24 Scotland124
Table 4.25 Language.....126
Table 4.26 Staffing.....126
Table 4.27 Trustworthines127
Table 4.28 Other Barriers129
Table 4.29 Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minorities129

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this research is to investigate the difficulties faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland. Based on published surveys in 2017, only 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business are in Scotland.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Snowball sampling techniques were used to recruit participants. 20 face-to-face, in-depth interviews were conducted with ethnic minority business owners in Scotland. The interviews were transcribed and then analysed using a thematic method of analysis.

Findings: This research found that lack of education, inability to apply online, lack of understanding of the English language, high interest rates, lack of trust, nationality issues and 5 years residency in the UK might be some of the reasons why ethnic minority owners of small businesses cannot access business loans in Scotland. Some factors such as credit ratings, information asymmetry, credit history regarding previous loan, strict process of loans, harsh credits check and strict rules could be reasons why there is only 3% of small business owners in Scotland are from ethnic minorities.

This research identified factors including too much paperwork, unnecessary questions from lenders, limited payback periods, fixed interest rates and slow responses from lenders as some of the terms and conditions discouraging interviewees from accessing business loans in Scotland. This research also identified factors such as professional fees, information opacity, and personal relationships with bankers as being important to accessing business loans whilst and not been aware of loans is one of the business challenges affecting ethnic minority business owners.

Originality/value – Some research has been conducted relating to ethnic minority owners of small business, but there is no research related to access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland in all aspects and context of this study.

Contribution and Recommendations – This research contributed to knowledge, policy and methodology. In terms of recommendation, this research recommended publicity and advertising, empowerment programs, reduction of interest rate and fees and education on how to apply for loan,

Keywords – Ethnic minority, small business, business loan, Scotland

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Overview

This research project explores ethnic minority owners of small business, access to business loan. The purpose of this chapter includes an overview of the chapter, the statement of the problem, definition of terms, the research aims and objectives, the research questions, the research rationale, the theoretical foundation, the conceptual framework, the research strategy and data collection and the structure of the research project. Finally, this chapter provides details of the thesis structure.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

According to Annamalai et al (2013:857) “*A problem statement is described in terms of scope, structure and its purpose. Analysis in problem statement is a critical element of a structured problem solving that has not been included in or explicated by traditional stage models of the process*”. The problem statement is well defined in simple terms to develop the solution to the problem. “*Problem Statement is a statement of the question that will be investigated in a research study*” (Ary, et al.:25). In this research project investigation was carried out about the problem statement for this project

The problem statement is a situation whereby only 3% of ethnic minority owners of small businesses are in Scotland as at 2017 (The Scottish Government, 2018). The goal of this research project is to improve on the rate and also look for possible solutions or alternatives to accessing business loans in Scotland.

A statement of the problem is the basis for this research project to carry out investigations which are needed to be addressed because the first proposition of any research project is the problem statement which needs to be accepted before considering the next proposition. According to Lunenburg and Irby (2008:114) *“The statement of the problem is a definition of what you investigated in your study. It is actually a formal and succinct version of the process you went through in selecting and delimiting your topic”*. However, this provides the investigations carried out in this project, hence, why the statement of the problem is relevant to this research project. Hernon and Schwartz (2009) state that an incomplete or absent statement of the problem could cause a project to be confusing.

The ideal is that all ethnic minority owners of small businesses have access to business loans in Scotland. What should be done is to look for the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland. What is expected or desired is to put facilities in place to encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to enable them to access these business loans.

The statement of the problem provides access to information and tools needed for this project. According to Gygi, Williams and DeCarlo, (2012:78) *“The problem statement serves several purposes. It serves as a great communication tool. It significantly clarifies the current situation by specifically identifying the problem and its severity, location and financial impact”*. However, the current situation might be the problem of accessing secondary data. Lunenburg and Irby (2008) noted that statements of the problem do provide solutions to the question of the research by clarifying, outlining and providing some useful suggestions to the examined problem or problems.

1.2 Definition of Terms

This study is centered on a specific set of people in a specific location, it is important to note a few key terms throughout this thesis. Thus, the following key terms are defined:

Ethnic minority: Scotland's Census (2018) defined ethnic groups as people with different cultural backgrounds. These are a small group of people who are not original descendants within a community. They could have different cultures, nationalities, traditions, beliefs and religions from the main population in that locality. In Scotland there are different ethnic minority group and population are increasing (Walsh *et al*, 2019).

Owners of Business: These are people who own businesses. They are entrepreneurs or sole proprietors, the business could be owned individually or by an entity which could be a family. This is also applicable to owners of small businesses. According to Turner and Endres (2017:34) *"Small-business owners are individuals who conceive, launch, and assume the risk for new economic activities in the form of a business venture"*.

Small business: These are businesses that are owned privately by a group, or individually, with more than 10 employees and the annual revenue is less than €10,000,000 (European Commission, 2017). Small businesses with 10 to 49 employees are called small businesses (The Scottish Government, 2018). This research focuses on small business because of the annual expenditure or income, the number of staff and the business size. Also the problem statement is based on small business businesses.

Business Loan: These are loans that are given directly to a company from lenders (Weltman, 2007). These are loans that are meant for business purposes and they are repayable at a particular period of time with an interest rate.

Scotland: Scotland is one of the four nations of the United Kingdom. Scotland is one of the most enhancing places for immigrants in both recent and ancient times (Worldatlas, 2019). Scotland is a small country which is part of the United Kingdom and it is close to England and the Atlantic. Scotland is known for its lush mountain and it is the second largest country in the United Kingdom. There are 5.29 million people living in Scotland, the four largest cities in Scotland by populations are Glasgow with 590, 507 people, Edinburgh with 459,366 people, Aberdeen with 195,021 people and Dundee with 147,285 people (Worldatlas, 2021). This research will focus on the four largest cities in Scotland during data collection process.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

1.3.1 Research Aim

This research project investigates the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland.

1.3.2 Research Objectives

The research objectives are as follows:

RO1. To identify the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland.

RO2. To critically identify the terms and conditions that will encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.

RO3. To examine how much awareness ethnic minority owners of small businesses have of accessing business loans in Scotland.

RO4. To identify what could be done to attract the highest number of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.

1.4 Research Questions

This research project will provide answers to the following research questions:

RQ 1. What are the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland?.

RQ 2. What are the opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loans in Scotland?.

RQ 3. How can banks encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.

RQ 4. What can be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland?.

1.5 Research Rationale

The rationale behind this research is based on the researcher personal motivation and the statement of the problem. This research project addresses the issue of 3% of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland as at 2017 (from the Small Business Survey Scotland, 2017 publication).

Many ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland are facing difficulties when applying for business loan. Some do face challenges like documentation issues, inability to read, lack of awareness of business loan and trust issues. This research will uncover some the reason why these challenges exist. This research project also try to solve this issue by investigating the reasons why low numbers of ethnic minority owners of small businesses are in Scotland. The goal is to improve on the low rate and look for possible solutions or alternatives to accessing business loans. What should be done is to look for the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans. What is expected or desired is to

put facilities in place to encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.

1.6 History of Asian Immigration to Scotland

The Irish people were the first people to migrate to Scotland before the Pakistani people migrated to Scotland. During the 19th century, the South Asian people were the first ethnic minority group to migrate to Scotland and they came through the seaports and settled in Glasgow. The Asian and black seamen were increasing during 1919. Some of the Asian and black seamen were not able to find work in Glasgow, some of the Asian and black seamen had to look for jobs in other industries such as steel plants, iron and coal mines around Lanarkshire area (Spencer 1997).

The India people migrated to Scotland during the 1920's. They were small numbers of men that migrated to Scotland, the India people who migrated to Scotland are not seamen but some of them are known or related to seamen seeking economic opportunities. Towards the end of 1920's the population of India people living in Glasgow increased to about hundreds and some of the India people spread to other cities in Scotland such as Dundee and Edinburgh. The India people population attracted the attentions of Scottish government (Spencer 1997).

Another ethnic minority group that migrated to Scotland is the Chinese people, during the 1950's some agricultural workers migrated from Hong Kong to the United Kingdom and Chinese people later moved to Scotland (Seawright, 2009).

During the Second World War the Asian and black people spread from the seaports to the industrial towns of the midlands, the north and to the forests of Scotland (Spencer 1997).

The Chinese people first of all settled in Glasgow during 1960's and the reason was because of the economic boom between 1950's and 1960's also because of the British hunger for foreign food (Seawright, 2009).

According to Walsh et al (2019:983) "*the proportion of the population belonging to a non-White ethnic group increased four-fold in both Scotland and Glasgow between 1991 and 2011*".

Recently Pakistani people are one of the most populous people in Glasgow. Nazir *et al*, (2021) started that in Glasgow there are a lot of Pakistani people living in the Southside of Glasgow specifically, the Pakistani people are the third demographic or social force after the Irish and the Scottish people in Glasgow South side.

It is important to note that some of the Asian people are first generation, second generation and third generation.

1.7 Research Strategy and Data Collection

This research project employed a qualitative research method; the data collection technique used in this research project is interview.

1.7.1 Qualitative Research

The qualitative research will represent a preliminary study and discovery nature. It will be based on in-depth personal interviews with ethnic minority owners of small businesses accessing business loans in Scotland. The qualitative research method is interpretive. Qualitative research's purpose is to contextualize, understand, and interpret (Stuckey, 2013). These aspects of the research try to contextualize the research project and to understand the problems as well as interpret the analysis and findings.

1.8 Structure of the Research Project

This research project contains five main chapters:

Chapter 1 of this research contains an overview, statement of the problem, research aim and objectives, the research questions, research rationale, theoretical foundation, conceptual framework, research strategy and structure of the research project.

Chapter 2 provides the critical review of literatures, up to date relevant and accurate academic journals and articles was reviewed, which focus specifically on ethnic minority owners of small businesses and their access to business loans in Scotland in general, including definitions, theories and a systematic literature review.

Chapter 3 presents the research methodology adopted in this research, the research approach of this research, the reason why the qualitative research method is employed in this research, the research design, the method use to collect data in this research, the data analysis process and the research direction for this research.

Chapter 4 elucidates the data analysis and discussion of findings, based on the data collected from ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. In each of the sub-themes, a table of analysis presents the summary of the findings; each of the findings was verified and some newly evolved issues were discovered from the data analysis.

Chapter 5 gives the main conclusions of this research project which are contribution to knowledge, policy and methodology. Notable recommendations such as publicity and advertising, empowerment programs, reduction of interest rate and fees and education on how to apply for loan. As well as future areas of studies and limitation of this study

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides a review of recent up to date related literature relating to access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland. This chapter is divided into seven parts. The first part of this chapter is about access to business loans, from the viewpoint of ethnic minority owners of small businesses, on the challenges they face when applying for business loans. The second part of this chapter discusses the type of lenders ethnic minority owners could borrow money from: family and friends, or from savings, which is the same as business owners acting as lenders, and from commercial lenders. The third part of this chapter concerns the process of business loans, the various types of loans and the terms and condition attached to loans, for instance the fully amortized term of loans and revolving business line-annual renewal. The fourth part of this chapter is a discussion about ethnic minority. The fifth part of this chapter discusses small businesses in Scotland while the sixth part of this chapter examines the types of small business loan: credit cards, operating lines, commercial loans, seasonal loans, overdraft checking, bank loans, letters of credit, factoring and credit unions. The final part of this chapter is about theories and concepts such as entrepreneurship, ethnic entrepreneurship, asymmetric information, the principle of asymmetric information, the purpose of asymmetric information, how asymmetric information works between lenders and borrowers and the previous related work on asymmetric information. Theories include the theory of contract, the principle of contract, the purpose of contract, how contract works between lenders and borrowers, the previous related work on contract, the principle of agency, the purpose of agency, how agency work between lenders and borrowers, and the previous related works on agency.

In this research, the researcher reviews numerous literatures, the researcher did systematic literature review producing a survey of previous studies in the area (Appendix 1: SLR Table). First of all the researcher identify some key literatures, created a survey table which includes the author name and year, the study of the title, the purpose of the research, the type of study, the theoretical foundations, the concepts dimension variables, the research questions objectives hypotheses, the research design, the key findings, the research contribution/implication, the observation/limitations and the locations.

2.1 ACCESS TO BUSINESS LOANS

Some people prefer to be self-employed, rather than relying on wages or salary payments. For these people, the major barrier is access to adequate funds to establish a business, although part of this funding will come from their personal funds (Ibrahim and Galt, 2011). Access to a business loan is one of the most important issues that affect small businesses. Thus, some entrepreneurs are discouraged because of the challenges of accessing business loans. Deakins *et al*, (2008) discovered that, based on the principle of asymmetrical information, some categories of small and medium enterprise owners will be affected by the biggest challenges in accessing bank finance. Information failure is also known as asymmetric information; this happens in any transaction whereby one party to an economic transaction has more material ability than the other. One such example is if the lendee possesses a greater level of information than the lender, or vice versa.

Cowling, Liu and Ledger (2012) researched small business financing in the UK before and during the current financial crisis. They discovered that bigger firms and the firms that are affected by a decline in sales are more to be expected to apply for external finance or maintain their request for external finance. In other words, some small businesses do not depend on internal finance, rather they depend on access to business loans. Deakins *et al*, (2005) conducted

interviews and validated that the local minority ethnic communities are a significant source for support, recommendations and sources of finance. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses normally make use of personal funds to finance their business. Weltman (2007) affirms that the common sources of personal loans used to finance businesses are home equity loans, credit cards, retirement plan borrowing and life insurance borrowing. However, it might be easier to access personal loans than business loans because lenders may require more documentation and evidence for business loans.

In the United Kingdom, small business lending markets experienced a dramatically greater decline than any other market during the global financial crisis. In 2012, only four banks in the United Kingdom accounted for over 80% of the loan originations (Mills and McCarthy, 2016). Sometimes the relationship affects small business owners' decision/ability to borrow from these agencies. Glantz (2015) affirms that, traditionally, small businesses do establish relationships with commercial banks. However, in recent times, it has been difficult for small business owners to access loans. Thus, the good news is that there are still some alternatives out there; apart from banks there are other lending agencies in town. Another pressing issue is immigration status. According to Dustmann and Preston (2001:353) "*Settlement of ethnic minority group who enter European countries on a refugee basis has become a political issue of considerable importance, local interest groups often oppose new settlements*". Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses find that their immigration status will not allow them the right to access formal business loans from lending agencies. Ethnic businesses experience many challenges in gathering the necessary capital to start up. One of the biggest challenges facing small business owners in the process of establishing their business, despite other challenges, is that if ethnic entrepreneurs were not able to source for formal or informal equity then their businesses will not prosper and develop (Volery, 2007). However, Scotland still has the highest percentage of external finance compared to England, Wales and Northern Ireland. Longitudinal Small Business

Survey LSBS (2018) argues that either businesses source for external finance or not in the last 12 months'. Looking at the United Kingdom countries, 6% of businesses in Northern Ireland source finance, 6% in England and 5% in Wales, compared with 10% in Scotland. Nevertheless, despite the high external source of finance, there is only a limited ethnic minority who run businesses in Scotland. Thus, there are drawbacks to running a business, although some business owners may not recognize the drawbacks right from the start. The best way to identify potential drawbacks of running a business is to work flexible hours. More than a few small business owners and entrepreneurs work seven days a week (Cohen, 2006). Some drawbacks in a small business can not be eliminated; even if the owners of the business work flexible hours or seven days a week the drawback could only be reduced to the bare minimum. Glantz (2015) noted that one of the challenges that small businesses face is tighter lending policies and procedures from commercial banks, for example tightened credit and raised fees. The lending policies and procedures from some lenders do not encourage small business owners to borrow money even if they have good potential for repayment. The financial crisis in 2008 started in retail banking and made many credit institutions reluctant to lend business owners and individuals because some financial institutions were more exposed and were exposed to riskier lending products and markets (Bank of England (2011) as cited in Cowling, Liu and Ledger, 2012). Prior to the 2008 financial crisis, lending policies and procedures were not as tight as compared to after the crisis. The 2008 financial crisis caused financial institutions all over the world to strengthen policies and procedures for lenders.

In order to access business loans it is of great importance for ethnic minority owners of small businesses to know about the different types of lenders.

2.2.0 TYPES OF LENDERS

There are several different types of lenders which come in all shapes and sizes, as do the loans themselves. Lenders have a limited say about how you run your business, they do not care where you find the money to do this and, furthermore, they do not care if the business is growing from year to year unless it impacts the debtor's ability to pay off the loan (Weltman, 2007).

2.2.1 Family and Friends

Some finance may be available from within the borrower's immediate circle. Small businesses often borrow from friends and family because of the comfort inherent in personal relationships. Their credit rating is usually not an issue, and repayment terms can be more flexible than those offered by commercial lenders. However, despite these advantages, there is a significant risk involved in interfamily borrowing. If you cannot repay the money, nonpayment can damage personal relationships (Weltman, 2007). Some ethnic businesses depend on support from family and other ethnic groups in terms of labour, or other matters such as money, to run the business. It is easier to borrow money in an informal way due to the relationship and network of ethnic people and the mutual trust among ethnic people. Furthermore, exchange of information is easier among ethnic group that is why it is easier for members of ethnic minorities to access informal loans (Masurel *et al.*, 2002). Nevertheless, Weltman (2007) argued that when borrowing from family and friends, it is best to keep things formal. One such way is to sign a promissory note detailing repayment terms. If the borrower subsequently defaults, following formalities will enable the lender to claim a bad debt deduction for the loan. Without formalities, the loan may be viewed as a non-deductible gift, leaving the lender without the funds and no tax write off.

2.2.2 Owners as Lenders

An owner as lender is a means whereby owners act as lenders. If the owner has the money, they can easily lend funds to their business and set the interest rates themselves. This can be a good loan arrangement because the lender can fix their own repayment terms that will not be onerous for the business and, at the same time, they will make money from the loan interest. For instance, a balloon loan can be used which requires the business to repay the principal all at once at some future date (for example, perhaps a year or two after the initial loan when the business anticipates receipt of funds from the project's completion). This relieves the business of the burden of making principal payments throughout the term of the loan (Weltman, 2007).

2.2.3 Commercial Lenders

Commercial lenders make loans to small as well as large businesses. A few years ago, small businesses who only wanted to borrow modest sums could not look to commercial banks. However, there is growing interest in the small business market and there are more resources for loans open to these businesses in America (Weltman, 2007). There are many commercial lenders in Scotland. Commercial lenders may include private financial institutions, mutual companies and commercial banks. Ethnic minority owners of small businesses usually face challenges accessing a business loan from commercial lenders, perhaps because of the period of the loan. In America context, Weltman (2007) noted that commercial lenders do not customarily make long term loans to small businesses, although exceptions are made to purchase real estate - such as factories, office buildings or retail premises. Short term loans run only for a year or two and so are not suitable for larger investment needs.

2.3 PROCESS OF LOANS

In recent times, many researchers have been conducting research into the process of loans and many researchers investigated more on the factor aspect of the process of a loan rather than the entire process (Dolezal *et al*, 2015). The process of loans is one of the challenges many people face from time to time, one challenging aspect can be the policy and regulatory framework. Mills and McCarthy, (2016) affirm that small business enterprises lending in the United Kingdom may have experienced slow movement due to certain contributory factors. These could possibly include a slowdown in investment and uncertainty in investment due to Brexit, notwithstanding the new Brexit rule that will be put in place may affect lenders, for instance some Europeans may not have the same rights as someone who is originally from Scotland.

There are major steps which small business owners could go through in processing a business loan. Banks or other financial institutions, such as credit unions, have different methods; for instance banks do not give loans to start ups, rather they prefer giving loans to existing businesses that are ongoing. However, some individuals obtain personal loans in order to use them to run a business. Weltman, (2007) made a point that business owners obtain personal loans, as the name implies, from their own resources. It is possible to obtain a personal bank loan based solely on the borrower's individual credit. This type of borrowing is hardly ever used in business. Interest rates on personal loans are usually high compared to other borrowing options.

Glantz (2015) noted that the savings rates are high and the fees are low in community banks compared to commercial banks. Community banks have become extra generous in giving business loans specifically to small businesses because of the service the banks render: one to one access to loan officers and the placing of more importance on a borrower's character rather than looking at the borrower's credit scores.

There is a need to know the various types of loans available and the terms and conditions of these loans.

2.3.1 Terms of Loans

The loan term is only one condition of a loan, it is critical because it can dictate or impact most or some of the other conditions (Jewells, 2012). Qualifying for a loan through commercial lenders, family and friends or owners as lenders are only the first step. Next, an applicant has to negotiate the repayment terms, often these are dictated by the lender on a non-negotiable basis. However, sometimes it is possible to work out terms favourable to the borrower, particularly with family and friends (Weltman, 2007). The loan terms and conditions from some lenders are structured. Nichols (2013) states that bank lenders structure the terms of a loan to match the useful life of the asset purchased from the loan proceeds. A loan to finance equipment could have a five to seven years repayment term or even be repayable within three years. The borrower needs to make regular reductions to reduce the principal balance. Loans are usually offered on either a long- or short-term basis. A short-term loan, in bank parlance, is one that must be repaid within a year, while a long term loan is any loan wherein the payment term is more than one year (Weltman, 2007). Thus, Nichols, (2013) noted that small business loan requests are usually meant for purchases of equipment, purchases of vehicles, business real estate purchases, business real estate improvements, refinancing existing business debts and for working capital.

2.3.2 Fully Amortized Term Loans

Fully amortized term loans are the best option for a client. A fully amortized loan is a loan which is usually spread out to the longest term feasible, given the purpose or collateral, and will simply mean that all principal and interest are paid off when the last payment is paid (if all payments are made on a timely basis). Fully amortized term loans can be either fixed rate or variable rate. A

fully amortized term loan is the easiest for a client to pay back because the longest term is usually offered and the payment is consistent or predictable (Jewells, 2012).

2.3.3 Evergreen Business Lines

Evergreen business lines are rare in banking. As the name implies, the line is open ended or with a distant maturity or renewal date. This, for example, may be 5 years, or 10 years. Even though this may be monitored less than a renewable line, and the requirement for resting the line may not be included in the loan terms, the lenders will still be watching it. They will usually have software systems in place that show variance in the line and how often it is paid down and drawn out. For example, if the borrower uses all the credit available and repays only the minimum payment for two years in a row, this will be a red flag to the lenders (Jewells, 2012).

2.3.4 Revolving Business Line- Annual Renewal

A revolving business line with annual renewal is similar to a credit card or home equity credit line, with one main difference. The primary difference, which is significant, is that each year the loan has a specific maturity date. This date allows for the lender to basically place the loan on demand or call the loan to be paid in full. A renewable feature will sometimes make this a non-event in the eyes of a borrower, but it is necessary to remember that the bank always has the option not to renew the line. This demand clause can catch a borrower off guard, especially if the line is not being used as intended (Jewells, 2012).

2.4.0 ETHNIC MINORITIES

Ethnic minorities are not a new phenomenon in the United Kingdom. Articles on ethnic minority businesses in the United Kingdom now have a considerable lineage, stretching back over 20 years, particularly focused on Asian entrepreneurs (Ward and Jenkins, 1984, as cited in Deakins *et al.*, 2007). Some academic scholars have been able to conduct research into ethnic minority

businesses in the United Kingdom using different approaches, different contexts and different population sampling. The term ethnic minority is extensively used in political and legal discourse where it is either descriptive or analytical (Kasatkina, 2003). Ethnic minority is also referred to as ethnic minority group.

According to Yusoff and Sarjoon (2016:146) "*Ethnic minorities are usually defined in contradiction to major groups with whom they coexist in political systems, as groups which experienced systematic discrimination and domination because of their numerical inferiority and a host of historical and sociological factors*". Thus, ethnic minorities are a group of people within a neighborhood which has different tradition, culture or nationality from the main population in the community. Yusoff and Sarjoon, (2016) argue that there is no proper and clear definition of ethnic minority but many researchers have attempted to define the term. However, Volery (2007) noted that ethnic ownership economy consists of small- and medium-sized businesses owned by ethnic or immigrant entrepreneurs and their co-ethnic helpers and workers; ethnic control economy refers to industries, occupations, and organization of the general labour market in which co-ethnic employees (not owners) exert appreciable and persistent economic power. Deakins *et al.*, (2005) studied minority ethnic enterprise in Scotland. The purpose of their study was to provide information on the distinctive issues and distinctive importance of minority ethnic businesses in Scotland. They discovered that over 3% of all the self-employed in Scotland are minority ethnic business owners, and furthermore, the most vital concentration of minority ethnic enterprises is in Glasgow which is the largest city in Scotland. Thus, ethnic minority businesses play a vital role in economic development and growth, also in creating jobs for the unemployed and students, as well as linking up the people in the local community. One of the pieces of research conducted by Deakins *et al.* (2007) revealed that the essence of networks within local communities gives a vital source of advice. There are many diverse attitudes towards community to be found within ethnic minorities. Dustmann and Preston (2001) argue

that the mindsets of ethnic minority populations regarding communities are possible vital influence on social exclusion and welfare of ethnic minorities. Deakins *et al.* (2005) maintain that traditionally, minority ethnic communities have had robust local networks, which have provided resources both financially and socially. It has been noted that the robust local networks that give informal finance for minority ethnic business owners also provide social capital, or informal sources of advice and support. Masurel *et al.* (2002) affirm that socio-cultural connections appear to create a more than average loyalty between the ethnic business owner and his clients. Ethnic culture seems to create specific customer relationships. On the other hand, Deakins *et al.* (2007) examine the nature of strong social and family ties within ethnic minority businesses in Scotland and argue that such relationships have complication and divergent effects on business and entrepreneurial development. In terms of borrowing money to finance a business from family and friends, once a family member or a friend borrows money to finance a business and subsequently defaults in repayment, this will lead to a loss of trust and the relationship will be damaged.

2.4.1 Ethnic Minorities Trends

The total population of people living in Scotland has change over time between mid 2011 and mid 2018 the population of people living in Scotland increased from 5,299,900 people to 5,438,100 people, which are about 138,200 people. The increase is 2.6% (National Records of Scotland, 2019).

In Scotland there are different ethnic minority groups, the most popular groups are among the Asia people and the Africa people compared with other ethnic minority groups.

In year 2011 census, it shows that the total populations of ethnic minority adults residing in Scotland grow from 5% to 8% between 2001 till 2011 (National Records of Scotland, 2016).

There is a possibility that ethnic minority populations might increase in the nearest future.

According to Walsh *et al* (2019:984) “New projections suggest that by 2031, around 20% of Glasgow’s total population (and 25% of children) will belong to a non White minority group”.

Glasgow is one of the largest cities in Scotland, if the population of ethnic minority increase by 20% then there is possibility that the low 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland may increase.

There are only 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business as at 2007 till 2013 and this figure has not change (The Scottish Government, 2013). However, in 2015 the constant 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business dropped from 3% to 2% (The Scottish Government 2016a). In 2016 the 2% of ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland increased back to 3% (The Scottish Government 2016b). In 2017 the 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business remain constant (The Scottish Government 2018).

Figure 2.1: Most common non-British nationalities in Scotland 2020

Source: National Records of Scotland, (2021)

From the figure 2.1 in pervious page, the polish people are the highest non British people living in Scotland followed by the Irish people then the Nigeria people who are one of the most populous ethnic minority and some of the Nigeria people are owners of small business.

In year 2020 the three cities with the largest proportion of non British residents are Aberdeen City, the City of Edinburgh and the Glasgow City (National Records of Scotland, 2021).

2.5 SMALL BUSINESSES IN SCOTLAND

Numerous researchers often call small businesses micro businesses. Micro businesses are businesses that employ fewer than 10 persons and whose annual income or annual expenditure is less than €2,000,000 (European Commission, 2017). In other words, the equivalent of €2,000,000 is approximately £1,800,000. A small business is a business which is owned or inherited and managed independently and is limited in size and in income. Small businesses are businesses with 10 to 49 employees are called small businesses (The Scottish Government, 2018). Some examples are local kebab shops, African stores and Chinese restaurants. Some of these businesses employ more than ten employees, some are even family businesses run by either or both the father, mother or children. Their income might be more or fewer than £1,000,000 (European Commission, 2017).

According to Scottish Enterprise (n.d) there are numerous factors impacting on Scotland's economic growth. One, among others, is the United Kingdom's leaving of the European Union. Scotland wanted to remain within the European Union, therefore this might result in a second referendum for Scotland to gain their independence and thus they could apply for re-admission to the European Union. LSBS (2018) opine that businesses in England and Scotland were more likely expected to employ people than those in Northern Ireland and Wales in the next 12 months (England 15% and Scotland 14%, compared with Northern Ireland 11% and Wales 11%). Thus, in terms of employment opportunity in Scotland, small business owners are one of

the employers of labour. Deakins *et al.*, (2005) researched minority ethnic enterprise in Scotland. The purpose of the scoping study was to lay emphasis on the distinctive issues and distinctive significant of minority ethnic businesses in Scotland; they found out that minority ethnic business owners account for just over 3 per cent of all self-employed in the nation. This 3% has increased and the expected percentage is 14% as at 2018. The highest rates of self-employment were in the Pakistani, Chinese, Indian and Bangladeshi communities. In Scotland the number of registered minority ethnic businesses is over 4,500 as at 2005 (Deakins et al., 2005). In Europe, businesses operated by persons from minority ethnic groups have always been present, but three changing historical circumstances have increased their salience and visibility over the past decades (Volery, 2007). In Scotland there are many ethnic minorities living, working and schooling in Scotland; many of these ethnic minorities are immigrants. Volery (2007) claims that firstly, huge immigration from former colonies, Southern Europe and North Africa has been responsible for the reasonable migration flow. Secondly, three decades of economic restructuring has been responsible for a fundamental transformation of the labour market and a general shift away from employment in large firms to self-employment in small ones.

2.6 TYPES OF SMALL BUSINESS LOAN

There are diverse types of small business loans which small business owners could access. Some researchers classified small business loans into two, personal loans and business loans. Weltman (2007) asserts that there are two main categories of loans; are personal and business loans. Personal loans are loans from an individual based on personal credit rating. While business loans are loans for business purpose, lenders reviewing the business loan applications will look at the business' credit and business' assets

2.6.1 Credit Cards

Credit cards are one of the quickest and simplest ways to increase credit score for loan in the future. Credit card owners do enjoy access to credit. Some credit card agencies may offer a very low interest rate in order to attract customer, however, once the customer defaults in paying back the money there will be a big increase in the interest rate (Glantz, 2015). Banks such as NatWest, Santander and Barclays offer credit cards to existing customers while shops including M&S and Tesco also offer credit cards. It is one of the less stressful means to access a business loan. One of the disadvantages of credit cards is that credit cards encourage people to spend more money which they do not have and go over budget. They also charge borrowers a huge amount of interest if the balance is not paid at the end of the month. Credit card borrowing is one of the types of small business loans which many small business owners start their businesses with. As the business becomes established, it can obtain credit cards in the company name. These credit cards typically have a line of credit that can be used to pay business expenses (Weltman, 2007).

2.6.2 Operating Line

Operating Line is one of the types of small business loans which is sometimes referred to as operating line of credit or line of credit. Banks may grant operating lines based on the borrower's inventory and the finance is from 60% to 90% within 90 days (Nichols, 2013). One good thing about an operating line of credit is that it allows the borrower to overcome short term cash flow problems. Furthermore, it allows borrowing up to the cash amount and paying off the loan in monthly installments. Line of credit is one of the types of business loan which is similar to a revolving loan. Line of credit has a fixed cap on how much you can borrow. The line of credit generally runs for a fixed term, such as two years, but can usually be renewed. The limit may even be increased if the borrower maintains good credit. Thus, as the loan is repaid, the borrowing capacity is replenished (Weltman, 2007). An operating line of credit is quite similar

to a credit card. For example, if there is a £25,000 line of credit and £5,000 is borrowed, the borrowing power is reduced to £20,000. However, once the £5,000 (plus interest) is repaid, the credit limit becomes £25,000 pounds again.

2.6.3 Commercial Loans

A commercial loan is one of the sources of credit for small business owners. Commercial loans are the most common type of business loan. The loan may be a general purpose loan, for example the loan can be used for purchasing inventory, launching a new product line or marketing, or the loan can be used for a single purpose, for example to acquire a new machine for the company (Weltman, 2007). A commercial loan is a short term loan and the repayment period is from 30 days to one year. Furthermore, a commercial loan can be granted in advance to a business owner.

2.6.4 Seasonal Loan

A seasonal loan is one of the dozens of different types of business loans and structures. Seasonal loans are loans in which the payment is structured to meet the seasonality or variable nature of the business. The best example of this is with farmers. Farmers are almost always seasonal. Seasonal payments take fragile timing and require care by a lender (Jewells, 2012). A seasonal loan has a good loan repayment period, although during low sales periods it may be difficult to pay expenses.

2.6.5 Overdraft checking

Overdraft checking is tied exclusively to the business and is a variation on a line of credit. A business owner can obtain a stated credit line that they can tap into at any point in time by writing a cheque in any amount. This form of borrowing helps protect the business' credit rating by ensuring adequate funds to pay bills in a timely manner, assuming, of course, that the

overdraft credit limit is not exceeded. Usually, to obtain an overdraft credit line, applicants must apply for it as they would any other loan. The difference is that the application process is usually a very simple one-page form without supporting documentation. The time from request to approval may take days or even weeks, depending on the lenders (Weltman, 2007).

2.6.6 Bank Loans

Bank loans are one of the types of loan available to small business owners. Bankers have high loan approval requirement. Larger banks can also issue corporate credit cards to small businesses which could be used to access a business loan (Glantz, 2015). In Africa, the banks intended for financing small businesses where small business owners can access business loans at an affordable rate are called micro finance banks. Some countries in Africa have different kinds of micro finance banks at different locations and in different cities. Nichols (2013) stated that banks are not flexible in the areas of loan structure, in security (also known as collateral), personal guarantees provided by business owners, length of repayment term and loan documents. No matter how good the business' credit is, certain lenders stipulate that an owner must give their personal guarantee for a bank loan under a set amount. However, having good business loan credit makes it easier to obtain the loan and, usually, on more favourable repayment terms (Weltman, 2007). However, bank officers might not have perfect information about access to, or application for, a loan for borrowers, who are small business owners accessing business loans (Deakins et al, 2008).

2.6.7 Letters of Credit

A letter of credit is typically used by a lender as a means of collateral for a third party. Some lenders, specifically small lenders, do not offer this as a product. Nevertheless, it is necessary to be aware of all possible options (Jewells, 2012). A letter of credit could be called a letter of understanding, banker's commercial credit or documentary credit. A letter of credit is not really

a loan but it provides a guarantee from the bank to a third party. The terms of a letter of credit state that the third party may draw funds on the letter of credit. The letter of credit is also commonly used as a way of facilitating international trade (Nichols, 2013).

2.6.8 Factoring

This is a special type of borrowing based solely on a company's accounts receivable (Funds which are owed from sales already made). In effect, the business is converting actualized sales into cash using the receivables as collateral. Usually, money can be obtained within 24 to 48 hours (Weltman, 2007).

2.6.9 Credit Unions

Credit unions are non-profit organizations with two key goals. The first is to render services at a lower cost and, the second is to share the proceeds among members of the credit union or to those who participate in the credit union. Many credit unions offer the same service and products which banks do. Credit unions do offer less rigid loan requirement which is one good aspect of them (Glantz, 2015). Thus, many communities, cities and organizations in Scotland have credit unions, for example the Glasgow credit union, NHS credit union and Renfrewshire wide credit union. A credit union is a member-owned cooperative which means it is owned by its members.

2.7 THEORIES AND CONCEPTS

2.7.1 The Theory of Entrepreneurship

There is no single definition of entrepreneurship. Some researchers attempt to define entrepreneurship from their own point of view, some may define it based on a sociological, economic and psychological point of view (Bula, 2012). Thus, few researchers have been able to define entrepreneurship. Mishra and Zachary (2015) defined entrepreneurship as value creation, which is a process whereby an entrepreneur identifies external opportunities and makes use of

the identified opportunities. Entrepreneurship is the act of being an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur is someone who undertakes innovations, finance, risk and business activities in a way to transform innovations into economic goods or services. It should be noted that, ethnic minority owners of small business are also entrepreneurs.

Chepurenko (2015) argues that a new definition of entrepreneurship theory developed in the last decade may lead to not only a major conceptual shift but also to entirely new directions of research in other areas of the social sciences. This could be called the entrepreneurship research driven imperialism, having a penetration into rather new areas of social research. Volery (2007) affirms that most initial theories on ethnic entrepreneurship stem from sociology. The disadvantage theory and the cultural theory are two major theories that can be drawn from this field to explain ethnic entrepreneurship

Mishra and Zachary (2015) noted that the theory of entrepreneurship is a multidisciplinary field that integrates ideas from many disciplines; it involves economics, sociology, strategy, psychology, decision sciences and finance. Chepurenko (2015) stated that the importance of the entrepreneurship field was recognized by the launch in 1995 of the Global Entrepreneurship research award which bestows awards to outstanding people who had a huge impact on the discipline of entrepreneurship. Simpeh (2011) asserts that entrepreneurship theories and research remain significant to the development of the entrepreneurship field. There are diverse types and approaches to entrepreneurship theories, which are the 1755 Cantillon's theory, 1949 Marshall's approach to entrepreneurship, 1975 Shultz approach, 1971 Knight's approach, the biological theory of entrepreneurship and the sociological theories of entrepreneurship (Bula 2012). Entrepreneurship research is without doubt one of the most dynamic areas within the cluster of socio-economic and managerial sciences in the last 20– 25 years (Chepurenko, 2015). Thus, Cederberg and Villares-Varela (2018) claim that literature on ethnic entrepreneurship has

focused on structural factors, group characteristics or a combination of both when explaining the entry and/or success of different ethnic groups in/ to self-employment.

Simpeh (2011) noted that the economic entrepreneurship theory has deep roots in the classical and neo-classical theories of economics. The economic entrepreneurship theory explores the economic factors that enhance entrepreneurial behavior. This theory has both classical and neo-classical theories. The classical theory deals with free trade and the mode of production, while the neo classical theory deals with the economic system. Thus, in Scotland, there are many opportunities for ethnic minorities to explore. In order to be entrepreneurial, entrepreneurship research should explore and use such opportunities (Chepureenko, 2015).

Simpeh (2011) studied the entrepreneurship theories and empirical research, whereby he focuses on economic entrepreneurship theory, psychological entrepreneurship theory, sociological entrepreneurship theory, anthropological entrepreneurship theory, opportunity-based entrepreneurship theory and resource-based entrepreneurship theory. Bula (2012) researched the evolution and theories of entrepreneurship. He focused on various approaches of entrepreneurship such as classical theorists like Richard Cantillon - the entrepreneur who equilibrates supply and demand in the economy by bearing risks or uncertainty. Mishra and Zachary (2015) studied the theory of entrepreneurship in which they focus on entrepreneurial value creation. Chepureenko (2015) researched entrepreneurship theory, new challenges and future prospects. He focused mainly on Russia, and claims that entrepreneurship theory in Russia is under-developed.

2.7.2 The Theory of Ethnic Entrepreneurship

This research project focuses on the theory of ethnic entrepreneurship. Waldinger (1986) defined ethnic entrepreneurship as any business which is owned by immigrant and ethnic group members. Some researchers refer to ethnic groups as immigrants because they migrated to a

specific community. However, many in Scotland were born here and did not immigrate. Volery (2007) affirms that an substitute term used to 'ethnic' is 'immigrant entrepreneurs', which, in turn, would only include the individuals who have really immigrated over the past few decades. The word ethnic could be referring to a set of networks and connections among different people who share the same background, race, sex, culture and belief. The phrase ethnic entrepreneurship is by no means a new phenomenon, as it is a firm part of any migration, most obviously observed in the United States, where the foreign-born have been overrepresented in small businesses since 1880 (Barret *et al.*,1996 as cited in Volery, 2007). Thus, ethnic entrepreneurship research could be traced back to the early 1900's with the concept of the stranger as trader in connection with the middleman theory and the enclave theory (Simmel 1950; Sombart 1914; Weber 1930). Middleman theory is also known as middleman minority, which deals with producers and consumers, buyers and sellers etc. In the United States of America, the middleman theory has a major relevance. According to Min and Kolodny (1994, :181) "*middleman has the following characteristics: (1) concentration in small business, (2) providing services to minority customers, (3) dependence on U.S. corporations for their supply of merchandise, (4) strong ethnic cohesion, (5) subjection to stereotyping, and (6) hostility from the host society*". Some of the characteristics of the middleman theory in the United States are also present in Scotland. The second theory is enclave theory. Ethnic enclave is a place where there is a high concentration of an ethnic group or high characteristics of culture and economic activities. Portes (1981) as cited in Light *et al.*, (1994) claims that immigrant enclaves have two characteristics: (1) numerous immigrant owned business firms that employ numerous co-ethnic workers and (2) Spatial clustering of enterprises. The first characteristic of immigrant enclaves is common in many countries. Desiderio (2014) noted that, at a little cost, immigrant entrepreneurship has much to contribute to the creation of jobs and economic revitalization and growth. Similarly, Cederberg and Villares-Varela (2018) researched ethnic entrepreneurship and

the questions of agency, in which they found that the entrepreneurs are active agents who play a vital role in shaping ethnic businesses. In many cases, ethnic entrepreneurship may also be seen as a new form of self-employment, be it in the formal or informal sector. It is noteworthy that this phenomenon used to be rather rare in Europe (Masurel *et al.*, 2002). It is vital to note that ‘Ethnics’, on the contrary, does not exclude immigrant or minority groups. The term ‘immigrants’ will however be used hereafter when speaking in particular of the early stages in the process of ethnic entrepreneurship, that is, when an ethnics group is new in a host society and its members can out rightly be considered as ‘immigrants’ (Volery, 2007). It is also important to note that many ethnic in Scotland are not immigrants.

Ethnic entrepreneurship has become a popular concept in a modern multi-cultural society (Masurel *et al.*, 2002). Ethnic entrepreneurship has become a significant aspect of modern urban life and fulfils a major economic and social role for ethnic communities. The restructuring of the Western economies have changed the situation for foreigners for the worse, but, at the same time, given rise to businesses with low economies of scale. This presents a new chance for immigrants to regain lost ground, but only if they are not held back by immigrant policies or subjected to invisible barriers, such as discrimination. The power of the socio-economic context, or ‘opportunity structure’, will continue to have an effect on the decision to enter self-employment (Volery, 2007).

2.7.3.0 Asymmetric Information

This research will also focus on the theory of asymmetric information. According to Izquierdo and Izquierdo (2007:858) “*The theory of asymmetric information has proven to be a very fruitful framework for the analysis of many types of market*”. The main reason why the theory of asymmetric information is used in this research is because it is a suitable theory that fits in with the loan market. Salehi, Rezaie and Ansari (2014) researched the corporate governance and

information asymmetry. They take the stance that there are two major types of asymmetric information; adverse selection and moral hazard. Numerous researchers used asymmetric information in their research and the theoretical foundation was based on asymmetric information (Akerlof, 1970; Lewis, 2011; Salehi, Rezaie and Ansari 2014; Spread 2015). Thus, the aim of the research is to investigate the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland. One of the challenges is information, and not just information, but having the right information at the right time. There is a saying that “if you are not informed you could be deformed”. According to Lewis (2011:1535) “*Information asymmetries are exacerbated in online transactions, where the buyer typically does not view the good in person*”. In other words, the buyer could be the ethnic minority owner of small business and the seller could be the lending agencies. Thus, the lending agency may not disclose all the information concerning the business loan. Disclosure of information is very important in a business. Lewis (2011) research shows that disclosure costs have an effect on how much information the seller decides to post, and therefore the prices he/she obtains. Relating the disclosure of information in the context of this research, whereby the seller is the lending agency and the buyer is the ethnic minority owner of a small business, when applying for a business loan there is a need for the lending agency to disclose all the relevant information; sometimes there might be hidden charges or additional costs attached to the business loan. This cost could be default charges, overdraft charges or annual interest rate on the business loan. Also the ethnic minority owner of a small business needs to disclose all the information needed in obtaining a business loan. Lewis (2011) takes the stance that disclosure is costless. It is better to disclose all the necessary and relevant information because it will not cost anything. However, if borrower does not disclose all the relevant information when applying for a business loan, this may lead to refusal of the loan. “*One of the influential factors in investment decisions is to have appropriate and new information. Since the required information is asymmetrically distributed among*

people, it can cause various results about one subject”(Salehi, Rezaie and Ansari, 2014:1829).

However, before a loan is approved the lending agencies issuing the business loan normally make their decision based on the supporting information submitted when borrowers apply for a business loan.

Akerlof (1970) used asymmetric information as one of the models with automobiles. In his research he discovered that trust is very important in any transaction. Apart from having the necessary and relevant supporting documentation, trust is one of the vital determinants in issuing loans. For example, if a borrower wants to access an informal loan, maybe from family or friends, the family or friend will issue the loan based on trust and may not consider the relevant supporting documentation which would be needed by a lending agency issuing formal loans. Lofgren, Persson and Weibull (2002) believe that asymmetric information is a common feature; the seller of goods usually knows more about their quality than the prospective buyers. The buyer of an insurance policy usually knows more about their individual risk than the insurance company. Thus, the lending agencies often know more about business loans than the borrower in some circumstances. This is supported by Spread, (2015:124) *“The term ‘asymmetric information’ has, however, come to be used more loosely for circumstances in which one agent is better informed than another.”* A similar view is held by Lofgren, Persson and Weibull (2002) wherein one side of the market is more informed than the other side. In this case the one side could be the ethnic minority owner of a small business accessing a business loan and the other side could be the lending agencies issuing the loan, who may be more informed than the ethnic minority owners of the small business accessing the loan. However, this is not accepted by De Meza and Webb (2016) who argue that their concern is whether the evidence for asymmetric information has been correctly interpreted. Lofgren, Persson and Weibull (2002) concur with this view. Other efforts to test for the predicted effects of asymmetric information have produced indistinct results (Lofgren, Persson and Weibull, 2002). The term ‘asymmetric information’ is

then not entirely suitable in some circumstances. People having the same information are not the same as perfect information, even if perfect information implies that everyone has the same information (Spread, 2015). Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses may think they have the same information as the lending agency issuing a business loan when applying for one.

2.7.3.1 The Principle of Asymmetric Information

The principle of asymmetric information deals with the distribution of information between two or more parties. Asymmetric information is *“the situation in which one of the two co-operation partners is better informed than the other one is described as asymmetric information. Problems resulting from this are economic disadvantages for one of the parties, the inefficient use of resources, and the resulting losses of welfare”* (Schieg 2008:48). The lender may have more information than the borrower or the borrower may have more information than the lender.

According to Sagi and Pataki (2009:691)

“Asymmetric information distribution means that some sellers are always informed on the quality of goods they offer, and consumers cannot recognize the differences in quality so they cannot form their preferentiality based on the quality of goods”.

In the context of this research the sellers would be the lending agencies while the consumers would be the ethnic minority owners of small businesses. In a two-sided market, information systems can serve as intermediaries between the buyers and the sellers, reducing the search costs buyers must pay to obtain information about the prices and product offerings available in the market (Yan, Yu and Zhao, 2015). In another context Stroebel (2016) shows that integrated lenders have greater information about the construction quality of individual homes and exploit this information to lend against higher quality collateral, decreasing foreclosures by up to 40%. In the finance context, it is argued by many that the fundamental cause of this finance gap is the information asymmetry that exists between the provider and the candidate recipient of finance. Arguably, the information asymmetry problem has been exacerbated in recent years by further

centralization in bank lending decisions and the introduction of computerized business credit-scoring (Lean and Tucker, 2001). According to Okuyan (2014:699) “*Asymmetric information is a factor that decreases the efficiency of markets*”.

2.7.3.2 The Purpose of Asymmetric Information

The purpose of asymmetric information cannot be over emphasized. As stated by Sagi and Pataki (2009) asymmetric information can cause a market collapse. The unfavorable pressure of asymmetric information can be reduced. The potential consumer can engage experts to test the quality of the item that he/she intends to buy. Ikeda (2019) describes the purpose of asymmetric information as an important aspect for understanding the disruption of the supply of credit. The supply of credit could be a business loan. Crawford, Pavanini and Schivardi (2015) discussed asymmetric information; their model of oligopolistic competition predicts different banks’ interest rate reactions to an increase in adverse selection, depending on the level of competition. Asymmetric information has different forms; the financial market can adopt any of the following types: adverse selection, moral hazard or monitoring costs (Benezuk, 2003). Adverse selection is one of the different forms of asymmetric information. According to Yan, Yu and Zhao (2015:3) “*A lender suffers adverse selection when he is not capable of distinguishing among borrowers and investment projects with different credit risks when allocating credit*”. The lending agencies find it difficult to approve business loans to ethnic minority owners of small business. The problem of information asymmetry, and the resulting adverse selection and moral hazard, are further compounded by certain trends which are evident in the banking sector (Lean and Tucker, 2001).

Similarly, according to Schieg (2008:48):

“Adverse Selection describes the quality uncertainty of the client with respect to his contractor. The client does not know the qualities or the exact qualification of the contractor before the contract is closed. The contractor might conceal lacking or negative qualities or a very qualified contractor might not tell about his positive qualities”.

In the context of this research, the client is the ethnic minority owner of a small business and the contractor is the lending agency. According to Okuyan (2014:700) *“moral hazard can be described as the misuse of funds borrowed. As moral hazard refers to the situation where the creditor cannot monitor the actions of the borrower, this situation is also called as the hidden action”*. Moral hazard problems are based on the theory of asymmetric information. It means that policy holders sometimes cause damage intentionally or they do not pay enough attention to avoiding risk (Sagi and Pataki, 2009). The monitoring costs could include a transaction cost or additional fees, *“lenders would face costs for screening safe applicants from risky applicants and for monitoring borrowers’ actions, and consequently they might require additional fees, that is to say they would transfer their transaction costs to borrowers”* (Okuyan 2014:700).

2.7.3.3 How Asymmetric Information Works Between Lenders and Borrowers

Research on asymmetric information between lenders and borrowers has been researched but using different terms. Ikeda (2019) takes the stance that entrepreneurs and a representative bank make a loan contract, where asymmetric information plays a critical role. Ikeda lays emphasis on the fact that there are a large number of entrepreneurs. Without loss of generality, there is a representative bank. Both entrepreneurs and the bank are competitive. One view, expressed by Yan, Yu and Zhao (2015) is that one of the apparent causes of information asymmetry in the traditional lending business is where the borrower has information that the bank ignores or does not have access to. A similar view was held by Bebezuk (2003), that there is asymmetric information in a financial contract when the borrower has information that the lender ignores or does not have access to.

According to Yan, Yu and Zhao (2015:2):

“To overcome this information asymmetry problem, the borrower signals and conveys information about him/herself and the investment project’s characteristics, while the lender searches credit information and screens the loan applicant. In the traditional banking system, the bank makes loan decisions and is in charge of collecting and evaluating credit information”.

The information asymmetry problem is one of the common problems between lenders and borrowers. In credit markets, asymmetric information problems arise when borrowers have private information about their creditworthiness that is not observable by lenders (Gail and Stebunovs, 2009). The information asymmetry problem may not only result in good lending prospects being rejected by providers, but also poor prospects being accepted by providers (Lean and Tucker, 2001).

According to Okuyan (2014:700):

“Credit markets are commonly affected by imperfections due to the presence of asymmetric information. Lenders might lack the necessary information to set the price of loans, which should reflect the borrowers’ riskiness, that is to say their probability of default”. Asymmetric information exists in business loans and other loans or markets.

2.7.3.4 Prior Related Work on Asymmetric Information

Several pieces of research have been conducted using asymmetric information. Kuniyoshi and Daisuke (2014) researched information asymmetry in small/medium credit guarantee schemes, and found that credit risk and the amount of guaranteed loans indicates that a public credit guarantee programme is influenced by asymmetric information. Sagi and Pataki (2009) studied consumer behavior and asymmetric information theory, they reviewed and analyzed the theory of asymmetric information and agent theory. In their studies they present the possibility of bankruptcy or market disturbance because of asymmetric informativeness of market participants. Entrepreneurs seek loans from banks for projects, but entrepreneurs do not get funded due to the riskiness of some entrepreneurs (Ikeda, 2019). In the context of this research, the entrepreneurs could be the ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. Asymmetric Information also exists in other countries. Crawford, Pavanini and Schivardi (2015) measured the consequences of asymmetric information and imperfect competition in the Italian lending market. Gail and Stebunovs (2009) examined whether asymmetric information problems exist in the corporate loan market, and whether ownership of loans provide lenders the incentive to

mitigate asymmetric information problems. Stroebel (2016) empirically analyzed credit market outcomes when competing lenders are differentially informed about the expected return from making a loan. Lean and Tucker (2001) studied information asymmetry, small firm finance and the role of government. Bebezuk (2003) carried out research on asymmetric information in financial markets. Okuyan (2014) explored whether asymmetric information causes problems in credit markets. Schieg (2008) researched the strategies for avoiding asymmetric information in construction project management. Albertazzi, (2017) conducted researched on asymmetric information and the securitization of small and medium enterprise loans. Despite the wide range of research conducted on asymmetric information, Ikeda (2019) argued that there is still a gap to be filled because the literature available on asymmetric information in financial markets is nearly 50 years old. A similar view was expressed by Gail and Stebunovs (2009) that few studies provide direct evidence of asymmetric information problems in credit markets.

2.7.4.0 Theory of Contract

The theory of contact is relevant to this research, it will be vital to know what a contract is. According to Wu (2006:491) *“Contracts are private trading arrangements customized to fit specific economic circumstances”*. A contract could be an agreement between two or more parties, or it could be a written agreement signed by both parties. A contract is not just an agreement but a legal agreement. *“Contracts are seen as tools for realizing individual self-determination by means of voluntarily entering legally binding agreements. This notion of individual autonomy is not a historically given, but was established and expanded through social struggles leading from “status to contract”¹ as the main determinant in our lives”* (Gutmann, 2013:3). Some people usually take their time to go through the legal document before signing it, on the other hand some people do not take the time to go through every detail of the contract, maybe because of the wording of the contract.

A similar view is held by Miric (2016:1):

“Sometimes parties to a contract agree on the wording of the contract, but disagree about its meaning. In such cases, the goal of purposive interpretation is to identify a legal meaning, within the limits of the language actually used, which best achieves the purpose of the contract in question”.

In the context of this research, the ethnic minority owners of small businesses are willing to sign a contract but they might not be happy with the meaning of the contract. This could be because of some hidden charges or terms and conditions that are applied to the contract. The process of contracting is not purely consensual if the parties are not fully aware of all external actions that may empower or bind them to a contract. The parties obviously cannot be aware of external consequences unless they experience them or otherwise learn of their existence (Barnes, 2008).

2.7.4.1 The Principle of Contract

Contract theory deals with financial and economic behaviors of two or more different parties.

According to Schmidt, (2017:490) *“contract theory deals with a fundamental problem of economic cooperation, two (or more) parties can jointly generate a surplus in addition to what each of them can generate on their own”*. In a contract one party is more self-sufficient than the other party. In the context of this research, the lending agency issuing a business loan is more self-sufficient than ethnic minority owners of small businesses. As stated by Miric (2016:10) *“A contract represents an expression of the autonomy of private will of the contractual parties. It gives rise to reasonable expectations among the parties to it”*. The reasonable expectation is for the parties not to default in irrespective of any circumstances. Barnes (2008:1130) argues that *“The objective theory of contracts also furthers the ideals of freedom of contract and personal autonomy by limiting the effectiveness of manifestations to gestures known to the other party”*.

To an economist, a contract is an agreement under which two parties make reciprocal commitments in terms of their behaviour - a bilateral coordination arrangement. Of course, this formulation touches on the legal concept of the contract (a meeting of minds creating effects in

law), but also transcends it (Brousseau and Glachant, 2002). Despite the fact that contract is an agreement, a contract could be exploitative. According to Koszegi (2014:1104) “*a contract is exploitative if the economically central considerations driving it derive from trying to profit from the agent’s mistake, and other considerations or constraints are nonexistent, not binding, or not central*”. In some contracts there are agency problems. The agency problems could be when the agent has access to private information before the contract is signed which could be ubiquitous in the real world (Hoppe and Schmitz, 2013). This could be one of the challenges facing ethnic minority owners of small businesses accessing a business loan.

2.7.4.2 The Purpose of Contract

Schmidt (2017) believes that the contract theory focuses on situations in which only a few parties interact with each other (often just two). This situation could cause problems such as a financial contracting problem. “*A typical problem in financial contracting is the so-called risk-shifting problem, which has been studied in economics and finance. This problem, which usually arises in the context of a lender incentive to give influence to the risk of his project*” (Inoue, Miyake and Takahashi, 2013:893). Risk is inevitable, even if there is contractual agreement it would not guarantee that there will be no defaulter in a contract. Some lending agencies assess the risk involved in issuing business loans to ethnic minority owners of small businesses. Also, when ethnic minority owners of small businesses want to access business loans they look at the risk. “*When parties to a contract agree on the wording of the contract, but disagree over its meaning, the goal of purposive interpretation is to identify a legal meaning, within the limits of the language actually used, which best achieves the purpose of the contract*” (Miric 2016:3). In other words, the purpose of a contract is the legal agreement which is enforceable and verifiable.

According to Barnes (2008:1157):

“The objective theory of contracts is the dominant philosophy in contract law for determining mutual assent to an enforceable agreement. The reasons are clear. It is a pragmatic rule, basing the determination of mutual assent on tangible, verifiable external evidence, rather than relying on problematic proof of subjective intent. It enforces the reliance and expectation interests of the parties”.

The theory of contract is not all about legal agreement, although there are some functions of the theory of contract. According to Bayles (1983:813) *“At least three distinct functions can be served by a theory of contract (or other part of) law: prediction, explanation, or justification. Most theories seek to serve all these functions but differ in the relative emphasis they place on them”.*

2.7.4.3 How Contracts Work Between Lenders and Borrowers

Contract theory analyses the optimal design of incentive schemes (“contracts”) that induce the involved parties to behave more efficiently (Schmidt, 2017). The optimal design of incentive could be the business loan by the lending agency, who is the lender, involving the ethnic minority owner of a small business, who is the borrower. Inoue, Miyake and Takahashi (2013) studied the circumstance of how the lender could protect his assets as well as the borrower’s assets when the borrower is a levered firm or has unhealthy assets. The contractual agreement is a promise and a legal document which could be used in a court of law. Barnes (2008) emphasizes that the promisee's affairs can be planned based on what is spoken or written, communications that can also be subsequently referenced when questions regarding performance and obligation arise. Despite the fact that a contract is an agreement, it could be incomplete. According to Koszegi (2014:1110) *“A contract is incomplete if it leaves the details of some transaction that the parties care about to be determined at a later time”.* Contracts are incomplete because there are significant information and measurement costs surrounding most business transactions. When a large number of possible contingencies exist regarding future

events, the use of the fully contingent complete contract of economic theory is too costly (Brousseau and Glachant, 2002).

2.7.4.4 Prior Related Work on Contract

Related research has been conducted on contracts by different scholars in differently related contexts. Wu (2006) researched on contract theory and agricultural policy analysis, focusing on some development and discussion. Schmidt (2017) studied the contract theory contributions of Hart and Holmstrom who are respected scholars. Inoue, Miyake and Takahashi (2013) researched risk incentive problems between a lender and a borrower and possible ways for mitigation. Hoppe and Schmitz (2013) conducted an experimental study on contracting under incomplete information and social preferences. Gutmann (2013) focused on the theory of contract and the concept of autonomy. Brousseau and Glachant (2002) wrote a book on the economics of contract theories and their applications. Barnes (2008) researched the objective theory of contracts. Ang (1992) first attempted to differentiate the problems of finance of the privately held small businesses from their larger counterparts and found that there is a prevalence of implicit contracts in small business. Koszegi (2014) examined the behavioural contract theory.

2.7.5.0 Agency Theory

Shapiro (2005) defined agency theory as a relationship between one party acting on behalf of another party. Relating agency theory to the context of this research, the lending agency could be acting on behalf of the principal in issuing business loans to ethnic minority owners of small businesses. Also, the ethnic minority owners of small businesses may seek the assistance of a firm or someone to help them apply for business loans acting on their behalf.

According to Shapiro (2005:273):

“Agency theory borrows jargon from agency law, but adopts neither its definition nor its central focus. The legal definition of agency is much narrower even than that employed in the economics paradigm of agency theory, let alone that found in the other social sciences”.

Agency theory has been in existence for several decades, not just in finance but in different related fields. According to Janda (2006:34) *“Agency theory has been a very successful and active research area in economics, finance, management and related subjects all the time since the beginning of the seventies”.* Agency describes the contractual relationship between two parties, which are agent and principal. The principal is said to act on behalf of the agent. Agency theory is vital but it is a controversial theory (Eisenhardt, 1989). However, even if agency theory is a controversial theory, this theory has been in existence for a long time, and many people have been using agency theory. Agency theory has been developed on a relatively high level of abstraction, but the theory is, to a limited extent, tested in empirical situations (Landstrom, 1993). Thus, much research has been conducted on agency theory. The table below contains the key idea of agency theory, the unit of analysis, the human assumptions, organizational assumptions, information assumptions, the contracting problem and the problem domain of agency theory.

Table 2.1 Agency Theory Overview

Key idea	Principal-agent relationships should reflect efficient organization of information and risk-bearing costs
Unit of analysis	Contract between principal and agent
Human assumptions	Self-interest, Bounded rationality, Risk aversion
Organizational assumptions	Partial goal conflict among participants, Efficiency as the effectiveness criterion, Information asymmetry between principal and agent
Information assumption	Information as a purchasable commodity
Contracting problems	Agency (moral hazard and adverse selection) Risk sharing
Problem domain	Relationships in which the principal and agent have partly differing goals and risk preferences (e.g., compensation, regulation, leadership, impression management, whistle-blowing, vertical integration, transfer pricing)

Source: Eisenhardt (1989:59)

2.7.5.1 The Principle of Agency Theory

The principle of agency theory is concerned with resolving two problems that can occur in agency relationships (Eisenhardt, 1989). Since the principal is acting on behalf of the agent in the course of carrying out his or her duties, the principal may incur a cost which is perceived as agency cost. Agency costs are one of the internal costs attached to the agent relationship that occur due to the misalignment of the interest between the agent and principal. They embrace the cost of examining and picking up a suitable agent, collecting of information to fix performance benchmarks, watching to control the agent's action, bonding costs and the loss due to the inefficient decisions of the agents (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). There are several agency problems.

According to Eisenhardt (1989:71):

“Agency theory is most relevant in situations in which contracting problems are difficult. These include situations in which there is (a) substantial goal conflict between principals and agents, such that agent opportunism is likely (e.g., owners and managers, managers and professionals, suppliers and buyers)”.

The agent opportunism is also likely to business loan agency and ethnic minority owners of small business.

Landstrom (1993) noted that the basic premise of agency theory is that both principals and agents are assumed to be rational economic-maximizing individuals. Therefore, the separation of ownership and control will result in decisions by the agent which are not always in the principal's best interest and costs will arise (agency costs) associated with bringing the agent's behavior into line. For example, costs arise which are incurred by the principals when monitoring and controlling the behavior of the agent (so-called monitoring costs), and costs incurred by the agent in demonstrating compliance with the wishes of the principal (so-called bonding costs). Agency costs arise from many sources: the costs of recruitment, adverse selection, specifying and discerning preferences, providing incentives, moral hazard, shirking, stealing, self-dealing, corruption, monitoring and policing, self-regulation, bonding and

insurance, agents who oversee agents, as well as failures in these costly corrective devices (Shapiro, 2005). Agency costs include monitoring costs, borrowing costs and residual loss (Panda and Leepsa, 2017).

Residual loss could be define as part of the cost which the agent incurred during his/her duty for the principal (Beisland, Ndaki and Mersland, 2019). In the context of this research the principal is ethnic minority owners of small business. Panda and Leepsa (2017) suggested way to reduced residual loss is for the owners to incur the bonding cost and the monitoring cost.

The cost of agency is one of the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses because the agency cost includes the borrowing cost and some of this cost might be hidden.

According to Eisenhardt (1989):

“Agency theory is concerned with resolving two problems that can occur in agency relationships. The first is the agency problem that arises when (a) the desires or goals of the principal and agent conflict and (b) it is difficult or expensive for the principal to verify what the agent is actually doing. The problem here is that the principal cannot verify that the agent has behaved appropriately. The second is the problem of risk sharing that arises when the principal and agent have different attitudes toward risk. The problem here is that the principal and the agent may prefer different actions because of the different risk preferences”.

The second problem might exist when ethnic minority owners of small businesses want to access business loans because it is difficult or expensive for lending agencies to verify what the ethnic minority owner of the small business is actually doing. Also it is very risky to grant a loan to someone you do not really know, even if they have collateral.

2.7.5.2 The Purpose of Agency

The purpose of agency is for the agent to work for the principal based the authority of the principal. According to Panda and Leepsa (2017:77) *“Agency relationship is also a kind of contract between the principal and agent, where both the party work for their self-interest that leads to the agency conflict”*. One of the reasons why both parties work for their own interest might be because of the contractual agreement. Agency theory encompasses several theoretical

perspectives. “*The agency theory ideas on risk, outcome uncertainty, incentives, and information systems are novel contributions to organizational thinking, and the empirical evidence is supportive of the theory, particularly when coupled with complementary theoretical perspectives*” (Eisenhardt 1989:58). Some lending agencies normally take risks in issuing loans to ethnic minority owners of small businesses, however, in some circumstances, the risk are shared between both parties. Bendickson *et al.*, (2016) stated that there are two perspectives in agency theory which have emerged: principal-agent research and positivist agency theory. Principal-agent research identifies two possible agency problems: risk-sharing and agent monitoring. The two problems are linked in that a divergence in the area of risk-sharing creates information asymmetry which, in turn, reduces the principal’s ability to monitor agent behavior. A typical problem in financial contracting is the so-called risk-shifting problem, which has been studied in economics and finance. This problem usually arises in the context of a lender’s incentive to give influence to the risk of his project (Inoue, Miyake and Takahashi 2013). There are three agency problems under uncertain conditions: adverse selection, moral hazard and hold-up. In adverse selection, a firm must ascertain whether an adviser possesses the required expertise. Moral hazard occurs when the principal is unsure as to whether the agent has exerted him or herself to the maximum. Hold-up describes an occasion when a party attempts to renegotiate a contract after other parties have made investments specific to that relationship (Mole 2002).

2.7.5.3 How Agency Works Between Lenders and Borrowers

There is agency problem between lenders and borrowers. The problem could be because of the risk involved in non-current assets such as goodwill, intellectual property and specifically intangible assets which are not physical assets. So, Bharati and Crain (2001) argued that small firms have more intangible assets, such as growth opportunities, than tangible assets, such as real estate. Since the former assets are riskier than the latter, and are heavily influenced by agency

problems, it is more difficult for small firms to obtain conventional loans from financial intermediates. Small business loan guarantees are, therefore, necessary for some smaller firms. Ethnic minority owners of small businesses are smaller firms so they should have growth opportunities and, in turn, the ethnic minority owners of small businesses should be able to access business loans even if some loans are conventional loans from financial intermediates. One of the most fundamental applications of agency theory to the relationship between lender and borrower is the derivation of the optimal form of the lending contract (Janda, 2006). The relationship of agency theory between lenders and borrowers is a normal phenomenon which occurs because both parties will have to look for the best or most favorable conditions in the contract before accepting the loan.

2.7.5.4 Prior Related work on Agency

Inoue, Miyake and Takahashi (2013) studied the lenders' risk incentive as well as the borrowers' risk incentive and their relationship. In particular, they focused on an effective finance strategy for a lender, for which the lenders' expected profit is valued by taking the borrowers' risk incentive into account and they found out that incentive do influences borrowers. So, Bharati and Crain (2001) examined the inter-relationship between risk-taking, agency problems, and small business financing. Janda (2006) researched agency theory approach to the contracting between lender and borrower. Janda mentioned only a selected few problems of agency theory approach within the wide area of contracts between lenders and borrowers. Bitler, Moskowitz and Vissing-Jorgensen (2005) developed a principal-agent model in an entrepreneurial setting and tested the model's predictions using unique data on entrepreneurial effort and wealth in privately held firms. Landstrom (1993) studied agency theory and its application to small businesses, one of the findings is lack of knowledge is one of the problems between agent and principal. Mole (2002) researched business advisers' impact on SMEs using the agency theory approach and his findings was based client relationship. Panda and Leepsa (2017) conducted research into agency

theory, they reviewed the theory with evidence on problems and perspectives. They found out the cause of agency problem

2.8 Chapter Summary

The researcher was able to discuss the existing studies regarding access to business loans. Specifically, these are the formal and informal; the types of lenders, which are family and friends; owners as lenders; and commercial lenders. The researcher explained the process of loan and the term of loan. Furthermore, the researcher reviewed articles on ethnic minority, small business in Scotland, the various type of small business loan such as credit cards, operating lines, commercial loans, seasonal loans, overdraft checking, bank loans, letters of credit, factoring and credit unions. This research focused on four key theories and concepts; among these are the theory of entrepreneurship, the theory of ethnic entrepreneurship, asymmetric information, theory of contract and agency theory.

In this chapter the researcher took time to conduct a systematic literature review on related articles in different locations on small businesses and ethnic minorities but there were few or no articles on access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. The researcher came across some core issues during the literature review process, some ethnic minority owners of small business depend on lending from family and friends, some ethnic minority do not prefer commercial lenders. Another core issues that was indentify during the literature review process was the process of loans, the terms and condition of business loan. In the literature the researcher found out that the population of ethnic minorities is increasing but there are still 3% of ethnic minority owners of small business despite the increase.

During the process of reviewing different literature, the researcher was able to develop interview question based on some of the sub section in this chapter. See (Appendix 3: Interview Questions). The interview questions will be use to conduct interview in the next chapter.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter is all about the research methodology utilized in this research, the data collection method, the analysis also the steps the researcher took to conduct this research.

The research methodology employed in this study is qualitative investigation in order to answer the research questions. Greener (2008) noted that research methodology is more concerning the researcher's approach towards the research and the researcher's knowledge of research and the strategy the researcher selects to answer research questions. This study addresses specific research questions, stated below:

3.1 Research Questions

***RQ1.** What are the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland?.*

***RQ2.** What are the opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loans in Scotland?.*

***RQ3.** How can banks encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.*

***RQ4.** What can be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland?.*

In this chapter the research design gives a description of the methodology utilized for this study.

The diagram below represents the research layers.

Figure 3.1: Research Layers

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.2 Research Approach

Research approaches are strategies used in research which could be the plan and procedure of conducting a study. There are three approaches to research; these are deductive approach, inductive approach and abductive approach. The table below gives a clear insight into the three approaches:

Table 3.1: Research Approach

	Deduction	Induction	Abduction
Logic	In a deductive inference, when the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true	In an inductive inference, known premises are used to generate untested conclusions	In an abductive inference, known premises are used to generate testable conclusions
Generalisability	Generalising from the general to the specific	Generalising from the specific to the general	Generalising from the interactions between the specific and the general
Use of data	Data collection is used to evaluate propositions or hypotheses related to an existing theory	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns and create a conceptual framework	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, locate these in a conceptual framework and test this through subsequent data collection and so forth
Theory	Theory falsification or verification	Theory generation and building	Theory generation or modification; incorporating existing theories where appropriate, to build a new theory or modify an existing theory

Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019)

The aim of this study is to investigate the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland by searching for unexpected data and developing new concepts about access to business loans. This study will adopt an abductive approach because it combines both inductive and deductive reasoning, which is a discovery-oriented process.

The reason why the researcher chose this research approach is because it is the most relevant in terms of being able to answer the research questions in the best possible manner. The researcher had to go and talk to every ethnic minority owner of a small business at their business premise, so a focus group would have been difficult to arrange by getting all the paperwork in place. And observation is probably not possible except they give me permission to follow them around.

3.3 Research Paradigm

Groenewald (2004) defined research paradigm as a pattern, model, principles or replica to follow to achieve the appropriate result. This chapter will discuss the methodology employed in this study. It is, therefore, important to discuss the pattern. According to Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2008:331) *“Paradigm is a consensual pattern in the way scientists understand, and inquire into the world”*.

Methodology, ontology, methods and epistemology are all the element of paradigm (Scotland 2012). The researcher applied paradigm in this research project because different methods were used to conduct this research project. The table below illustrates the comparison between positivism and interpretivism:

Table 3.2 Positivism and Interpretivism Comparison

	Positivism	Interpretivism
Basic Principles View of the world	The world is external and objective	The world is socially constructed and subjective
Involvement of researcher	Researcher is independent	Researcher is part of what is observed and sometimes even actively collaborates
Researcher’s influence	Research is value free	Research is driven by human interest
Assumptions What is Observed	Objective, often quantitative, facts	Subjective interpretations of meanings
How is knowledge developed	Reducing phenomena to simple elements representing general laws	Taking a broad and total view of phenomena to detect explanations beyond the current knowledge

Source: Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2008)

3.4 Research Philosophy

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019:130) *“the term research philosophy refers to a system of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge”*. This section of the study describes the system of ideas about the development of understanding to address the problem statement of this study. The table below shows the definition of research philosophy,

the explanation of research philosophy and how, and why, research philosophy is applicable to this research.

Table 3.3 Research Philosophy

Philosophy	Definition	Explanation	How it is apply to this research And why
1. Ethnography	According to Mohajan (2018, p.34) <i>“The word ethnography comes from Greek ethnos, which means ‘folk, people, and nation’, and grapho which means ‘I write’. Therefore, ethnography has a setting in anthropology, which means ‘portrait of a people’”</i>	Ethnography is a method of business research which is the end product of ethnographic research. Ethnographics are designed to convince readers of the reality of the events and situations described, and the plausibility of the analyst’s explanations. Ethnography is a strategy that is imbued with realism. (Bryman, and Bell, 2011)	Ethnography will be applied in this research because it will be used to show the reality of the problem statement.
2. Ontology	Ontology is about the nature of reality and existence. (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015)	Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2015) noted that ontology is philosophical assumptions about the nature of reality	This research will make use of ontology to find out the nature and existence of the reality
3. Epistemology	Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2015) defined epistemology as a general set of assumptions about ways of inquiring into the nature of the world	Epistemology is about the theory of knowledge and helps researchers understand the best ways of enquiring into the nature of the world. (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015)	Epistemology will be applied in this research in order to understand the best ways of enquiring.
4.Paradigm	According to Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2008:331) <i>“Paradigm is a consensual pattern in the way scientists understand, and inquire into the world”</i> .	Paradigm consists of the following components: ontology, epistemology, methodology, and methods. (Scotland 2012).	Paradigm will be applied in this research because different methods will be used to conduct this research
5.Research Method	Grover (2015) defined research methods as ways to get information from the sample. Research methods seek to address the research questions or hypotheses.	The ways of getting information from the sample could be in the form of interviews, questionnaires or observation (Murtonen and Lehtinen, 2005)	This research employed the use of research methods to get information from the sample, which could be from interviews.

Sources: Mohajan, (2018); Bryman, and Bell, (2011); Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, (2015);Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, (2008); Scotland, (2012); Grover, (2015); Murtonen and Lehtinen, (2005).

3.5 Research Methods

Research methods refer to precise activities designed to produce data, for example observation, questionnaires, focus groups and interviews (Greener, 2008). Similarly, Dawson (2002) stated that research methods are the tools the researcher uses to collect data. In this chapter, the tools used to collect data will be discussed. Also, the techniques and procedures will be discussed, according to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, (2012:4) who state: *“The term methods refer to techniques and procedures used to obtain and analyze data”*. The characteristics of a research method includes questionnaires, observation and interviews as well as both quantitative (statistical) and qualitative (non-statistical) analysis techniques (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012). In this research, some characteristics of research method will be employed, for instance conducting interviews.

The term *methodology* *“refers to the theory of how research should be undertaken...It is important to have some understanding of methodology in order to make an informed choice about the research”* (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012:4). Nevertheless, Collis and Hussey (2014) noted that research methodology is the whole approach to the entire process of the research. Research methodology incorporates by the research problem, the assumptions the researcher utilizes in the research and the approach the researcher conducts the study. Thus, research methodology is the philosophy or general principle which guides the research. (Dawson 2002). The characteristics of research methodology consist of methods such as qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods. This research is conducted using the qualitative method.

3.6 Qualitative Research Methodology Justification

Research can be conducted using qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods, which is the combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods. This depends on the research topic, the research questions and the problem statement of the research. It is important to note that

qualitative research depends on the type of information employed to study a phenomenon. Furthermore, qualitative studies base their accounts on qualitative data such as sentences, narratives and words (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler 2008). However, it is due to the type of information, for instance the research topic and research question, that this research adopts the qualitative method. Another reason why this research adopts the qualitative method is because of the issue of 3% of ethnic minority business owners who could access business loans in Scotland, as at 2017, according to the Small Business Survey Scotland (2017) publication. Thus, qualitative research usually investigates the generation of a problem and the investigation would not use a comprehensive survey. Instead, it would be depending on observation and/or deeper and less structured interviews (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler 2008). This research will try to solve this issue by investigating the reasons why low numbers of ethnic minority owners of small businesses are able to access business loans.

3.7 Similar Studies Using Qualitative Methods

Many studies on access to business loans and ethnic minorities have adopted qualitative techniques (for example, Deakins, *et al.*, (2008); Rahman, Ullah and Thompson, (2018); Faroki, (2014); Haron *et al.*, (2013); Kung'u, (2011); Bone *et al.*, (2017); Coleman, (2000); Chaganti and Greene, (2002); Deakins, Whittam and Wyper, (2010); Deakins *et al.*, (2009); Deakins, Majmudar and Paddison, (1997); Deakins, Ram and Smallbone, (2003); Hussain and Matlay, (2007); Irwin and Scott, (2010); and Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam, (2010)). The table below shows a list of qualitative research approaches adopted by these researchers.

Table 3.4 Qualitative methods employed in related prior studies regarding access to business loans and ethnic minority studies

Authors	Year	Topic	Methods
Rahman, Ullah, and Thompson	2018	Challenges and Issues facing Ethnic Minority Small Business Owners: The Scottish experience	Qualitative
Bone et al	2017	Detecting Discrimination in Small Business Lending	Case Study
Faroki	2014	Factors Influencing the Financing of Business Start-ups by Commercial Banks in South Africa	Qualitative
Haron <i>et al</i>	2013	Factors Influencing Small Medium Enterprises (SMES) in Obtaining Loans	Case Study
Kung'u	2011	Factors Influencing SMEs' Access to Finance: A Case Study of Westland Division, Kenya	Case study
Deakins, Whittam and Wyper	2010	SMEs' access to bank finance in Scotland: an analysis of bank managers' decision making	Case Study
Irwin and Scott	2010	Barriers faced by SMEs in raising bank finance	Qualitative
Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam	2010	Racism: A barrier to entry? Experiences of small ethnic minority retail businesses	Semi Structured Interview
Deakins, <i>et al</i> .	2009	Minority ethnic enterprise in Scotland	Case Study
Deakins <i>et al</i> .	2008	SMEs' Access to Finance: Is there still a debt finance gap?	Case Study
Hussain and Matlay	2007	Financing preferences of ethnic minority owner/managers in the UK	Qualitative
Deakins, Ram and Smallbone	2003	Addressing the business support needs of ethnic minority firms in the United Kingdom	Qualitative
Chaganti and Greene	2002	Who are ethnic entrepreneurs? A study of entrepreneurs' ethnic involvement and business characteristics.	Case Study
Coleman	2000	Access to Capital and Terms of Credit: A Comparison of Men- and Women- Owned Small Businesses	Case Study
Deakins, Majmudar and Paddison	1997	Developing success strategies for ethnic minorities in business: Evidence from Scotland	Qualitative

Source: Generated by the researcher

The above table 3.4 indicates the previous qualitative studies regarding access to business loan. Some of the studies are different or a little similar from this research. Rahman, Ullah, and Thompson (2018) did qualitative study but they did not focus on access to business loan. While faroki (2014) did a qualitative study but his study was not in Scotland. Irwin and Scott (2010)

also did qualitative study but they did not focus on ethnic minority owners of small business. Hussain and Matlay (2007); Deakins, Ram and Smallbone (2003) did qualitative study but their studies is not specifically in Scotland. Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam (2010) use semi structure in interview to collect data, but their studies focus on retail businesses, while the rest authors did case study. This research is different from previous studies in terms of topic and research method.

3.8 Research Design

There are numerous definitions of research design but none of the definitions has been able to fit in different context. Research design is like a plan of action on how to collect data, how to measure the data and how to analyze the data (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008). Similarly,

According to Pandey and Pandey (2015:18)

“A research design is simply the framework or plan for a study that is used as a guide in collecting and analyzing the data. It is a blueprint that is followed in completing a study. Research design is the blue print for collection measurement and analysis of data. Actually it is a map that is usually developed to guide the research”.

These sections will discuss the blueprint for collection of data. Greener (2008) noted that research design is the whole blueprint or approach on how to investigate a project. It involves quite a lot of work and reading.

3.8.1 Types of Research Design

There are three types of research designs: descriptive, correctional and experimental. A single study may have more than one research design. The type of research design relies largely on the goal of the research (Adams and Lawrence, 2015).

3.8.2 Methods Use to Collect Data

This section discusses the method of data collection employed in this research. There are several methods which could be employed to collect data in research. The methods of data collection in qualitative research could include interviews, observations and/or focus groups. The primary means employed in collecting the data in this research is interviews because it's most the appropriate means of collecting data for this research. Interviews will be elaborated on in the following section.

3.8.3 Interview

Interviews are one-on-one conversations directed by a researcher that can take place in person, over the phone, or via e-mail. The one-on-one interview may inspire the participant to take the research more seriously. Face to face interviews are specifically rich sources for observing nonverbal cues such as facial expressions, hand gestures, pauses, and posture (Adams and Lawrence, 2015). One on one, or personal, interviews were conducted with ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland. Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2008) noted that a personal interview (i.e face-to-face communication) is a two way conversation initiated by an interviewer to obtain information from a participant. The differences in the roles of interviewer and participant are pronounced. They are typically strangers, and the interviewer generally controls the topics and patterns of discussion.

Bolderston (2012) noted that in interview the researcher is interested in the individual participant. The reason why interview is used is because the researcher is interested about individual ethnic minority owners of small business.

The researcher did face to face interview, the reason behind it is because the researcher can observe voice, intonation and body language during the interview process which is one of the

advantages of face to face interview (Opdenakker, 2006). Another advantage of interview is that the participant can express their own viewpoint in private (Bolderston, 2012).

The researcher used the concept of probing. The reason why the researcher decided to do semi structure interview is because the researcher will be able to ask probing questions and it allow clarification of issues that are raised (Bolderston, 2012).

3.8.4 Types of Interview

There are different types of interview, but in qualitative research interviews can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured. In a structured interview, the researcher uses a very detailed interview guide-line similar to a questionnaire in quantitative studies. One good thing about semi-structure interview is that it gives the interviewee to follow their opinion rather than asking particular questions (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008). Thus, in order to discover more information from ethnic minority owners of small business, this research will adopt semi-structured interviews

3.8.5 Semi-Structured Interviews

Flexibility is one of the unique features of semi structured interviews compared with other structured interviews. The interviewer has a base set of probing questions or topics that they will follow, Thus, the interviewer may have some follow up questions that will be more important (Adams and Lawrence, 2015).

3.8.6 Validity of the Research

In order to accurately describe something, the measure used must be valid. Conducting a pilot study with a smaller sample is a good way to test the measures and work out any challenges prior to conducting the full study (Adams and Lawrence, 2015). A pilot study will be conducted,

which will be the preliminary study with a small number of ethnic minority owners of small business in order to test the measures and procedures.

3.9 Defining The Population And Obtaining A Sampling

3.9.1 Population:

Adams and Lawrence (2015) define population as the group of people, animals, or archives that the researcher is involved in investigation. Residency, occupation, gender, age and time frame are some of the characteristics that define a population. The smaller and more clearly defined the population, the easier it is to conduct the research that adequately describes that population. The population used in this research is ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. Dawson (2002) noted in sampling the researcher could select some individual's if it is not feasible to get in touch with all the individuals in the research population.

3.9.2 Sampling

A Sample is a subset of the population that is meant to represent the full population from which the data are collected. Sampling is the procedure used to obtain the sample. It is also the process of choosing a sample (Adams and Lawrence, 2015). The population of this research is ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland and the sample of this research is ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. The basic ideal of sampling is by chosen some of the aspect in a population, conclusions might be drawn about the whole population (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008). Thus, by selecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses from the three largest cities in Scotland, this might be able to draw conclusions about the entire population in Scotland.

3.9.3 Types of sampling Technique

Sample of a study could be selected in a numerous several ways and the method employed could be based on the preference of the researcher and the research methodology (Dawson 2002). Based on the context of this research, and the research methodology used, snowball sampling has been adopted.

3.9.4 Snowball Sampling

Adams and Lawrence (2015) define snowball sampling as the process whereby the participants recruit others into the sample. Snowball sampling is typically used to seek out members of a specific population who are difficult to find or who might be distrustful of a researcher. Similarly, Dawson (2002) noted that it is not easy to speak to each individual within the research population. Because of these challenges, the best method is to use snowball sampling. Snowball sampling is particularly helpful if the researcher wants to sample subjects that are not easy to discover, because they are not registered anywhere as a population (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008). Snowball sampling would best be used for a smaller, harder to reach subset of ethnic owners of small businesses.

3.9.5 Profile of Participants

The researcher considered ethnic minority owners of small businesses who might have already accessed business loans or tried to apply for business loans recently or in the past. The profiles of some of the participants are illustrated in the next page:

Table 3.5: Profile of the Participants						
Participant Number	Fictive Name	Gender	Type of Business	Nationality	Business Location	Number of Employees
P001	Abi	Male	Barber's Salon	Kuwait	Glasgow	12
P002	Giza	Male	Food Business	Pakistan	Glasgow	17
P003	Chen	Male	Chinese Medical Clinic	China	Glasgow	11
P004	Ade	Male	Counselling Services	Nigeria	Aberdeen	13
P005	Mark	Male	Café	Albanian	Glasgow	13
P006	Nnake	Female	Food	Nigeria	Dundee	12
P007	Bobby	Male	Fast Food	Syria	Glasgow	18
P008	Ifeoma	Female	African Store	Nigeria	Edinburgh	14
P009	Anu	Female	Food	India	Edinburgh	15
P010	Robert	Male	Fast Food	Hong Kong	Glasgow	16
P011	James	Male	Italian Takeaway	Albanian	Glasgow	16
P012	Isah	Male	Grocery Store	Egypt	Glasgow	14
P013	Umar	Male	Grocery Shop	Iran	Glasgow	12
P014	Hassan	Male	Fast Food	Pakistan	Glasgow	14
P015	Abdul	Male	Convenience Store	Pakistan	Glasgow	13
P016	Fahad	Male	Fast Food	Pakistan	Glasgow	14
P017	Ola	Male	Facility Management	Nigeria	Dundee	16
P018	Humza	Male	Off License Convenience Store	Pakistan	Glasgow	17
P019	Bola	Female	Restaurant Takeaway	Nigeria	Aberdeen	15
P020	Naeem	Male	Retail	Pakistan	Glasgow	13

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.10 Process of Planning and Development of Qualitative Interview

This section describes the process that the researcher took when planning and developing the qualitative interview. According to King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019:52) *“It should come as no surprise that there cannot be a single universal protocol to follow for developing a qualitative interview study”*. In the research, the researcher followed four phases in planning and developing the qualitative interview. Figure 3.2 illustrates the phases taken to conduct the qualitative field work investigation.

Source: Generated by the researcher

The first phase involved systematic literature review, list of questions, and reason for asking questions and do the questions meet the research objectives. Before starting this research, the researcher reviewed several related pieces of literature and created a systematic literature review table (see appendix 1) of this thesis. The list of questions was derived from each of the sections of the literature review (see appendix 3) of this thesis. In order to ensure that the questions meet the research objectives, the researcher ensured that each of the questions are related to the research of objectives, as shown in table 3.7

Table 3.6: Relationship Between Research Objectives and Interview Guide

Research Objectives	Interview Guide
<p>RO1. <i>To identify the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.</i></p>	<p>Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access? Q3. Did you face difficulty in accessing a business loan? Q4. Can you tell me the Challenges you have faced when applying for a business loan? Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner? Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for a business loan? Q24. Do you apply directly to the lending agency or do ask someone to apply for you? Q26. Do you disclose all the necessary information to the lending agencies when applying for a business loan? Q27. Does the lending agency disclose all the necessary information to you when applying for a business loan?</p>
<p>RO2. <i>To critically identify the terms and conditions that will encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland</i></p>	<p>Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in the business loan are? Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business? Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business? Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing the business loan encouraging? Q21. How do you feel when applying for a business loan? Q25. Do you go through the contract document before signing the contract? Q33. In what way could the loan issuer encourage you to gain access to a business loan?</p>
<p>RO3. <i>To examine how much awareness ethnic minority owners of small businesses have to access business loans in Scotland</i></p>	<p>Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan? Q5. Do you know the types of lenders? Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan? Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans? Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation? Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans? Q19. Are you a migrant? Q20. Where are you originally from? Q23. Do you know the required information needed to access business loans?</p>
<p>RO4. <i>To identify what could be done to attract a high number of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.</i></p>	<p>Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access? Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loans to small business owners? Q14. Do you get loans from banks, credit agents, family friends or from your savings? Q18. What do banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loans? Q28. What type of business are you running? Q29. Why did you start this particular business? Q30. Who are your target customers? Q31. Are there easy ways to get business loans? Q32. What do you think could be done for you to access business loans? Q34. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loans?</p>

Source: Generated by the researcher

The second phase involved pilot interviews, redeveloping the interview guide, conducting the main interviews and recording. The researcher took time to conduct pilot interviews because the implementation of a pilot interview is one of the key elements in interview preparation (Turner, 2010). The details of the pilot interview will be discussed in the next sub-section of this thesis. After the pilot interview, the researcher had to redevelop the interview guide (see appendix 7 of this thesis). When conducting the main interviews, the researcher first of all had to seek the consent of each individual participant (see appendix 5) of this thesis and issue a letter of invitation to the participants (see appendix 4 of this thesis).

The third phase included transcribing, open coding, axial coding and selective coding. The researcher started transcribing the audio recording immediately after conducting the main interview; after transcribing, the researcher started coding.

During the day the researcher go out to conduct the interview and at night time the researcher try to transcribe the interview, during the transcription process the research found out that some interview answers are similar to other participant interview answers, the researcher got to category saturation point during the 16 participant, the researcher already have 6 appointment with some participant. When the researcher got to the 20 participant the researcher found out all the interview answers are the same with other participant interview answers.

The fourth phase involved analyzed interviews, identified emerging factors and summarized all the findings. The researcher used a thematic method of analysis to analyze each of the interviews, the researcher then identified emerging factors and, after that, the findings were summarized.

3.10.1 Pilot Study

According to Teijlingen et al (2001:289) “*the term ‘pilot studies’ refers to mini versions of a full-scale study (also called ‘feasibility’ studies), as well as the specific pre-testing of a particular research instrument such as a questionnaire or interview schedule*”. The researcher conducted a mini version of this study because conducting a pilot study is one of the essential phases in any study (Hassan, Schattner and Mazza, 2006). The researcher conducted three pilot study interviews, all of which were conducted within the Glasgow area. This was because Glasgow is the largest city in Scotland and the researcher lives in Glasgow so it was easy for the researcher to conduct the pilot interview because it is preferable to be carried out a pilot test with little number of people before the main study (Bolderston, 2012). The researcher conducted the pilot study based on qualitative research methods. Teijlingen *et al.* (2001) noted that huge project could involve pilot study before the main project and pilot study could be based on either qualitative or quantitative method. One good thing about conducting pilot study for the main study it is because the researcher would be able to identify any challenges before the main study and it would help in the research design by having a clear plan and viable objectives and the requirement for determining success of achievability (Thabane *et al*, 2010). The initial interview guide during the pilot study was 29 questions which was later redeveloped to 34 questions. The final version of the interview guide is included in this thesis (Appendix 7). The pilot study inquire if something could be done, should the researchers proceed with it, and if so, how. However, a pilot study also has a specific design characteristic (In, 2017). The pilot study was able to discover possible real problems in the research procedure (Teijlingen *et al.*, 2001).

Interview Challenges

In qualitative interview it’s normal for researcher to expect challenges during the process (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2019a). The researcher faced multiple of challenges when conducting this

research. The main challenges were accessing the participant, the interview setting and building rapport. The table below contains a summary of the main challenges:

The Interview Challenges	Interview Research Action
Accessing Participants	Accessing participants for this research was a challenging task because the participants in this research are ethnic minority owners of small businesses. The researcher used snowball sampling. The researcher used the initial few interviewees to recommend other potential participants who fit the inclusion criteria for the study.
Interview Setting	The physical space in which an interview is conducted can have a strong influence on how it proceeds, because of the important of comfort, privacy and quiet. The researcher first of all offer participants the options to choose any location of their choice. All the participants chose to use their business premises because some of the participants do not have any place apart from their business premises, and some of them did not want to leave their business because they had to attend to their customers. However, the researcher met with all participants before their business hours in order to maintain privacy, comfort and quietness. Thus, some participants had to book two or three appointment schedules with the researcher
Building Rapport	The vital aspect to successful conduct qualitative interview is to build rapport with the participants. The researcher tried to build trust with the participant so that the participant could feel free and comfortable to open up. The researcher ensured that all participants were treated with respect. The researcher maintained a smiling face at all times and did not force participants to give a specific answer.

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.10.2 The Field Experience

Three pilot interviews were conducted by the researcher. During the fieldwork process the researcher gained much experience, which helped in the main interview. While conducting the pilot study the researcher faced numerous challenges. However, the researcher was able to assess those challenges and some actions were considered on how to deal with them during the main fieldwork. The table in the next page contains the pilot study fieldwork experience:

Number of pilot interview	Experience	Action Considered
01	Participant was not available	Be ready to accept another appointment and be ready to be there 10 minutes before the scheduled time
	Participant did not understand English fluently	Be ready to face this problem because English is not their first language so ensure that the questions are simple for them to understand.
02	The environment was noisy	Try to offer a place which is not noisy, where it is comfortable, and maintain privacy.
	Participant refused to sign consent form	Be ready to explain in detail to the participant and tell them that their personal details and signature will not appear in this research.
03	Participant shared their own experience	Be ready to listen to whatever they say, because that information might be needed later.
	Participant was attending to customers	Try to know their rush hours and quiet times and be prepared to accept any rearrangement. Be ready to pause the recording and start again.

Source: Generated by the researcher

During the pilot interview the researcher gained experience by taking some actions before conducting the main interview for this thesis. However, some of the challenges identified by the researcher arose during the main interview and the researcher was able to continue despite the challenges.

After gaining experience during the pilot interview, the researcher proceeded to conduct an interview with respondent Abi. He was happy to participate in the interview but he chose a different day and time which was convenient for both parties. After the first interview, all other interviews were based on appointments. Some participants honored the interview and some of them failed to honor the interview. The researcher traveled from Glasgow to Edinburgh, Dundee and Aberdeen to conduct the interviews with each of the participants. The researcher traveled to meet Ade in Aberdeen, but on the day of the appointment Ade was not in his office. The

researcher waited for more than one hour. Ade's secretary booked another appointment after going through Ade's weekly schedule. The researcher accepted the new appointment date and time, which was a week later. The researcher went again the second time and Ade had an emergency issue to attend to so the researcher could not conduct any interview. After waiting for more than three hours the researcher had to speak with Ade's secretary to request another appointment. The third appointment was made and the researcher accepted the new date and time. For the third attempt, the researcher was 15 minutes earlier than the agreed appointment time and Ade was happy to participate in the interview. One of the participants, named Chen, was finding it difficult to understand some words so the researcher had to explain some words for him. Chen was complaining that he had another appointment and he wanted to leave the shop; the researcher had to let him know that there were only a few questions left in the interview guide so Chen agreed to continue to answer the questions till the final one. The researcher always wore his University Student ID Card before approaching any participant. The researcher met Giza, after a brief introduction the participant agreed to do the interview immediately without accepting any prior notice or appointment. At the end of the interview Giza explained that he graduated from the School of Sciences of the University of the West of Scotland, in the class of 1990. Giza said that immediately, when he saw the University ID Card, he knew the researcher was not an inspector or investigator and that is why he granted the researcher an audience on the spot without any hesitation, despite his busy schedules in the shop. Mark, Nnake, Bobby, Ifeoma and Anu agreed to participate in the research without prior notice and appointment. The researcher approached Robert for an interview. Robert was very busy, so he agreed to do the interview the next day at the shop just one hour before the shop's opening time. The interview was done successfully and Robert was happy that the researcher was there on time. The researcher faced challenges while conducting an interview with James, the environment was not conducive and the participant and the researcher were finding it difficult to

hear each other; at some points some words were repeated because of the noisy background environment. James informed the researcher that he has a hearing problem so the researcher had to increase the volume of both his voice and the recording device.

3.11 Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative analysis could be the analysis of qualitative data which include data collected from the field investigation (Bhattacharjee, 2012). In this research, the researcher transcribed all the interviews and the text data from the transcribed interviews were analyzed. Qualitative data analysis procedure could be a personal process because of the guiding principles (Dawson, 2002). In qualitative analysis where the data is collected it all depends on the researcher’s analytical skills and understanding the phenomena (Bhattacharjee, 2012).

One of the common problems in some research is that the researchers mostly focus more on addressing the research questions and less on data analysis (Greener, 2008). In order to have credible qualitative research data, analysis is essential (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017).

There are different types of data analysis in qualitative research but this research only focuses on two types of data analysis. The table below contains the two types of data analysis with an explanation about each of them:

Table 3.9: Qualitative Data Analysis Selection	
Type of Data Analysis	Explanation
Thematic Analysis	Thematic analysis is the process of identifying themes or patterns within a qualitative data set. In this type of analysis, the data collection and analysis take place simultaneously. Thematic analysis is closely connected to comparative analysis. The data in thematic analysis is analysed by theme.
Content Analysis	In content analysis, the researcher systematically works through each transcript assigning codes to specific characteristics within the text. Content analysis is dependent on creating labels (codes) that can be applied to data in order to develop data into meaningful categories to be analysed and interpreted.

Source: Adapted from Dawson, (2002): Maguire and Delahunt (2017): Blair (2015)

From table 3.9, the most appropriate type of data analysis is thematic analysis because the data collection and analysis took place simultaneously and the researcher identified some themes

3.11.1 Thematic Data Analysis

Thematic data analysis is the appropriate qualitative method that could be employed when analysis big qualitative data sets and working in research teams (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). The researcher analyzed the interview conducted with ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.

“When data is analysed by theme, it is called thematic analysis. This type of analysis is highly inductive, that is, the themes emerge from the data and are not imposed upon it by the researcher” (Dawson, 2002:115)

Nowell *et al.*, (2017) argue that in qualitative research method the widely used analysis for answering research questions is thematic analysis. The researcher used thematic analysis to provide answers to the research questions for this research.

Maguire and Delahunt (2017) claim that the aim of thematic analysis is to discover themes, that is blueprint in the data that are significant or that make sense and use these themes to answer the research questions.

Thematic analysis is a kind of analysis that is extremely inductive, which means the themes come out from the data rather than being forced upon it by the researcher (Dawson, 2002). In this research, the themes were derived from the interview transcripts.

The merits of thematic analysis it is because it is helpful for summarizing vital characteristics of a huge data set. Furthermore, it's highly flexible approach and the demerits of thematic analysis are when doing thematic analysis with another qualitative research method it will become extra obvious. There are little or no considerable literature on thematic analysis compared to that of

grounded theory, ethnography, and phenomenology (Nowell *et al.*, (2017). From the above definitions of thematic analysis, the advantages and disadvantages of thematic analysis meant that the researcher had to follow a framework for doing thematic analysis. The table below contains the framework the researcher used in doing the thematic analysis.

Source: Adopted Braun and Clark (2006)

From the above framework, the researcher first of all became familiar with the data by reading and proof reading each of the transcribed interviews. Before generating initial codes, which are also known as open coding, after generating each of the codes the researcher had to search for themes relating to the codes. After that, the researcher reviewed each of the themes to ensure accuracy, then the researcher defined each of the themes and, later, wrote them up. The next section below contains the coding procedures for this research.

3.12 Coding Procedures

According to Ping (2008:20) *“Coding is the action of identifying a passage of text in a document that exemplifies ideas or concepts and connecting it to a node that represents that idea or concept. Multiple codes can be assigned to the same segment of text in a document”*. Coding procedure involves activities such as identifying characteristics of the data systematically over the whole data set (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). Coding is the task of identifying material to enter into the cells of a matrix, coding is essentially one of the thematic coding (King, Horrocks

and Brooks, 2019b). Coding is a means of labeling. A similar view is held by Akinyode and Khan (2018): data coding in qualitative research means assigning labels or codes to diverse sections of data that relate to diverse problems. This is contrary to the view held by Theron (2015) that coding is not merely labeling, but also relating data to an idea. The researcher ensured that all the labeled codes were linked with each of the data. According to Sutton and Austin (2015:228) “coding refers to the identification of topics, issues, similarities, and differences that are revealed through the participants’ narratives and interpreted by the researcher. This process enables the researcher to begin to understand the world from each participant’s perspective.” During the coding procedure the researcher was enabled to identify issues from the transcript and the process gave the researcher more insight. Coding in qualitative research allows researchers to discover, classify, and categorize (Williams and Moser, 2019). In this research the researcher employed coding techniques to identify, organize and build theory.

Figure 3.3: Coding Techniques

Source: Adapted from Bhattacharjee (2012)

3.12.1 Open Coding

According to Blair (2015:17) “open coding involves applying codes that are derived from the text (emergent codes).” The researcher derived the codes from the transcribed interviews. Bhattacharjee (2012) describes open coding as a procedure intended at discovering concepts or key ideas that are hidden within the transcribed interview, which are possibly associated with the phenomenon of interest. The researcher was able to identify some hidden concepts and ideas in each of the transcripts. Bowen (2008) asserts that open coding helps to trim down the gathering of largely textual data into convenient groupings. The researcher was able to reduce the transcripts. Open code is also known as initial coding because it entails the process of breaking down the qualitative data into different parts (Theron 2015). The researcher took time to break down all the data. According to Holton (2010:24) “Open coding Beginning with line-by-line open coding of data and comparing incidents to each other in the data, the researcher codes the data in every way possible and asks a set of questions of the data”. A similar view is held by Bhattacharjee (2012); the researcher scrutinize the transcribed interview line by line to discover discrete events, incidents, ideas, actions, perceptions, and interactions of significance that are coded as concepts. The researcher did a line-by-line open coding of data from the interview guide. Figure 3.4 contains the annotated transcript.

Source: Generated by the researcher

The researcher started open coding immediately after the entire interview was transcribed.

The table in the next page is an example of the open coding:

Table 3.11: Open Coding		
Stage 1: Code generated from Interview guide	Stage 2: Code generated from Interview Transcript	
C001: types of Loans C002: Knowledge of Loan C003: Challenges of Accessing Loan C004: Types of Lenders C005: Knowledge of Lenders C006: Process of Business Loan C007: Terms and Conditions of Business Loans C008: Ethnic Minority Business Owners Challenges C009: Why doing Business in Scotland C010: Job Creation C011: Awareness of Scottish Govt Grant C012: Where do you get Loan From C013: Source of Finance C014: Knowledge of Small Business Loan C015: Encouraging Lending Policies and Procedure C016: Encouragement from Banks C017: Migrant C018: Ethnic Background C019: Immigration Status C020: Discrimination C021: Information for Accessing Loan C022: Application of Loan C023: Contract Document C024: Disclosure of Information C025: Hidden Information C026: Types of Business C027: Reasons for Starting this Business C028: Target Customer C029: Ways to get Business Loan C030: Encouragement from the Bank C031: Encouragement from Loan Issuer C032: Others	C033: Awareness of the kind of Loan C034: Banks or Personal Loan is more easier C035: Intermediary C036: Trust C037: Payback C038: The problem is the Limit of the Money C039: Bank of Scotland gives Loan C040: High Income C041: Depending on your Income C042: Bounce Back Loan C043: Lack of Awareness of the Terms and Conditions of Loan C044: Language C045: Difficulty in speaking English C046: Scottish People are Friendly C047: Scottish Govt gives Loan C048: Depend on Personal Money C049: Loan from Rent C050: Lending Policy and Procedures are not encouraging C051: Clydesdale Bank and Bank of Scotland gives Loan C052: Difficult for first timer C053: There's a need to know the rules C054: Immigration status is not a barrier C055: Inflow and Outflow of Cash C056: Third Party Application C057: All Information Must be Correct C058: Not aware of all the information C059: Passion for the Job C060: More local Customers	C061: Depend on the Information C062: Income Based C063: Financial Capability C064: Cash Flow C065: Collateral C066: Reduced Amount C067: Credit Crunch C068: Changes in Lending Policy C069: Conservative in Govt Loan C070: Bank Financial Capability C071: Private Lenders and Banks C072: Relationship with the Bank C073: Private Equity Firms C074: High Risk Lenders C075: Low Risk Lenders C076: Role of Business Manger C077: Incentives C078: Payment Holiday C079: Discrimination in the 80's C080: Personality C081: Naturalized C082: Scottish Enterprise C083: Grant for certain Sector C084: Business Interruption Loan C085: Profit from Business C086: Govt or Private C087: Not aware of the Lending Policies C088: Zero Percent Interest C089: Free Money C090: Extended Payment time C091: Feeling not Cheated C092: Bank Statement C093: Income C094: Expenditure C095: Company Details C096: Distinguishing Information

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.12.2 Axial Coding

Williams and Moser (2019) define axial coding as the second stage of coding which focal point is on discovering evolving themes. Axial coding further refines, aligns, and categorizes the themes. A similar view about axial coding is held by Bhattacharjee (2012), that the second segment of thematic analysis is axial coding, whereby the categories and subcategories are pull together into causal relationships or hypotheses that can tentatively explain the phenomenon of interest. In this second phase of coding, the researcher categorized all the open codes. The objective of axial coding is the strategic reassembling of data that have been split during initial coding (Theron, 2015). After generating the open codes, the researcher looked for relationships between each of the categories.

During this phase of coding, six main themes were identified and sub-themes were created from the interview transcripts. The table below contains an example of axial coding:

THEME 1: Business Loan	THEME 2: Business Challenges
<p>Sub-theme 1: Credit Note C001: Types of Loans C061: Depend on the Information C093: Income C094: Expenditure C095: Company Details C131: Business Proposal C132: Viability of the Business C134: Secure and Unsecure Loan C137: Start up Loan C191: Turnover C254: Depend on Sales C259: Depend on Credit Score C297: Credit Information C314: Cash and Carry C334: Credit Note</p> <p>Sub-theme 2: Buy Now and Pay Later C029: Ways to get Business Loan C064: Cash Flow C085: Profit from Business C118: Individual Situation C158: Personal Loan C166: Less money C195: Set the Rules C244: Buy Now and Pay Later C260: Age Eligibility C312: Respectful Customer C324: Higher Interest Rate C386: Prompt Response</p> <p>Sub-theme 3: Hire Purchase C048: Depend on Personal Money</p>	<p>Sub-theme 1: Accountant Fee or Agency Fee C035: Intermediary C056: Third Party Application C197: Role of Accountant C257: Professional Advice C299: 50% Profit C308: Role of Lawyers C309: Processing Fees C373: Scottish Accountant C374: Ethnic Minority Accountant C375: Financial Adviser</p> <p>Sub-theme 2: Relationship with Bankers C034: Banks or Personal Loan is more easy C039: Bank of Scotland gives Loan C040: High Income C123: Role of Personal Banker C124: Types of Bank Accounts C169: Existence of Business C170: Checking Accounts C171: Approval Process C172: Loan Decision C178: Depend on the Bank C179: Business Account C180: Small Procedure C196: Approach the Bank C200: Private Loan C295: Personal Lender C296: Personal Issues C319: Depend on Bank Manager C337: Trust and Relationship C352: Less Requirement for Business Loan</p>

C052: Difficult for first timer C081: Naturalized C112: High Interest Rate C119: Financial Books C120: Income and Expenditure C181: Pre Covid-19 C182: Identification C183: Proof of Documentation C192: Improved Credit Score C256: Background Check C313: Hire Purchase C353: Transaction History C354: Thorough Credit Check C371: Capital One C372: Funding Circle C377: Business Gateway Sub-theme 4: Reason behind Business Loan C012: Where do you get Loan From C027: Reasons for Starting this Business C049: Loan from Rent C059: Passion for the Job C133: Business Situation C136: Depend on the services C139: Nature of Business C142: Purpose of Loan C144: Positive mind set C156: Business Equipment C223: Reason for the Loan C342: Doing it for Money C343: Ways of Surviving C344: Liquidate C369: Business Expansion	C370: Bank Manager Relationship C385: Relationship with Lenders Sub-theme 3: Lack of Information C002: Knowledge of Loan C004: Types of Lenders C005: Knowledge of Lenders C014: Knowledge of Small Business Loan C021: Information for Accessing Loan C022: Application of Loan C033: Awareness of the kind of Loan C053: There's a need to know the rules C058: Not aware of all the information C087: Not aware of the Lending Policies C232: Limited Knowledge of Loan C293: Depend on Contract Papers C306: Lack of Response C359: Apply directly
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Source: Generated by the researcher

3.12.3 Selective Coding

According to Holton (2010:31) “*Selective coding begins only after the researcher has identified a potential core variable*”. The researcher was able to identify some core variables during the open coding and axial coding processes. The final and the third stage of thematic analysis is selective coding which entails recognizing a central category or a core variable and systematically and logically linking this central category to other categories (Bhattacharjee, 2012). In this stage the identified core variables were classified into categories and subcategories; the categories and subcategories are also known as themes and sub themes. The researcher compared the themes with the conceptual framework which was emanated from the literature review, in order to ensure consistency.

Selective coding is also known as theoretical coding. This process involves selecting the core group that functions like an umbrella which covers all codes and groups (Theron, 2015). The researcher ensured that all the categories and subcategories were related to each other. The table below contains an example of the selective coding for this research:

Table 3.13: Selective Coding	
<p>Business Loan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Credit Note ○ Buy now and Pay later ○ Hire purchase ○ Reason behind business loan 	<p>Terms and Condition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Contract Document ○ Payment Period ○ Charges/Fee ○ Sensitization
<p>Small Business Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Accountant Fee or Agency Fee ○ Relationship with Bankers ○ Lack of Information 	<p>Scotland</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Environment ○ Government ○ Support ○ Role of Job Centre
<p>Source of Funds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Family and Friends ○ Credit Agency ○ Grant ○ Banks 	<p>Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Language ○ Staffing ○ Trustworthy ○ Other Barriers

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.13 Good Practice Guidelines for Data Analysis

3.13.1 Credibility

Credibility is like internal validity, many positivist researchers addressed credibility as one of the key criteria in a research because it seeks to ensure the research measures or tests what is actually intended (Shenton, 2004). According to Cutcliffe and McKenna (1999:375) “a

qualitative study is likely to lack credibility if it is critiqued using positivistic criteria". However, this research does not lack credibility despite the key criteria. In this study the researcher used semi-structured interviews to collect data. Previous researchers who conducted related studies concerning ethnic minorities used semi-structured interview to collect their data, for example: Deakins *et al.*, (2005); Jones and Parry, (2011); Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam, (2010); Owen, Batelho and Anwar, (2016); and Kitching, Smallbone and Athayde, (2009); thus, their research methodology and analysis that they used in their previous research ensured the credibility of research findings.

Each of the interviews was audio recorded and transcribed verbatim in order not to miss any word. To make sure the data are accurate, all the participants were asked to go through the transcript just to double check.

Meetings and workshops were organized by the researcher's lead supervisor, which served as avenues from which general feedback was obtained. New perspectives obtained from the supervisory team were helpful in shaping the research design and objectives.

In this research, probing questions were asked. However, the researcher asked probing questions in a manner which did not pressure the interviewee (Dawson 2002). During probing, the researcher had to think about obtaining clarification, explanation, elaboration and understanding.

3.13.2 Dependability

According to Elo *et al.* (2014:2) "*dependability refers to the stability of data over time and under different conditions*". The data collected in this research are stable data and could be used under different conditions. The purpose of dependability is to guarantee that the results of this qualitative investigation are repeatable if the investigation is conducted within the same group of participants, coders and context (Forero *et al.*, 2018). However, there is no guarantee of this, because if it is not the same participant.

In this research, the researcher ensure that the same participants in this research, who are the ethnic minority owners of small businesses, were asked the same questions and the participants still give similar, or the same, answers.

In order to ensure that the data are correct, a cyclical method was conducted in every three weeks descriptive coding phase just to make sure that the results are consistent. In order to ensure accuracy the transcribed interview was given to the respondents despite the large volume of data and their busy schedules.

3.13.3 Conformability

According to Elo *et al.*, (2014:2) “*Conformability refers to the objectivity, that is, the potential for congruence between two or more independent people about the data’s accuracy, relevance, or meaning*”. In this research, the researcher consults his lead supervisor on timely basis. In order to make sure that the transcribed interview is correct, the research gave each participant their recorded interview and the transcribed interview for them to go through, likewise the researcher gave these to his lead supervisor to also check if everything is fine.

The purpose of conformability is to extend the assurance that the results corroborated or confirmed with existing research (Forero *et al.*, 2018). In this research the researcher confidently confirms that similar research corroborates the findings.

According to Noble and Smith (2015:34) “*Conformability or neutrality is achieved when truth value consistency and applicability have been addressed*”. The researcher applied the principle of conformability.

3.13.4 Transferability

The possibility for extrapolation could be transferability, because it depends on the grounds that findings could be generalized or transferred to another settings or set of people (Elo *et al.*, 2014).

In this research the reasoning is that the findings could be transferred to another setting or set of people.

The aim of transferability is to extend the level to which the results can be widespread or transferred to another aspect (Forero *et al.*, 2018). The result of this research could be transferred to other settings.

According to Drisko (2013:17) “*Transferability is premised upon a sampling plan that includes variation in time, setting, and participants. Any claims to transferability must be consistent with the study philosophy, goals and obtained sample*”. In this research, transferability is allowed because of the sampling plan and it is consistent with the purpose of the sample collected.

Researchers usually give details on transferability which includes how participant is recruited. The details could help with judging the transferability of the research result (Moon *et al.*, 2016). In this research, participants were identified using snowball sampling techniques. This started during the pilot study. The first participant referred the researcher to another participant, subsequently another participant was referred and by these means that was how the entire group of participants for this study was recruited.

3.13.5 Ethical Considerations

Research ethics is all about ensuring both the participant, and the information the participant provided, are treated with honesty and respect (Dawson, 2002). In this research, all the participants and the information collected from the participants were treated with respect and honesty and there was prior approval of the ethical committee. Some of the most important ethical problem in carrying out research is Respect for privacy, Beneficence- do no harm, informed consent, Respect for anonymity and confidentially (Fouka and Mantzorou, 2011). This research has fulfilled the requirement of the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee research and scholarship guidelines (2016), and this research is guided by the ethical principle

guiding research with human participants which are autonomy, veracity and informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, justice and inclusiveness, benefits and harm.

None of the participants in this study were pressurized to take part in the interview. The entire groups of participants are ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. Prior to the interview, participants were informed that they can withdraw from the research at whichever point in time if they are not happy with any of the interview questions. They also had the right not to provide answers to any of the questions.

3.13.6 Autonomy, Veracity and Informed Consent

According to the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (2016), the principle of autonomy recognizes the right of all individuals to decide on their own course of action. The university further underlines the need for free and informed consent. Prior to the main interview, the research sent a letter of invitation to the entire participant group to invite the participants and also inform the participants before the due date of interview.

According to Stein and Savulescu (2011:309)

“Informed consent is a liberal principle, not a libertarian principle. The requirement that consent be informed is a form of paternalism; liberal autonomy will not honor a person’s decision to be a subject in an experiment unless that decision is made with full information, under conditions that conduce to full understanding and authentic choice”.

One of the elements of informed consent is for the researcher to provide accurate, relevant and detailed information to the participant (see appendix 5: Individual consent form). Informed consent is the one of the most important ethical problem when conducting research. Participant right to autonomy is protected by means of informed consent (Fouka and Mantzorou, 2011). In the context of this research, the patients are the participants who are ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. The individual consent form was given to each participant and the researcher informed participants that they can withdraw their consent at any point in time and there will be no undue influence at any particular point in time. Fouka and Mantzorou (2011)

stated that informed consent is a request to integrate the rights of autonomous persons through self-determination. In some instances, the researcher gave participants some days so they could study and understand the procedure and nature of this research, because prospective participants should be given adequate time to think about the information and to make a decision concerning participation (University of the West of Scotland ethics committee, 2016). Similarly, Bolderston (2012) affirms that, researchers need to explain risk and benefits of the research to each of the respondents for respondents to make an informed decision on either to participate. Respondents need to be aware of the topic, the kind of questions, and how the collected data will be protected. The researcher told participants about the title of this research and the kind of interview questions, the risks and benefits of this research, and also the researcher explained how the data will be used and stored.

3.13.7 Privacy and Confidentiality

According to the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (2016), every person is entitled to privacy and confidentiality. The researcher informed the entire participant group that the information obtained from, and about, participants would remain confidential and the individual participants were not personally identifiable in this research.

Coffelt (2017) refers to confidentiality as modifying any personal data or information provided by the participants. The researcher ensured that the personal details of all the participants were modified. The data and personal information about each participant should be made as anonymous as possible (Bolderston, 2012). The researcher applied the principle of anonymity by ensuring that participants' names were not used and each participant were assigned number and code.

3.13.8 Justice and Inclusiveness

Justice and inclusiveness is all about being fair and equal to all research participants. The researcher ensured that there was fairness and equity for all participants who participated in this research. All participants were treated equally and all participants were asked the same questions irrespective of their age, background, religious belief and culture. There was no conscious bias in the interview process.

3.13.9 Benefits and Harms

According to the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (2016), risks and benefits are important in the review of applicants. Risk is defined as potential harm, discomfort or stress generated by the research. Thus, during this research, the risk of causing harm, either physically or emotionally, or discomfort and stress to the participants was continually assessed.

Participants benefited from this research. Participants were pleased that they were interviewed because they were given the opportunity to express their feelings about the challenges they face whilst accessing business loans.

The researcher developed a model of data analysis, the figure in the next page contains a detailed flow chat of the data analysis.

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.14 Research Direction

The researcher took time to develop the table 3.14 in the next page, linking the research aim, research problem statement, research questions, research objectives, interview guide and each of the thesis chapters.

Table 3.14: Research Direction Table

Aim	Research Problem Statement	Research Question	Research Objectives	Interview Guide	Themes
<p>This research project will investigate the Challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.</p>	<p>The problem statement is a situation whereby only three percent of ethnic minority owners of small business are in Scotland as at 2017 from the small business Scotland</p>	<p>RQ 1. What are the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.</p>	<p>RO1. To identify the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.</p>	<p>Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access? Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loans? Q4. Can you tell me the Challenges you have faced when applying for a business loan? Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner? Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for a business loan? Q24. Do you apply directly to the lending agency or do you ask someone to apply for you? Q26. Do you disclose all the necessary information to the lending agencies when applying for a business loan? Q27. Does the lending agency disclose all the necessary information to you when applying for a business loan?</p>	<p>THEME 1: Business Loan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Credit Note ○ Buy now and Pay later ○ Hire purchase ○ Reason behind business loan <p>THEME 2: Business Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Accountant Fee or Agency Fee ○ Relationship with Bankers ○ Lack of Information
		<p>RQ 2. What are the opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loans in Scotland?.</p>	<p>RO2. To critically identify the terms and conditions that will encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland</p>	<p>Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in the business loan are? Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business? Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business? Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging? Q21. How do you feel when applying for a business loan? Q25. Do you go through the contract document before signing the contract? Q33. In what way could the loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loans?</p>	<p>THEME 3: Source of Fund</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Family and Friends ○ Credit Agency ○ Grant ○ Banks <p>THEME 4: Terms and Condition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Contract Document ○ Payment Period ○ Charges/Fee ○ Sensitization
		<p>RQ 3. How can banks encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.</p>	<p>RO3. To examine how much awareness ethnic minority owners of small businesses have about accessing business loans in Scotland.</p>	<p>Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan? Q5. Do you know the types of lenders? Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan? Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans? Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation? Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans? Q19. Are you a migrant? Q20. Where are you originally from? Q23. Do you know the required information needed to access a business loan?</p>	<p>THEME 5: Scotland</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Environment ○ Government ○ Support ○ Role of Job Centre
		<p>RQ 4. What can be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland?.</p>	<p>RO4. To identify what could be done to attract a high number of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.</p>	<p>Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access? Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loans to small business owners? Q14. Do you get loans from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?. Q18. What do banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loans?</p>	<p>THEME 6: Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minority</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Language ○ Staffing ○ Trustworthy ○ Other Barriers

Source: Generated by the researcher

3.15 Chapter Summary

The researcher discussed everything that deals with the research methodology, such as the research approach, the research paradigm, the research philosophy and how it is applicable to this research, the method employed in this research and justification of why qualitative research was used in this research. The researcher discussed the similar previous studies whereby some previous researchers employed qualitative methods. Furthermore, the researcher shed light on the methods used to collect data, which was semi structured interviews. The researcher used probing concept during the interview process. The population samples in this research are ethnic minority owners of small businesses, specifically those who had applied for a business loan recently or in the past years. The researcher used snowball sampling techniques by asking ethnic minority owners of small business if they know any of their colleagues or family friends. The researcher created a profile of the entire participant group. During the field investigation, the researcher encountered some challenges so the researcher deemed it necessary to share the experience. The researcher also drew a map of how the qualitative field investigation was conducted. Pilot study was conducted prior to the main study in order to identify potential problems. During transcription process the researcher got to research found out that some interview answers are similar to other participant interview answers, the researcher got to category saturation point during the 16 participant, when the researcher got to the 20 participant the researcher found out all the interview answers are the same with other participant interview answers. Thematic data analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The coding techniques used in this research were open coding, axial coding and selective coding. The researcher ensured that good practice guidelines for data analysis were followed in this research. The researcher explained the procedure used for analysis of the interviews. Finally, the researcher created the research direction table which includes the research aim, research problem statement, research question, research objective, interview guide and the themes for discussion.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research used a qualitative method to address all the research objectives of this research.

The research objectives are as follows:

- 1. To identify the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland.*
- 2. To critically identify the terms and conditions that will encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland*
- 3. To examine how much awareness ethnic minority owners of small businesses have of accessing business loans in Scotland.*
- 4. To identify what could be done to attract the highest number of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.*

The researcher produced a qualitative data analysis template which contains the participants' responses according to themes that facilitate data analysis. The qualitative data analysis template is included in appendices 8, the important quotes from the transcripts assisted the researcher to discuss the six different themes. These six themes are as follows:

1. Business Loans
2. Business Challenges
3. Sources of Funds
4. Terms and Conditions
5. Scotland
6. Challenges affecting Ethnic Minorities

4.1 THEME 1: BUSINESS LOANS

This first part identifies and discusses business loans in Scotland from different contexts, such as credit notes, buy now pay later, Hire purchase and reasons behind business loans.

4.1.1 Credit Notes

A credit note is a document which is issued by a seller to a buyer and it stands as evidence to allow the buyer to buy items or services from the same seller on a particular date in the future. According to respondent Abdul, *“Credit note for a month but I normally pay within 3 or 4 days”*. It is clear that credit notes are a type of business loan that some ethnic minority owners of small businesses use to access finance. However, credit notes are limited, According to respondent Hassan *“They need to give more loans”*. The credit note is not sufficient for some ethnic minority owners of small businesses because of some requirements such as certain information, credit history, and credit scores. According to respondent James, *“The Bank, so it all depends on your credit score, if its higher you can easily access business loan if its lower it will be difficult for you to access business loan”*. This challenge reflects the view of Frame, Srinivasan and Wossley (2001) that larger branch networks are possibly linked with the use of credit scoring because it aids them in making a lending decision because its one of the legal requirement to use computerised loan evaluation. Thus, disclosure of credit information is important to access a business loan, but in the opinion of respondent Isah *“I don’t need to disclose the credit information about myself, just ask for the money and that is all”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses believe that lenders such as banks, credit agencies and the Government already have their information and they do not need to ask for this type of information. Cavalluzzo and Wolken (2005) found that credit history is one of the determinants explaining the reason behind the denial of loans among African-American owned firms. In Scotland new immigrant cannot access business loan because new migrant do not have credit history in the United Kingdom. Another challenge facing ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans is the requirement of the business loan, such as the credit note requirement. Respondent Ade said, *“it depend the requirement yes I know, I have said it initially it depends on your financial books and on how you’ve run your accounts and all*

the business activities on your account and your proposal and your business proposal and the viability of the business you want to get yourself into". Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses do not have a sufficient inflow and outflow of funds in their financial books, which is one of the hindrances affecting them in accessing a business loan. Respondent Giza mentioned a few, among other, requirements "*Well, the bank managers will tells you they need xyz, they need company details, they need this they need that, bank statement, income, expenditure, inflow and outflow of cash*". Some of this requirement is easy to obtain. Why, then, is it still difficult for ethnic minority owners of small businesses? The reason they face challenges accessing business loans might be because of the accuracy of the information. According to respondent Abi: "*not really sure, it all depends on your information, if your information is all true the lenders will give you. But if you have any mistake like that they make it hard for you*". Information asymmetry is a traditional theory of small business credit markets which exists between borrowers and lenders; it could lead to credit rationing (Frame, Srinivasan and Wossley, 2001).

From the fieldwork investigation, it emerged that the amount of business loans issued to ethnic owners of small businesses is not enough for them to use. The researcher found that credit rating and credit history is what banks, credit agencies and the government look at before approving loans. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses do not have accurate information when applying for a business loan. Some other challenges when applying for business loans are the requirements; some ethnic minority owners of small businesses cannot meet the requirement of the business loan.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.1: Credit Note			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Limited amount	Insufficient loan	Not identified	Yes (based on the amount of loan)
Credit Rating	Credit Score	Credit Scoring	Yes (based on credit rating)
Ethnic Minority Perception	Loan Perception	Not Identified	Yes (based on owners of small businesses)
Credit History	Previous loan	History	Yes (based on previous loan)
Requirement	Loan requirement	Not Identified	Yes (based on the requirement of the loan)
Information	Correct Information	Information Asymmetries	Yes (based on accurate information)

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.1.2 Buy Now Pay Later

Some ethnic minority owners of small business prefer to use buy now and pay later options because it is easier for them to access it compared to other sources of business loans. According to respondent Umar, *“Cash and Carry guys are good because they give you goods and you pay later”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses usually benefit from buy now pay later schemes, but some of them still face challenges because of the process involved in accessing business loans. However, according to respondent Abi, *“how much is coming in and how much is going out like every month or a year and if you have good money they will give you”*. Haron, *et al.*, (2013) found that having a good financial record has a significant effect on loan approvals by the financial institution. Most, if not all, of the lenders who prefer buy now and pay later schemes stated that they would like to see the cash flow statement. However, it does not end at inspecting the cash flow. According to respondent Ade *“it depends on individual situation if you are like in a business it is easier for you to access loan depending on your financial book.”* Before any lender will grant or approve buy now and pay later, the lender would want to see the financial books of the ethnic minority owners of small business, to check if they will be able to

pay the loan back. This is one of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses.

Respondent Mark said that:

“Borrowing from your friend you have to set the rules because there is no paper work and if your friend takes you to court without any document he can’t prove anything. Because money change people very easy even your brother can cheat you, so my recommendation is you should borrow money from a friend if you can and second recommendation is to go to the bank”.

It is easier to borrow from friends than other lenders because there might be no paper work. Furthermore, the borrower can potentially run away if they want to because there might not be any evidence to show regarding the buy now and pay later agreement.

Buy now pay later is also applicable to small business owners, for example some customers will buy some goods from ethnic minority owners of small businesses and they will pay later. According to respondent Anu, *“some customers like buy now and pay later which is not a good idea by the end of this month I will have to stop the buy now and pay later because people are abusing it.”* Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses do face challenges when doing business and some customers do abuse the small privilege of buying now and paying later.

The field investigation shows a few, among other challenges, affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans using a buy now pay later basis. The researcher discovered some of these factors, for instance cash, individual situations, paper work and abuses of privilege.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.2: Buy Now Pay Later			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Cash	Cash flow	Not identified	Yes (based on income and expenditure)
Individual situation	Financial books	Identified	Yes (requirement to access loan)
Paper work	Documentation	Not Identified	Yes (no documentation when borrowing from friends)
Abuse of privilege	Privilege	Not identified	Yes (take the buy now pay later agreement for granted)

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.1.3 Hire Purchase

Hire purchase is another means of accessing a business loan. Hire purchase is also known as an installment plan. With most banks and credit agencies, whenever they issue loans, the remittance is always through installment payments. However, it is not easy to access business loans because of some factors such as bank statements and transaction histories.

According to respondent Ola:

“if you went to the bank and ask them of business loan they will look at your bank statement and your transaction history because you are a new business then you want to buy this, you want to improve your business for example now I want to get a loan to do my approval, documentation SIA approval all this I could not get a loan for the past 2 years, it is only Government loan now that will help me. That help me now just because government make it relax now it help my business and my business is pushing forward”.

It is noted that the new government loan, which is a bounce back loan, is easy to access because, before approval, the government will not ask for bank statements and transaction histories.

In respondent Ola’s opinion:

“The bank should make it simple, banks should not be using any credit history but they should make it simple and there should be fair credit checking. The credit check should not be harsh, they should not see a young business like a business that has no future, assuming the banks can help us my business is almost 7 years and I am still looking for money if the bank has help us I would have employed up to 15 or 16 people bust because there is no much job so I am just using my own personal money you know, business required money.”

Ekpu’s (2011) finding shows that small banks receive loan applications from firms that have a pre-existing loan, although not all ethnic minority owners of small businesses have pre existing

loans. However, thorough credit checks and lack of interest in young businesses is one of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for a business loan. According to respondent Robert *“if you apply for it they will run some check like credit check and background check”*. It has been mentioned that credit checks and background checks are two of the checks that lenders will carry out before approving the hire purchase. According to respondent Ade, *“for you to access loan depending on your financial book, your yearly financial book.... how much is your income and spending and your expenditure.”*

Haron, *et al.*, (2013) findings showed that having a good financial record is one of the important variables for credit officers to approve a loan. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses may not have a good financial record perhaps that is the reason they have not been able access a business loan. According to respondent Chen, *“I need to do that I need to do something know some loans from the bank and know some grants but the interest is high so they can give grants”*, Fagerstrom and Hantula (2013) found that nearly 40% of students are willing to pay a high interest charge. The reason why some businesses are operating is to make a profit. Some ethnic minority owners may not be able to afford a business loan because of the high interest rate. This is because some of the small businesses owned by ethnic minorities are newly established businesses. The respondent Abi said *“First when you do a business here it is hard for you first time but after you know the rules it will be easy and not difficult and you will know how to connect with people then with”*. It is always difficult for first time applicants to access a loan.

According to Haron, *et al.*, (2013:184)

“Banks are not willing to provide loans to small medium entrepreneurs as they (are) high risk group. Small medium enterprises can sometimes not be interested to borrow from banks due to the tight procedural process and the length of time it might take to obtain the loan”.

One of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans is the procedure involve in accessing them.

During the field investigation, the researcher found that interest rates, financial books, credit checks and the rules of hire purchase are some, among other, factors affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for a business loan.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Interest rate	High interest rate	Identified	Yes
High risk group	Difficult for new owners	Identified	Yes
Financial Books	Income and expenditure	Identified	Yes
Credit Check	Thorough credit check	Identified	Yes
Young business	No feature for young business	Identified	Yes
Rules	Strict rules	Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.1.4 Reason Behind the Loan

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses see a loan as a debt, but some of them might have a genuine reason behind a loan.

In his response, Ade expresses that:

“Business loan I have said it initially it all depends on the business situation and in terms of business loan in the United Kingdom...Yes accessing business loan is depending on the business you know I said it initially before I became psychotherapy before I diversify my business I use to run a private company, I got a removal services so I use to run that in the local area in Dundee where I use to live, removal service have got a van which I use”.

It might be the small business is in need of some cash to meet some liabilities in order to gain competitive advantage or to maximize their profit. Another reason why some ethnic minority owners of small businesses apply for business loans is for expansion purposes. According to respondent Bola, *“I want to expand my business and I was going to be a long process but I did not see the business manager, I had to call I had to go to the branch so I got put off half way so I*

never". Apart from the reason behind the loan, one of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans is the long process period during application. In respondent Ade opinion, *"Definitely they are encouraging yes, but it all depends on what you want to use the business loan for...Accessing business loan in Nigeria is more difficult than here, I feel more relax here whenever I go to my bank to ask for a loan and I feel more positive"*. The challenges affecting this group are lower compared with other developing countries in Africa. However, this might depend on what is available. In his response, Ade said, *"challenges it depends on what you are providing me as a person that provide my service you need my services you will have to look for me to get my services"*. In other words, the owner's goods or services will determine the kind of challenges they will face when applying for business loans.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.4: Reasons Behind the Loan			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Business Expansion	Business Expansion	Not Identified	Yes
Application Process	Strict process of loan	Not Identified	Yes
Depends on services	Depends on Services	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

During the process of this study, the researcher came across a few previous studies which discuss business loans specifically, relating to ethnic minority owners of small businesses, and many of newly emerged factors were identified during the discussion process.

The summary of theme 1, the key findings, is presented in the table below:

Table 4.5: Business Loans	
Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Credit Scoring	Limited amount and Insufficient loan
History	Credit Rating
Information Asymmetries	Ethnic Minority Perceptions about Loans
Financial books	Credit History regarding Previous loans
Interest rates	Requirement that is a Loan requirement
High risk groups	Information, having the Correct Information
Credit Checks	Cash flows
Young businesses	Individual situations
Rules	Paper work and Documentation
	Abuse of privilege
	High interest rates
	Difficult for new owners
	Income and expenditure
	Thorough credit checks
	No feature for young businesses
	Strict rules
	Business Expansion
	Strict process of loans
	Depends on Services

Source: Generated by the Researcher

The table above shows that many factors emerged from the fieldwork.

4.2 THEME 2: BUSINESS CHALLENGES

This section discusses the results regarding business challenges. The discussion will be centered on accountants' fees or agency fees, relationships with bankers and a lack of information.

4.2.1 Accountants' Fees or Agency Fees

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses hire an accountant or an agent to work or act on their behalf in a different capacity. According to respondent Abi: "*to help you to speak to the bank*". In terms of accessing a business loan, the accountant or agent helps the business owner to speak to the bank about a business loan because of the owner's limited knowledge of business loans. Lee and Black (2017) found that immigrant business owners experience challenges when applying for capital because of their lack of understanding about the available loan and how to

obtain the loan from a financial institution. In her response, Nnake asserted that *“I don’t really have much information on that, I think my Accountant has much information about that”*. Some ethnic minority owners do not have much knowledge of business loans, which is why they hire the services of a professional, Respondent Robert stated that *“Yes I do have to read it, I go over and over again before signing and sometimes I do ask for professional advices before signing the document.”* These professional services are not free of charge; the fee is also known as an accountant’s fee or agency fee. In his response, Umar mentioned that *“I don’t know but some lawyers will come here and ask me to give them £5,000 so they could apply form for a loan for me, I tell them no.”* One of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans is the agency fee. The agency fee can be very high. Some ethnic minority business owners cannot afford this fee, which can be around £5,000. However, some ethnic minority business owners feel it is better to have an accountant who is from an ethnic minority than a Scottish accountant.

According to respondent Bola:

“Only one I was able to get because it was accessible to everyone. I also got the furlough pay. And another thing is this, I have an accountant who is Scottish and I am genuinely and I am about to switch my accountant as well, I feel like when you are also ethnic minority rather than them having or help you grow they look for ways to make sure all your earnings go to the government because already you are paying your staff, you are paying so much to run a business but I found my accountant always not on my side rather than to look for more money for the government if that make sense and I personally believe also because I am from an ethnic minority, There is been need for expansion for a long time but of course and you need to make money save money, I couldn’t even access the start up fund when I started my business, I couldn’t get the £50,000 start up fund and I have just graduated from the University which I thought that would have been an easy way”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that Scottish accountants are not so helpful in terms of accessing business loan when compared to ethnic minority accountants, notwithstanding the accountant’s fee.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.6: Accountant’s Fee or Agency Fee			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Limited Knowledge	Limited Knowledge	Yes, but in setting up a business	Yes
Professional Services	Professional Fees	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.2.2 Relationship with Bankers

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses do face challenges when applying for business loans from the bank, but this largely depends on their relationship with the bankers. Abi said that: *“I think is like from the bank or personal is easier....I think Bank of Scotland is better, I bank with them”*. Having a personal relationship with a banker might increase the chance of accessing a business loan. Degryse and Cayseele (2000) found that loan rates do increase with the duration of a company’s relationship with their bank. The relationship between bankers and some ethnic minority business owners is similar to that of creditors and debtors (Singh, 2019). In order to gain access to business loans, ethnic minority business owners do establish good relationships with their bankers.

According to respondent Ade:

“I have been in relationship with my personal banker which I operate premier banking with my bank and I have been with my bank for several years for close to 17 years now I have been with my bank so in my own situation I don’t have challenges in accessing business loans because of the good relationship I have with my bank and the kind of account I am operating with my bank”.

The relationship with a banker depends on the individual bankers in particular. Respondent Hassan mentioned that *“See loan is easier if I have to go to the bank, I have to go to them and asking them about loan, that my business is not running good, I need some small loan depending on the manager, the manager is going to say yes or no”*.

Similarly, in his response, Abdul said *“No, nothing like that. They’ve known my dad for many years, so based on that trust and relationship”*. Trust and relationship is more important when applying for a business loan. However, this is not applicable to ethnic minority owners of new

businesses because they are inexperienced in this area. Therefore, some business owners still feel as though, according to respondent Fahad, “requirements should be a little bit less for a business loan”. Some ethnic minority business owners are facing challenges to meet the business loan requirements, despite their relationship with their bankers.

Respondent Bola explained her procedure:

“so I just didn’t see it through and I feel personally that when it come to ethnic minority they require a lot more guarantee before you can get a loan, they should make it easier because the first impression if you walk into a bank like really do you deserve it, you need to prove to us that you worth it, do you understand that was the first impression I got, the only good thing for me that made me see through to some extent was that I have know the bank manager for like few years and he was nice and unfortunately he was not in charge of business loan, so the business sector is different and this is just a general branch manager, I had to speak to someone.

It is noted that ethnic minority owners of small businesses do face numerous challenges when applying for a business loan. First of all, some owners do not have the required guarantee to access a business loan, and their first impression when applying for a business loan is not encouraging. However, if these people have a good relationship with their banker, then it might be easier for them to access a loan.

From the field investigation, it is shown that before ethnic minority owners of small businesses could access loans they must have had a personal relationship with their bankers for many years. Also, they need to meet all the requirements of the loan.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.7: Relationship with Bankers			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Relationship	Personal Relationship	Identified but not for new owners	Yes
Requirement	Business Loan Requirement	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.2.3 Lack of Information

Lack of information is one of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans. Radipere and Scheers (2005) found that small business owners are constrained, not only by financial factors, but also particularly by non-financial factors such as lack of information. Not having the right information at the right time is a problem with a solution. Some small business owners know the types of loan available but they do not know the rules involved.

According to respondent Abi

“No, Yes I get you, I know there are too many different kind of loan...You just need time to know the rule before you can do business...To be honest I don't know about the information but I think they tell my Accountant. My Accountant act on my behave so he speak with them and he knows what to do”.

Some ethnic minority business owners lack the necessary information to access business loans, which is why some of them do employ the services of an accountant to assist them when applying for a loan. Lee and Black (2017) found that a lot of immigrant small business owners are not sufficiently aware of the borrowing opportunities for which they are qualified. However, some of these people do not know about the various kinds of loans. In her response, respondent Ifeoma said *“I don't really know the various kind of small business loan but my Accountant has a wider knowledge about this”*. Ethnic Minority owners of small businesses believe their accountant has the knowledge and information needed to access a business loan.

Ortiz-Molina and Penas (2008) noted that there is concern that firms may face challenges in accessing formal finance due to informational opacity. According to respondent Umar *“Yes, I applied for a loan like three month ago and up till now no response, no single email or phone call. COVID 19 is Grant. But I applied for a loan for my shop”*. From the field investigation, it can be seen that some ethnic minority business owners, after applying for a business loan or grant, will have to wait for more than two months without any information about their

application. Nevertheless, some ethnic minority owners of small business can easily access business loans due to Covid 19. In his response, respondent Ola mentioned that *“During this period it is very simple to get a loan. I just go online and check what the government says we should do then I apply directly to my bank”*. Some of the business owners were lucky to access the recent Covid 19 loan. This could be because they were aware of the loan being available.

From the field investigation it shows that the reason why some ethnic minority owners of small business are still facing challenges in accessing business loans is because they are not aware of the loan, and perhaps because the process is not transparent.

The table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.8: Lack of Information			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Awareness of Loan	Not aware of loan	Not Identified	Yes
Opacity	Transparency	Identified	No

Source: Generated by the Researcher

During the process of this research the researcher came across a few previous studies which discuss business challenges specifically relating to ethnic minority owners of small businesses; many newly emerged factors were identified during the discussion process.

The summary of Theme 1, the key findings, is presented in the table below:

Table 4.9: Business Challenges	
Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Limited knowledge for new business owners	Limited knowledge which is why they employ an accountant or agent
Relationship with bankers is important but not for a new business owner	Professional fees
Information opacity	Personal relationship with bankers is important
	Unable to meet the business Loan requirement
	Not aware of loan

Source: Generated by the Researcher

The table above shows that few factors emerged from previous studies.

4.3 THEME 3: SOURCES OF FUNDS

This section is divided into four parts. The first part presents and discusses the topic of family and friends, the second part is about credit agencies, the third part is about grants while the fourth part is all about banks.

4.3.1 Family and Friends

Family and friends are one of the most common informal sources of funds for ethnic minority owners of small business. As stated by Lee and Presson (2016:2341) *“Most informal finance comes from family and friends. Existing informal finance theories cannot match two characteristics of family finance: family investors may accept below market or even negative returns, yet borrowers often prefer formal finance”*. Ethnic minority owners of small businesses prefer borrowing from family and friends because it is easy to access. According to respondent Mark *“if it is a small amount maybe it’s better to borrow from my friend because you don’t have to pay any interest... It depends on the friends you’ve got, if you got rich friends it is always easy, A friend is always good. I will recommend you to try a friend. It depends the loan and the amount of money”*. Some ethnic minority business owners would rather borrow funds from their family or friends rather than going to the bank to borrow. In his response, respondent Chen mentioned that, *“(I do get loan) from my daughters and sometimes from my daughters and government”*. Based on the above statement, it can be inferred that the ethnic minority owners of small businesses do first of all ask for funds from their family and friends before borrowing from banks or other sources. Similarly, in her response, respondent Nnake said *“Hmm so I have my family supporting me and just the little from my savings so we are still hoping that with time it will grow”*. One of the opportunities when these small business owners access business loans from family and friends is flexibility and extended payment time. Borrowing from family and friends, to some ethnic minority business owners, is better because there are no strict terms and

conditions compared to other providers of formal sources of funds, which have terms and conditions.

Respondent Abi said:

“like how much you get if you can pay it back they will give you, just to make sure that all information about your business or company, how much is coming in and how much is going out like every month or a year and if you have good money they will give you. If you don’t have enough money maybe you can’t pay it back”.

Other formal sources of funds’ terms and conditions are not encouraging to ethnic minority business owners when applying for a business loan. Respondent Giza suggested that *“the payment time should be as long as you need it”*. Some of the business owners feel that providers of formal sources of funds should offer extended payment times.

Bewaji, Yang and Han (2015) take the stance that it is more difficult for some ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access different sources of finance due to their nationality. Hence, this might be why ethnic minority business owners always resort to borrowing from family and friends. According to Lee and Persson (2016:2377) *“Financing from family and friends, in contrast, tends to be cheap; moreover, despite this discount, informal finance is often in limited demand when formal funding is available”*. It is because they are cheaper and easier to access loan from family and friends, although, in some cases, family and friends may not have the required funds available to borrow.

From the field investigation, the researcher critically identified factors such as flexible terms and conditions and extended payment periods as some of the terms and conditions that do encourage ethnic minority owners of small business to access business loans in Scotland

Table 4.10: Family and Friends			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Flexibility	Flexible terms	Not Identified	Yes
Payment time	Extended payment	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.3.2 Credit Agency

A credit agency is an agency that deals with information about debts. Credit agencies are profitable companies that specialize in assigning scores to borrowers indicating the credit worthiness of a borrower. Failures in paying outstanding debts will affect the credit score. James emphasizes that *“you don’t have any debt outstanding and you need to have money coming in and going out from your account”*. In order to access a formal business loan there is no need to look at the credit score. According to respondent Mark *“the lending agency will approve you loan through your credit score system. Before they approve you the loan they will send you name and request all credit agency to check your credit score and if you have a good credit score they will approve the loan”*. Having a good credit score is one of the conditions of obtaining a formal business loan. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that the credit score sometimes does not encourage them to access formal business loans. In his response, respondent Abi said *“just to check about your income”*. Some ethnic minority business owners would prefer borrowers to just check their income and not their credit score. This is because some credit scores might not be accurate or correct. Liao, Chen and Lu (2009) found that agency problems and information asymmetry are some of the vital causes of deviation in credit evaluation. Thus, another issue or factor affecting the business owners when applying for business loans is the need to have a guarantee. Respondent Jamshair believes that *“securing business loans with guarantee, business loan should be without guarantee but they ask many of things...yeah after 5 years they give a loan. Something like steady income for 5 years and you have to have a business”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that if a small business has been in existence for up to 5 years then there should be no credit check, because if the business can survive for the past 5 years then it should be easy for them to acquire a formal business loan.

From the above discussion, the researcher was able to identify some factors; the table in the next page contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.11: Credit Agency			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Credit Score	Low Credit Score	Not Identified	Yes
Information Asymmetry	Inaccurate Score	Identified	No

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.3.3 Grants

A grant is an amount of money given to an individual or group of people for a particular purpose, most grants are not refundable. This is supported by Chen *“For equipments, for some other stuffs, most importantly for the clients”*. This ethnic minority business owner was given a grant for equipment purposes. A grant is one of the sources of funding available to ethnic minority owner’s small businesses. Some grants are provided by the government.

According to Wallsten (2000:98) *“Funding by the government could also be a mechanism that helps the firm (to) attract additional private funding. Ultimately, these are both additional empirical questions that could be addressed in future work”*. Government funding is always there whenever there is a crisis. Recently, much business was interrupted due to the Covid 19 pandemic and the Scottish government provided some grants to business owners. Respondent Abi acknowledged that *“I think the first year they don’t take any money, when you take the loan the one year is like free, after the one year you have to payback that is the bounce back loan from the government”*.

Similarly, according to respondent Giza, “

So it takes may be 6 months for your cash to go okay, so once its 6 months you don’t pay us nothing but probably you still have 6 month of interest to pay...yes, that’s like a grant but it is for certain sectors so whether it is given for ethnic minority or not, I don’t know, the accountant dealing with my application on business interruption loan”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses benefited from bounce back loans. According to respondent Mark *“Yes, The Bounce Back Loan, there are different ones but the better and best loan is bounce back loan because they give you one year free interest and after one year the additional fee is only 2.5% interest rate on top of what every you borrow from them which is one of the best loan”*. But some ethnic minority business owners were not able to receive the grant.

Humza mentioned that *“Just now, just now believe it or not...I am having an issue with the COVID19 grant”*. Nevertheless, some ethnic minority owners of small businesses said it was easy to apply, and once they had applied for the grant they would receive it. However, it is difficult to apply for a bank loan. According to respondent Umar, *“There is no easy way. Its always difficult, but applied for the grant it was easy and straight forward, because it was funded by the city council, they require just your name and your shop address and the reference of your business rate, that’s all”*. According to the above participant, it seems easy to get the grant. However, respondent Mark said *“No its not encouraging to give loan, Nobody will encourage you to give you loan, even if you apply for bounce back loan you still have to meet some regulations as well before they approve you the bounce back loan, even if the government said nobody can get refuse, they might refuse you”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses would be happy to apply for loans if there was encouragement. Some banks are introducing personal loans and they encourage their customers to access the facility. In his response, respondent Jamshair said that *“Yeah. I got a Barclays personal loan with Barclays bank”*. The Barclays personal loan is similar to the bounce bank loan because the borrower does not need to repay anything until after several months.

From the previous page discussion, the researcher was able to identify some factors; the table below contains the summaries of the findings from this section:

Table 4.12: Grant			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Covid 19 Grant	Bounce Back Loan	Not Identified	Yes
Bank Loan	Barclays Personal Loan	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.3.4 Banks

Banks are one of the sources of funds, and some ethnic minority owners do go to their bank to access a business loan. There are different kinds or types of bank but the most accessible type of bank is a commercial bank. In his response, respondent Umar mentioned that *“The easy bank is*

Bank of Scotland, Royal Bank of Scotland, Halifax all Lloyds group is very good including Nat West bank. They could reply my email and get back to me on time". A similar view was held by respondent Abi *"I think Clydesdale Bank and Bank of Scotland this two do give loan"*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses have been patronizing some commercial banks and some ethnic minority business owners know which of the commercial banks do give business loans. Apart from banks, there are other lenders, such as private lenders, but some ethnic minority business owners prefer borrowing from the banks. In his response, respondent Giza said, *"Well you have the private lenders and the banks....easier for us and easier for them and beside private equity firms they want something like a share in your company, a share in your investments and sometimes it might look good, they are high risk enough"*. This participant feels that to borrow from a bank is better than to borrow from a private equity firm. Mark suggests that *"If it's a big amount of money its always better to borrow from bank"*. This interviewee's suggestion might be because of low interest rates or other factors.

According to respondent Jamshair

"if you go for private agency its too much interest they charge, private companies charge too much interest than the bank. But when you go for a loan, you need to go to the bank because the credit card people are too much. Some company charge more than 30% interest which is too much, it those not matter the time you return the money it will be the same interest, if I pay off within three month I have to pay the full interest. They don't care".

Similarly, one respondent Nnake said,

"they should not put as much interest on the loan because it will be discouraging, at lease if they can put less interest a certain number people will be encourage to take a loan although I understand that the banks too will want to make their gain or profit but if they could reduce the money that will be better".

This ethnic minority owner of a small business mentioned that the interest rate is one of the factors affecting ethnic minority business owners when applying for a business loan. Bruder, Neuberger and Rathke-Doppner's (2011) findings show that ethnic entrepreneurs are more expected to be given smaller loan or be denied access to credit. However, there are other factors

affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans. In his response, respondent Hassan said *“Yes, sometimes they don’t trust, see the small business they don’t give them the loan they required anymore...It depend on the bank rate, sometimes what is happening right now business can fold up. See if you have staff you need to give them wages”*. Some bankers do not trust ethnic minority owners of small businesses who try to access a business loan. Irwin and Scott (2010) found that ethnic minority businesses have the greatest problems when applying for business loans.

The table below contain summary of the findings for this section:

Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Bank	Easy access to loan	Not Identified	Yes
Interest rate	High interest rate	Not Identified	Yes
Trust	Not trustworthy	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

The researcher was able to critically identify the sources of funds that will encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans. The researcher came across a few factors from previous studies which discuss sources of funds.

The summary of Theme three key findings is presented in the table below

Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Information Asymmetry	Flexible terms and conditions
Inaccurate credit scoring	Extended payment period
	Low Credit Score
	Bounce back loan is Covid 19 Grant
	Barclays Personal Loan is similar to a Grant
	Easy to access loans from banks
	High Interest rates from private equity
	Ethnic minorities are not trustworthy

Source: Generated by the Researcher

The table above shows that a lot of factors emerged from the field work.

4.4 THEME 4: TERMS AND CONDITIONS

In business loans there are terms and conditions, these include the rules and guidelines of the business loan. In this section, the researcher discusses the contract document, payment period, charge fees and sensitization.

4.4.1 Contract Documents

Contract documents are written documents which could contain the terms and conditions of some business loans. Suchman (2003) believes that a contract document could be many things to many people. For instance, to a law professor, a contract is a body of doctrine delineating transactions between people. One of the discouraging factors affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans is the contract document; some ethnic minority business owners may not know what the contract document entails. According to one of the respondent Nnake states that *“my accountant did all the paperwork”*. The reason why some ethnic minority owners of small businesses prefer to allow their accountant or someone else to go through the entire contract document, and then sign on their behalf, might be due to too much paperwork. Respondent Ola said that: *“I don’t go through it oh, I just sign because the contract is too much, they should make a contract simple”*. This interviewee believes the contract document does not encourage them to access a business loan, which might be the reason why ethnic minority business owners prefer to access informal business loans. In his response, respondent Abdul mentioned that: *“Cash and carry is fine because they know me I go in everyday because if I go ask from the bank they won’t give me just because of the question they will ask and the paper work is too much just because you need money they will ask you to sign a lot of paper”*. The types of questions banks do ask ethnic minority business owners when they want to access a business loan is not encouraging. Respondent Anu explained that, *“Not really, but sometimes they ask unnecessary questions...I think they use to hide some information until after you have sign the contact they will now tell you some things”*. Another factor discouraging

ethnic minority business owners when applying for business loans is hidden information in the contract document. According to respondent Abdul, *“They don’t disclose all the information, they put in the little imprints (this is 500% interest rate), see if you have a business, just do it yourself. And if you have savings just do it”*. The opposite view is expressed by Hassan, *“Yes, they disclose all the necessary information to me. They don’t hide any information”*. Disclosure of information is a vital aspect when applying for business loans.

The researcher was able to critically identify some factors discouraging ethnic minority business owners when applying for business loans from the field investigation. The table below contains the summary of the findings from this session:

Table 4.15: Contract Document			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Contract document	Too much paperwork	Not Identified	Yes
Questions	Unnecessary questions	Not Identified	Yes
Information	Hidden information	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.4.2 Payment Period

A payment period could be the period wherein the borrower is required to pay back the loan. The payment period could also be the period between when the loan is incurred and the due repayment date. According to Jamal, Sarker and Wang (2000:59) *“The customer pays no interest during the permissible time for payment, but interest will be charged if the payment is delayed beyond that period”*. One of the factors discouraging ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loans is the payment period and the charges when they default on repayments. According to respondent Anu, *“Yes, because some banks or lenders will tell you what you need to payback and the time frame and the charges if you refuse to pay in time... the time frame to payback need to be increased”*. The time frame is also another factor discouraging some ethnic minority owners of small businesses from accessing business loans. In her response, respondent Nnake mentioned that, *“possibly paying back when due and not*

defaulting...I tried to get a credit card before, I was rejected because I haven't stay in the UK for up till 3 years". Some lenders normally check if an ethnic minority owner of a small business has lived in the United Kingdom for up to five years before applying for the business loan. Also, some lenders are wary of whether ethnic minority business owners could manage the payment period, so some lenders do issue the money little by little. According to respondent *Abi* “*see if you are going to payback or not...I think there is no problem but they will tell you we will try to give you £5,000 and if you pay back we will give you more. So the problem is the limit of the money, how much amount you can get*”. Some ethnic minority owners of small business are very interested in the payment period. One of the respondents *Giza* suggested that lenders should: “*Make things simple*”. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses are pleading for lenders to assist them to make things simple so they could be able to access a business loan.

The table below contains a summary of the findings in this section. The researcher was able to critically identify some factors discouraging ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loan.

Table 4.16: Payment Period			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Payback	Problem with payback	Not Identified	Yes
Charges	Fees for late payment	Not Identified	Yes
Time frame	Not enough time frame	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.4.3 Charges or Fees

Charges or fees could be the amount of money required when a loan is granted or when the borrower defaults on repaying the loan at the due date. These charges or fees could be the interest rate or annual percentage rate (APR). Some lenders do charge a certain percentage for not paying on time.

According to respondent Nnake

“If you borrow from somebody and if they ask for interest you will pay, the thing is instead of you to pay so that you don’t pay the late fee charges because they do charge, for my credit card they charge me like 12% if I don’t pay the minimum payment in a month, so if I pay the minimum payment they won’t charge me the £12 for late fees so the earlier I pay the better for me. As long as you keep using the card to make purchases they are certain charges that are accrued to the card as well so if you are buying something £50 now they will put a charge now interest on that £50 maybe like let say £2 on it so if you are going to pay minimum payment that is £38 pounds you have to increase it, if you keep on making that payment the interest will increase on the card, you will have to make at least more than that minimum payment whether you pay minimum payment this month”.

Some ethnic minority business owners are discouraged when they want to access business loans because of the late payment charges. Neuberger and Rathke-Doppner (2015) found that the largest pressures on loan prices are late payments. Another factor that does discourage these small business owners when applying for business loans is interest rates. One of the respondents Mohammed mentioned that: *“You have to pay some kind of fixed interest, like the interest rate will rise upon the due payment and I don’t think the bank and the lender will think of anything else aside the money. Just to increase the interest and if you agree with it that’s it and nothing else”.* Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that some lenders do not inform them properly about all the charges.

In his response Ola said that:

“They don’t really tell you, they will just say this and that is all, they don’t hide the interest rate but some time you discover that they hide something like that you know if you are paying off your loan if you want to pay it off early you will discover that you need to pay £50 extra and they will not tell you until when you want to pay off the loan they will now tell you it is remaining £50”.

Hidden charges or fees do discourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans. A similar view was held by respondent James: *“No they hide a lot, the interest rate will change, like after a year the interest rate will go up. They will tell you we will keep it the same but it will go up next time, that is what they will do to make more money”.*

Changes in interest rates, or not informing borrowers about increases in the interest rate, is also

another factor that normally discourages interviewees when applying for business loans. This is contrary to the view held by respondent Nnake, who said:

“no they will tell you, even the credit card that I have, all the document that they send to me via email it will show that if you did not make any payment there is a charge, if you make or buy anything there is a charge, if you use the card at certain pay point to withdraw money there is a charge so everything is on the documentation that they send to me via email so I don’t think they hide anything”.

Some ethnic minority business owners do not thoroughly read all the documents send to them by the lender, this might be the reason that they feel there are hidden charges in a business loan. However, some ethnic minority owners of small businesses have been able to look for solutions to extra charges.

According to respondent Bola:

“if I default on the payment then I am in debt, rather I will pay upfront for what I may need so I don’t know much lenders apart from the other two I told you earlier funding circle because they keep writing me and the other one, there was the other one I mention capital one and then my bank”. Paying upfront is the solution to avoiding extra charges or fees.

From the field investigation, the researcher was able to critically identify some factors discouraging ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans. The table below consists of summarized findings in this section:

Table 4.17: Charges or Fees			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Fees	Late Fees	Late fees	No
Interest	Fixed interest	Not Identified	Yes
Charges	Hidden charges	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.4.4 Sensitization

Sensitization in the context of this research means to be enlightened, in other words the lenders need to give the borrowers greater knowledge and understanding about their business loan. Some ethnic minority business owners do not have sufficient knowledge about business loans.

According to respondent Chen: *“I don’t know too much but someone told me about loan from*

government, first year you don't need to pay interest but that's very good. I'm not sure, but something like that". Some ethnic minority owners of small business have limited information about business loans.

One of the respondents Humza mentioned that:

"I have recently applied for the bounce back loans, it's seem the loan will not went through but the process seems pretty straight forward I am still waiting on the outcome of what they will say, but the grant I have applied three or four times and they've not been back and they gave me two reasons and the two reason do not apply to me so I am trying to find out why and they issues is that you only have now till Friday".

The field investigation showed that lenders do not respond on time to borrowers whenever they apply for a business loan. A similar view was held by respondent Umar: *"I know about HSBC bank, I went there they ask me to give them my passport, visa, one address for the last five years and your credit and everything. I gave them everything they asked and I don't know why they did not give me the loan".* The lack of a timely response might be one of the reasons why ethnic minority business owners are discouraged whenever they want to access business loans. However, some participants suggested ways to get information. One of the respondent Ade suggested that: *"just to do all your proper research".* In order for ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans there is a need for them to undertake proper research. In his response James said: *"The government website is one of the easy way".* From the field investigation, it was shown that the government website is one of the easiest ways to find information about business loans. Also, some recommendations were made. According to respondent Giza: *"do a lot of seminars, advertise a lot, be a little bit more friendlier when discussing it with people".* In order to encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans, there is a need for lenders to offer seminars, advertise and be friendly to ethnic minority business. The table 4.18 in the next page contains a summary of the factors discouraging ethnic minority owners of small businesses whenever they want to access business loans.

Table 4.18: Sensitization			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Information on loan	Limited information	Not Identified	Yes
Slow response	Slow response	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

From the field investigation, the researcher was able to critically identify the terms and conditions that would encourage ethnic minority business owners to access business loans. The researcher came across one factor from previous studies which discussed terms and conditions.

The summary of Theme four key findings is presented in the table below:

Table 4.19: Terms and Condition	
Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Late Fees	Too much paperwork
	Unnecessary questions
	Hidden information
	Problems of paying back
	Fees for late payment
	Not enough time frame
	Fees when defaulting on payment
	Fixed interest rates
	Hidden charges
	Limited information about business loans
	Slow response from lenders

Source: Generated by the Researcher

From the table above, it has been shown that many factors are discouraging ethnic minority owners of small businesses from accessing business loans, which emerged from the field work.

4.5 THEME 5: SCOTLAND

Scotland is one of the nations in the United Kingdom which borders England, and is close to Northern Ireland and the Atlantic Ocean. In 43 AD the Romans invaded the British Isles, although 80 years later the Romans retreated. In 410 AD Scotland was called Caledonia. Scotland is also one of the most enhancing places for immigrants in both recent and ancient times (Worldatlas, 2019). The official language is English, the unofficial languages are Gaelic and Scots. The four largest cities in Scotland are Glasgow, Edinburgh, Aberdeen and Dundee. There are ethnic minority owners of small businesses conducting business in the four major

cities in Scotland. According to Cunningham and McGuire (2019:526) “*Minority-ethnic family-run SMEs perform an increasingly important role in the Scottish economy*”. Yet, research has identified that such businesses are less likely to access publicly funded business support and training opportunities”. Ethnic minority owners of small businesses are not just doing business in Scotland, they also contribute to the Scottish economy.

It is important and useful to provide an introduction to the geographical and political landscape of Scotland in order to understand the context which this research was set. The figure below is a map of Scotland.

This section is divided into four parts. The first part presents and discusses the subject of the environment, the second part discusses the government, and the third part looks at support while the fourth part concerns the role of job centres.

4.5.1 Environment

In the context of this research, the environment could refer to the surroundings or conditions in which ethnic minority owners of small businesses live and operate their businesses. According to Warren and Birnie (2009:97) “*Scotland has the best onshore and offshore wind resources in Europe*”. Thus, it could be because of the resources available in Scotland that ethnic minority business owners are basing their businesses in Scotland. In his response Jamshair mentioned that: “*Glasgow is flexible and has more chances to grow the business*”. Business growth might be one of the reasons why some ethnic minority business owners remain in Scotland. The safer environment could be another reason why these people are trading in Scotland. One respondent Mohammed said: “*Because it is safer environment and people are so friendly than any part of European country ... In the beginning, there was like a cultural shock in terms of language and different cultures*”. Although some participants reported cultural shock, the Scottish people are friendly to ethnic minority business owners. As stated by respondent Abi: “*I move from Cardiff*

to here. I like Scotland more than Cardiff, people are friendlier here in Scotland and I have my family also here”. Some ethnic minority members had to move from another nation within the United Kingdom with their family to Scotland just because of the friendly environment. Thus, ethnic minority owners of small businesses do not only benefit from the resources that are available in Scotland, they also help in job creation. In his response James said: *“At this moment and time yes, a lot of people don’t have job, I have got 6 new staff”*. It is encouraging that these business owners can still employ people to work for them despite the current situation of Covid 19, wherein some multinational companies are sacking their workers. According to respondent Hassan: *“We can’t afford to employ more than 14 or 15 workers... Within 200 meters we have 6 shops with the same business”*. It is has been identified from the field investigation that there are too many firms within a 200-metre area all running the same type of business. This shows there is a competitive environment. This environment might be one of the reasons why some respondents could not access a business loan. In her response Ifeoma said: *“Yes I do, sometimes I feel maybe because I am not originally from here. Some people use to look down on my shop and they don’t know we generate a lot of money in this shop that could pay the wages of 2 or 3 bankers”*. This perception might be one of the reasons why ethnic minority owners of small businesses are discouraged whenever they want to access business loans.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.20: Environment			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Friendly	Friendly environs	Identified	No
Job creation	Create jobs	Not identified	Yes
Many Shops	Many shops in Scotland	Not identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.5.2 Government

The Scottish Government was formed in 1999, and one of its responsibilities is to ensure there are equal opportunities for everyone. The government is also required to ensure that the essential

infrastructures are in place (Mambula, 2002). Some ethnic minority owners of small business were able to access the recent business interruption loan. According to respondent Abi: *“Yes you mean like loan, yes they give loan to all business, all small business, the government gives two loans, one they give you like £50,000 and they give you £10,000 for the small £10,000, I think you don’t need to pay back, it is like to help you to pay the rent and other things”*. The Scottish government has been able to provide business loans for all businesses, although some ethnic minority business owners do not believe in business loans. One of the respondent Robert mentioned that: *“I don’t know, I don’t really believe in business loan unless you really need it, like I said I do not take one if not for this COVID-19 period we have to spend more money on obviously like staffs, fitting in more screen, buying more personal protective equipment, buying more delivery bags. Buying more hand sanitize and writing the signs for 2 meter gap”*. Due to the current pandemic, some ethnic minority owners were able to access the government business loan and some are still hopeful that they will receive the business loan.

Respondent Humza said:

“So the bounce back loan that was no problem like I said I don’t know what the outcome is going to be but the other one I have had issues with it. I think it would be clearer and better. So if they refuse the application, a reason should be given on how to rectify the issue and because of the current issues now we can’t talk to them because there is no body there, so there is an email and I have emailed them to let them know can you tell me what is wrong but that was three days ago and I am still waiting on their reply, I will probably get a reply on Monday, like I said Friday is the cut-off date, so I have been applying maybe for the last 6 weeks, if they had told me at the start what the problem was maybe I would have sorted it out so now I am waiting for them to tell me what the problem was but I think by the time they will tell me I think it will be too late”.

Some interviewees who applied for the bounce back loan are yet to receive it; lack of response is one of the discouraging factors affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when they want to access business loans. Some business owners allegedly feel that the Scottish government is conservative when it comes to granting business loans.

One respondent Giza stated that:

“the ways they lend money especially the Royal Bank of Scotland the government took over and they have been very conservative on how they actually give out the loan now. So it all depends on what the banks want to do, if the banks got a lot of money they will give you money to do anything...Free money and they will get plenty of business, Zero percent interest, free money”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that the Scottish Government is selective when it comes to issuing business loans. According to respondent Ifeoma: *“I think the loan issuer should not be so pick, I mean selective on giving loan as far as you have a legit business and you’re paying your tax and you have enough income, also they should not look down on small store like my shop”.* From the field investigation, it is not only the Scottish government which is selective in the matter of issuing business loans.

A similar view was held by one respondent Anu:

“I went to another branch lucky I meet a banker who is from India and he gave me the requirement for business loan so I took my time to go through the requirement I now found out that I meet all the requirement so I went back to the other branch and I met the Indian man and he gave me the application which I filed and I attached all the necessary document and I got the loan”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses have been able to access business loans despite the discouragement from the loan issuers. In her response Anu suggests that: *“I think they should work on the policy and procedure because the interest rate should be reduced”.* The way forward to encourage ethnic minority business owners to access these loans would be for the loan issuers to amend the policies and procedures related to business loans. Respondent Jamshair said: *“Dependent on their policies, no strict regulations or policies on how much money coming how much money you are saving”.* One Islamic ethnic minority owner of a small business made a suggestion.

According to respondent Mohammed:

“Yeah for sure, Like I mention before they have to consider kind of Islamic terms of loans because many or so many Muslims are into the business and they don’t even ask for loans because it doesn’t fit into the Islamic concept also like, if you want to buy house they will ask you to locate this as a mortgage this doesn’t fit Islamic religious a thing like this maybe for them to consider but not an obligatory issues”.

This Islamic business owner said that it is not mandatory for the Scottish government to introduce Islamic business loans, but the government could introduce it for Islamic ethnic minority owners of small businesses.

The table below contains summary of the findings in this section:

Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Government Loan	Business interruption loan	Not Identified	Yes
Government response	No response about the government loan	Not Identified	Yes
Ethnic minority perception	Conservative in issuing business loan	Not Identified	Yes
Some loan issuers	Selective in issuing loan	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.5.3 Support

Support could be in the form of financial assistance. For example, other nations such as England do publicly advice and support small businesses through a network called the business link network (Mole *et al*, 2009). In Scotland, the Scottish government does give support to small business owners. About 96% of small business owners were aware of the business support available from the Scottish government (The Scottish Government 2013).

According to respondent Ade:

“the Scottish government do give grant to small and medium enterprises grant for you to start of a business so if you are starting up a business because of the population the government give out incentive they want a lot of business to settle down in Scotland and I am aware of it”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses also affirm that the Scottish government does give support, although the support is limited. Giza said: *“Scottish enterprises yes...Based on that you may want a £100,000 and they may turn around and say £50,000...currently, I don’t have any challenges but in the past I had challenges due to the credit crunch period”*. Similarly, according to respondent Robert: *“NO, not at the moment, prior to this COVID-19 situation, it may be hard for businesses to get loans but now I feel like this is easy now cause of the situation of COVID-19 we had to close for three weeks, we had to fit the screen and purchase personal protective equipment but loans are easier and accessible now”*. Some ethnic minority business owners are not aware of the support that is available for them to access business loans. One respondent Ifeoma mentioned that: *“I did not know on till this corona virus period. My accountant was able to apply for my shop to be able to get the bounce back loan and the furlough pay”*. Some of the research participants made some suggestions. Respondent Anu suggests that: *“I think government need to let people know about the grant and also the same procedure on how to get the bounce back loan should be adopted for all the other loans”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses are aware of other support that is available.

In his response James stated that:

“Yes I am aware, they have the bounce back loan, they have the catering loan, I can’t remember all from the top of my head. The catering loan is only for small business with up to 18 seat or not more than 18 seat...if your company was created before the 17th of March 2020 they will give you the bounce back loan, if you apply for it. The bounce back loan was available until after the 27th of July 2020. And you can also claim wages from the government, the bounce back loan and the wages are not the same. I have got my Accountant. He helps me to apply for everything, that’s why I don’t have too much idea about everything”.

However, some ethnic minority business owners depend more on their accountant in the area of application for business loans. This might be one of the reasons they are not aware of the support that is available. Also, some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that neither banks nor the government will support them if their business cannot survive. Respondent Hassan explained that: *“I don’t think the government is going to do anything, see if the business fold*

they will not do anything, even the banks don't care, they don't even support you". While some interviewees believe that the Scottish government and banks do not support small businesses, other ethnic minority members are agitating for an increase in the recent loan amount. In his response Hassan proposed that: "I think the Government need to increase the loan from £20,000 to £50,000 or £100,000 for small business. You can imagine water bill is £720 for one year, electricity and gas bill is like £2,000, you see the £20,000 is nothing compare to the expenses". Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses also stressed the need to reduce interest rates. According to respondent Chen: "If they can reduce the interest it will be better". A similar view was held by Ade: "Actually to reduce the interest rate and to do more publicity to let customers know that oh this thing is accessible and they can increase the loan term...I did not register a limited company if I had registered a limited company I would have been able to access loan".

Another suggestion was made by respondent Naeem:

*"see for me this time is the government should give offer to the bounce back loan at a very low rate because in five or six years you just need to pay £3,000 extra, that's very good opportunity if anybody want to start business or any other thing, because it is a very low rate, low rate is the main thing you know, the government should continue with the bounce back loan because already 20% of the economy is f***ed, if they did not have issue like this stuff, it will be more f***ed and in coming days and coming years it is going to affect a lot".*

Due to the current pandemic, some ethnic minority business owners suggested the way forward. One respondent Ola said: *"Well in order to make this economy grow the bank should make the business loan easy, The bank should not target the big company they should come down for the small company like us but the bank don't want to see us so they pay that money to big company".* Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel that banks do concentrate on giving loans to big businesses rather than small businesses.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Support	Support from Scottish government	Not Identified	Yes
Awareness	Lack of awareness	Not Identified	Yes
Interest rate	Reduced interest rate	Not Identified	Yes
Amount of Money	Increase in the money	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.5.4 Role of Job Centres

One of the roles of job centres is to help those who are job seekers to access employment, and this could be information about support to access business loans. However, some ethnic minority business owners who depend on clients in order for their business to survive cannot attract clients in Scotland. According to respondent Ola: *“Well most of my client is private sector, I don’t really get a job from Scotland they don’t give it to immigrant they give it to their own people, I get contract from England direct”*. Some respondents feel it is easier to find jobs in England. Another role of job centres is to direct job seekers to the right place where a solution could be provided for their problem.

In his response Naeem mentioned that:

“I cannot remember the name of the loan because its more than 4 years now. I know I went to job center and job center directed me to the Scottish government office that they can issue me the loan you know, I have been there and they said we can issue you loan £80 a week. I told them £80 is just one game for my son you know, they said you can give it to your son. I left there I never go back there again”.

It is really unfair and discouraging that the Scottish government has introduced £80 a week loans because some ethnic minority owners of small businesses have goods or liabilities that amount to more than £80 a week. Some ethnic minority business owners suggested the best way to access a business loan is to approach smaller lenders. According to respondent Ade: *“it all depends on loan adviser or financial adviser which you can access all the smaller lenders*

because those smaller lenders they don't operate in the public that makes it difficult for people to get loan from the smaller lenders". However, some staff at job centres work in the role of loan advisers or financial advisers.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.23: Role of Job Centre			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Difficult to get jobs in Scotland	It is easy to get clients in England	Not Identified	Yes
Smaller Lenders	Smaller Lenders do give loans	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

The researcher was able to identify some emerging factors from the field investigation. During the discussion process only one previous study was able to validate the findings.

The summary of Theme five key findings is presented in the table below:

Table 4.24: Scotland	
Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Scotland is a friendly environment	Ethnic minority owned small businesses do create jobs
	There are many shops in Scotland
	Business interruption loans
	No response about the government loan
	Conservative in issuing business loans
	Selective in issuing loans
	Support from Scottish government
	Lack of awareness
	Lenders should reduce interest rates
	Increase in the approved amount of money
	It is easy to get clients in England
	Smaller Lenders do give loans

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.6 THEME 6: CHALLENGES AFFECTING ETHNIC MINORITIES

Challenges are inevitable; all businesses have their own challenges. This is normal, there is no perfect system. There are many challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small business including languages, staffing, trustworthiness and other barriers. Bouazza, Ardjouman and

Abada (2015) found that there are external and internal factors affecting small businesses. Other researchers, such as Cant and Wiid (2013) were able to identify inflation and interest rates as two of the challenges affecting small businesses. Asare (2014) found that access to easy and reliable credit is one of the factors that affect small businesses. These challenges are also applicable to ethnic minority owners of small business.

4.6.1 Language

In Scotland, English is the official language, although the Scottish people also have their other languages: are Scots and Scottish Gaelic. The main language of communication is the English language. Some of the ethnic minority business owners do not understand English because it is not their first language.

According to respondent Abi:

“Yes with the Language, the language is difficult, if you don’t know the language, if you don’t understand one word it’s like you can’t speak, you know if you don’t understand the sentence, if you can’t understand one word then you can’t understand the sentence”. My main problem is the language because you can’t connect with the people. It is very hard, I can speak Arabic but if I want to speak English it is very hard for me”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small business cannot access business loans because they cannot speak the English language. Akilli (2003) claim that some of the Chinese people working in the United Kingdom cannot communicate fluently in English language. It has been reported that ethnic minority groups generally has low level of spoken English (National Records of Scotland 2016). This might be one of the reasons why only 3% of these business owners could access a business loan. Another challenge affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses might be a lack of education. In his response Mohammed mentioned that: *“usually people who start these business aren’t people who are actually educated so they are not totally aware of what is going in the banks and how can we get loans”.* Some ethnic minority owners do not know where and how to access business loans because they are not educated.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.25: Language			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
English Language	Lack of understanding English Language	Identified	Yes
Uneducated	Lack of education	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.6.2 Staffing

Staffing could be the process of employing the person required to occupy a vacant position. Alonso and O’Neill (2009) found that staffing is one the challenges affecting businesses. This staffing issue is also applicable to ethnic minority owners of small businesses because it is difficult to get reliable staff. According to respondent Anu: *“I face a lot of challenges for example during this covid 19 period my business have been down, I don’t use to make much profit also like getting a reliable staff is another problem”*. Making only a little profit might mean they are not able to hire the staff needed. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses prefer to work in their business in order to reduce labour costs because these costs are high.

Respondent Hassan said:

“You either reduce the number of staff in other not to pay wages and you work more hours. You cannot seat at home and wait for people to work for you. The best is for you to employ one person and also work in the shop but if you employ 2 or 3 people in the shop you will not make more money because you will have to pay the 3 staff their wages”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses have resorted to reducing the number of staff in order to make a profit.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.26: Staffing			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Staffing	Difficult to hire staff	Identified	Yes
Labour costs	High labour costs	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.6.3 Trustworthiness

To be trustworthy means to be honest and truthful. Some lenders do not trust ethnic minority owners of small businesses. According to respondent Abi: *“I think they will give you like £5,000 and if you pay back they can give you more money, like £10,000”*. Some ethnic minority owners of small businesses may not be happy to apply for loans because, if they apply, the lenders will only give them a reduced amount of the money they applied for. In his response Hassan said that: *“They required anymore, maybe they are afraid that they will not payback”*. Some lenders are afraid of lending money to ethnic minority owners because, if they borrow, they might not pay it back. Some lenders do not trust ethnic minority owners of small business because they are foreigners. According to respondent Anu *“Yes some lenders do not trust us foreigners sometimes, some people don’t trust foreigners”*. A lack of trust might be one of the reasons why there is low rate of ethnic minority business owners could access a business loan. Another reason might be the nationality of some ethnic minority owners.

In his response Mark mentioned that:

“As for my nationality, I don’t think it has to do anything to do with nationality, if you have a business and you go to a bank for loan it doesn’t have anything to do with the nationality with loan. Even if you are foreigner, European, international it doesn’t matter, if you are doing business that is what the bank check, they don’t check nationality”.

If nationality does not matter, why are lenders afraid to issue loans to foreigners?

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.27: Trustworthiness			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Trust	Lack of trust	Not Identified	Yes
Nationality	Nationality Issue	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.6.4 Other Barriers

One of the barriers affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses is the number of years needed for small business owners to access business loans.

According to respondent Nnake:

“I haven’t stay in the UK for up till 3 years and with the business when I try to begin the business it was also an issue because I haven’t stay in the UK for up to 5 years and above so I think staying or haven to live in the UK is needed for you to start up a business or have a business so you have to stay for like a particular number of years before you can access anything..I am from Nigeria...How do I feel, it’s a hustle because I am not from here, when I finally get it. I feel okay, I feel good but trying to get it is a problem, it is stressful...you have to be resident in the UK for I think it is 5 years and above then you have to..i think that is the only one I know”.

The 5 years’ residency should be reduced to 2 or 3 years in order to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses who are able to access business loans in Scotland.

Some business owners wish there were no limit on the amount of money they can access. In his response Mohammed said that: *“I think the allowance time for me to pay back and also the limited amount of money I will be allowed to take, sometimes you go to the bank and ask the bank for £10,000 they will just give you £5,000 this is your allowance”.* The limited permissible amount given to ethnic minority owners of small businesses might be one of the reasons why only a small number of ethnic minority owners do access business loans in Scotland.

Another barrier affecting these business owners is the process of the loan. One respondent Ifeoma mentioned that: *“I think they should simplify the process for foreigner and they should not look down on some people...sometimes they look at my passport and they will tell me you are not qualified to apply for this fund”.* If the process of business loans for ethnic minority business owners were to be simplified, that could attract a higher number of ethnic minority owners to access business loans in Scotland. Another barrier affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses might not know how to access a business loan.

According to respondent James said:

“Some business owner don’t know how to access business loan, you can imagine the next barber shop have been closed for more than 6 months and they did not know how to access business loan...there should be more flexibility on how to get it...they could help with the form and with the application because they have all your details so you don’t need to stress yourself to go to the bank or contact them, as soon as you register your company they all have your details”.

Some ethnic minority owners of small business are not conversant with the internet.

Respondent Humza said that:

*“like to myself I’m okay I know about online you most have been to a lot of shop with older generation half of them don’t know how to use the internet, like my uncle for example he has the old Nokia phone with no camera and internet not because he can’t afford it because he can’t operate it because of new technology so to ask him to do anything online is like asking him to go to the moon, see if you ask my uncle what is your email address he will tell you what the f**k. A lot of Asian shops within there are a lot of older generation”.*

In order to attract a higher number of ethnic minority owners to access business loans in Scotland it would be helpful for lenders to help borrowers to complete the loan application manually. Another challenge affecting ethnic minority business owners is the high running costs.

According to respondent Hassan *“Can you imagine water bill is £720 for one year, electricity and gas bill is like £2,000, you see the £20,000 is nothing compare to the expenses”.* Another barrier to accessing business loans is the fees and interest rates.

According to respondent Humza:

“Better rates and less kind of set up fees because they have a set up fees and interest rate as well so if that was lower maybe I could access or maybe do it more because right now I only do it often when I need it, you know I don’t just do it for the sake I need it”.

If the rates, fees and interest rate were to be reduced, that could attract a higher number of ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland.

The table below contains the summary of the findings for this section:

Table 4.28: Other Barriers			
Factors	Interview	Literature Review	Newly emerged
Interest rates	Low interest rates	Not Identified	Yes
Allowable amount	Allowable amount	Not Identified	Yes
Online Application	Unable to apply online	Not Identified	Yes
5 years residency in UK	5 years residency in UK	Not Identified	Yes
Running costs	High running costs	Not Identified	Yes

Source: Generated by the Researcher

During the field investigation, the researcher was able to identify some emerging factors from the field investigation. During the discussion process, only two previous study was able to validate the findings, although there might be further previous studies relating to the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland.

The summary of Theme six key findings is presented in the table below:

Table 4.29: Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minorities	
Validated Factors from Literature Review	Factors emerging from Fieldwork
Difficult to hire staff	Lack of understanding English Language
English Language	Lack of education
	High labour costs
	Lack of trust
	Nationality Issue
	Low interest rates
	Allowable amount
	Unable to apply online
	5 years residency in UK
	High running costs

Source: Generated by the Researcher

4.7 Chapter Summary

The researcher used the data analysis to discuss the findings, during the data analysis process the researcher create qualitative data analysis template (see appendix 8). The researcher used the important quotes from the transcribed interview.

The discussion was based on the six themes, the first theme is on business loans, the researcher was able to identify some key findings, some factors emerged from the fieldwork like credit rating, high interest rate, paper work and documentation are some of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loan, some of the findings were corroborated with relevant articles and the researcher validated some of the factors from different literature.

The second theme is on business challenges, the researchers identify some key factors affecting ethnic minority owners of small business, some of the factors emerged from the fieldwork like the professional fees, limited knowledge of loan and having a personal relationship with bankers is important. The findings were validated with some literature.

The third theme is on sources of funds, the researcher found out that information asymmetry, and inaccurate credit scoring are some of the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small business to access business loan.

The fourth theme is on terms and conditions, some factors emerged from the fieldwork like hidden information, slow response from lenders and not enough time frame factors are discouraging ethnic minority owners of small businesses from accessing business loans.

The fifth theme is on Scotland, the researcher found out in Scotland, smaller lenders do give loans, ethnic minority owners of small business do create jobs, it is easy to get clients in England compared to Scotland. The findings were corroborated with some literatures.

The sixth theme is on challenges affecting ethnic minorities, some factors such as lack of understanding English language, 5 years residency in the United Kingdom, unable to apply for loan online and lack of trust are some of the factors that emerged from the fieldwork and all the findings were validated from relevant related literature.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aim of this research is to investigate the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland. At first, the research aim seemed to be impossible because the researcher had the planned to go to all the cities in Scotland. However, during the pilot study, the researcher considered simply conducting the research in the four major cities of Scotland.

This chapter contains answers to each of the research questions. The primary investigation was conducted among ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland in order to attain the aim of this research. The previous chapter presents the data analysis and the discussion of the findings for this research. The researcher was able to identify some challenges affecting ethnic minority business owners when applying for business loans in Scotland. Chapter 2, the researcher took time to review over fifty relevant related articles. A systematic literature review table was created to indentify the gaps. This chapter also presented the recommendations for policy makers, ethnic owners of small businesses and prospective ethnic entrepreneurs. This study opens further areas for future research. The researcher further discussed the limitations and contributions of this study.

In order to accomplish the aim of this research, in this chapter the researcher attempts to address the following research questions in the next page

RQ 1. *What are the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland?.*

RQ 2. *What are the opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loans in Scotland?.*

RQ 3. *How can banks encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.*

RQ 4. *What can be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland?.*

5.1 Research Question One

What are the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses when applying for business loans in Scotland?

The statement above is the first question. In order for the researcher to answer the research question, the researcher first of all carried out a critical literature review. During the process of the literature review, the researcher was able to identify some challenges affecting ethnic minority owners when applying for business loans such as *information asymmetries, credit checks, and interest rates*. (Ekpu (2011): Shikumo and Mwangi (2016): Blanchard, Zhao and Yinger (2005): Petersen and Raja (1994): Asiedu, Freeman and Nti-Addae (2012): Glantz (2015): Lewis (2011): Crawford, Pavanini and Schivardi (2015): Ikeda (2019). However, some of the literature focuses more on small businesses in general.

During the field investigation, the researcher identified some factors affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses, such as the *strict process of business loans*. It is difficult for new business owners to access business loans, due to *thorough credit checks* and other factors.

In terms of business challenges, the researcher identified some business challenges from the prior literature. This included *information opacity* (Ortiz-Molina and Penas 2008) and *good relationship* (Singh, 2019), ethnic minority owners of small businesses having limited knowledge of how to access business loans and the importance for ethnic minority business owners to have a good relationship with their bankers in order to access business loans. Some factors emerged from the fieldwork. These included participants having *limited knowledge* of business loan leading them to employ an accountant or agent to apply for the loan on their behalf. Other factors included *expensive professional fees*, not being able to meet the *requirements* of business loans *not being aware* of business loans.

In this research, the researcher identified some new challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loans. From the above discussion it could be said that research question one has been answered.

5.2 Research Question Two

What are the opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loans in Scotland?.

The statement above is the second question. In order to answer the second question, the researcher looked at sources of funding and the terms and conditions when applying for a business loan. The researcher came across *information asymmetry* (Liao, Chen and Lu, 2009) and *credit history* (Cavalluzzo and Wolken 2005) in some literature as being some of the factors affecting ethnic minority business owners when applying for business loans. Furthermore, the opportunities when applying for business loans are *flexibility in the terms of payment; extended payment periods*; small business owners being able to access business loans, even when they have a low credit score, through informal business loans; and the bounce back loan having a low interest rate with no repayment due in the first twelve months.

In this research, the researcher was able to identify some new opportunities when ethnic minority owners of small businesses access business loan. From the above discussion it could be said that the second research question has been answered.

5.3 Research Question Three

How can banks encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland?.

The statement above is the third question. The researcher explored what banks could to encourage ethnic minority business owners to access business loans in Scotland, since Scotland is the location of the case study. The researcher found that Scotland is a *friendly environment* (Warren and Birnie 2009) and this finding was validated by prior studies.

Some factors emerged from the field investigation on how banks could encourage these small business owners to access business loans. For example, banks should *create more awareness of business loans*, banks should *not be selective in issuing loans*, and banks should *offer reduced interest rates*.

In this research, the researcher was able to identify some emerging factors from the fieldwork investigation. From the above discussion, it could be said that the third research question has been answered.

5.4 Research Question Four

What can be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland?.

The statement above is the fourth question. In order to answer the final question on how to increase the rate of borrowing among the selected group, the researcher explored the challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small businesses. These could include *language barriers*, *staffing*, *trustworthiness* and other barriers.

The researcher found that some ethnic minority owners are *unable to complete online applications* for business loan. This could be because they do not understand the English language, and the *permissible amount of lending* to ethnic minority owners of small businesses is not encouraging.

In this research, the researcher was able to identify what could be done to improve the low rate of ethnic minority owners of small business who access business loans. However, factors emerged from the fieldwork. From the above discussion it could be said that the fourth research question has been answered.

5.5 Recommendations

This research has four research questions and research objectives. Based on these questions and objectives the researcher was able to identify some challenges affecting ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loans. The recommendations are as follows:

1. **Publicity and Advertising:** from the fieldwork investigation, some ethnic minority owners of small businesses are not aware of some of the business loans that are available for them to access. This could be due to a lack of publicity and advertisement, or insufficient publicity and advertisement.
2. **Reduction of Interest Rates and Fees:** Some ethnic minority owners of small business would be willing to access a business loan if the interest rate and some fees were reduced. During the fieldwork investigation some participants expressed their views about interest rates and fees. So, it would be better if lenders could reduce interest rates and fees in order to encourage ethnic minority owners of small business to access business loans.
3. **Loan Requirements:** From the fieldwork investigation, the researcher found out that one of the reasons why some small business owners could not access a business loan in Scotland is because of the loan requirements. It would be beneficial if lenders could simplify loan requirements for ethnic minority owners of small business to enable them to access business loans.
4. **Education on How to Apply for Loans:** Some ethnic minority owners of small business are not educated and some of them do not know how to apply for business loans. Specifically, some members of the older generation cannot access the internet. Therefore, it would be better if lenders could have an officer who would educate ethnic minority business owners as to how to apply for loans, or lenders could help ethnic minority owners of small businesses to apply online.

5. **Terms and Condition:** from the fieldwork investigation, it could be said that one of the reasons why ethnic minority owners of small businesses could not access business loans might be because of their terms and conditions., If lenders could ensure that the terms and conditions include flexibility then many interviewees reported that they would be happy to access a business loan.
6. **Business Interruption Loans:** The Scottish government could ensure a similar loan same as the business interruption loan that was available for business owner's during covid 19 pandemic which ethnic minority owners of small businesses benefited from. This is because the business interruption loan has a low interest rate and the borrower will not make any instalment payment during the first 12 months after receiving the loan.
7. **Language:** from the fieldwork investigation, some ethnic minority owners of small businesses do not understand English, because it is not their first language. It would be helpful if lenders were to have translators or interpreters or maybe employees in larger cities who also spoke the ethnic languages. This would enable ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans.
8. **Trust:** Some lenders do not trust ethnic minority business owners because of their nationality or, perhaps, because of the perception they have of one particular such business owner. It would be beneficial if lenders could have a little trust or build trust with ethnic minority owners of small businesses, which would encourage them to access business loans.
9. **Nationality and 5 Years Residency in the UK:** from the fieldwork investigation, the researcher found that some of the ethnic minority owners of small businesses cannot access a business loan because they have not reside in the United Kingdom for up to 5 years, and because of their nationality. If lenders could reduce the 5 years' residency criteria then many of these business owners would be able to access business loans.

10. Empowerment Programs: The Scottish government, charity organisation or lending agencies should introduce empowerment programs specifically for ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland on business loans. And the empowerment programs could be held at the church, at the mosque or in their ethnic group meetings.

5.6 Research Contribution

This research has three contributions, which are knowledge, policy and methodology.

Contribution to Knowledge: This research was able to identify some emerging evolved issues relating to access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small businesses in Scotland. From the findings of the field investigation, the researcher was able to provide some notable recommendations. Other researchers could be clever to utilize the outcome of this research to conduct their own research. This research focuses mainly on access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small businesses, for that reason it will supplement the literature on business loans and ethnic minority owners of small businesses.

Contribution to Policy: This research investigated the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small business when applying for business loans in Scotland. The recommendations of this research will be helpful to the Scottish government, Banks and Lending Agencies as to how to improve on the low, 3%, rate of ethnic minority owners of small businesses who are able to access business loans. The Scottish government could formulate new laws and regulations to encourage ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans.

Contribution to Methodology: This research was able to identify some themes from the fieldwork and some literature which caused this research to contribute to methodology. This research employed a *cyclical process*, starting from a systematic literature review producing a

survey of previous studies in the area (Appendix 1: SLR Table) table to the thematic analysis. During the thematic analysis some new themes emerged.

5.7 Future Study

It is vital to indentify the perception of ethnic minority owners of small businesses regarding business interruption loan, although it is beyond the scope of this research to do so. It would be also vital to know the actual numbers of ethnic minority owners of small businesses who are not able to access business loans in Scotland. However, the researcher will recommend future studies on business interruption loans and the relationship between lenders and ethnic minority owners of small businesses.

It will be important to look at one ethnic minority group, maybe the Pakistani people or one specific ethnic minority from Africa, another area for further research could be to focus on one particular type of business like Asian shop or African shop. Also future study could be carried out on a particular city in Scotland maybe a specific largest city in Scotland or the least populated city in Scotland.

Comparative analysis could be carried out between ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland and England or comparative analysis between ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland and the Scottish owners of small businesses in Scotland.

5.8 Research Limitation

The researcher was able to answer all the research questions. Nevertheless, this research identifies some limitations. The research limitations are as follows:

1. It was difficult to find enough published articles in the areas of access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small businesses. Some papers used in this research were

from small business, ethnic minorities and business loans. The findings of this research provide others researchers with an avenue for further research.

2. The time scale to complete this research was not sufficient. The research phase at least, should be a minimum of three years rather than 2 years.
3. Difficulties over the definition of ethnic minority, specifically in Scotland where the Pakistani community has been resident in large numbers in Glasgow and Edinburgh since the 1960's
4. It is was difficult to collect data during the covid 19 period because of the virus some participant were not accepting invitation because they do not want to get the virus and the lockdown rules which was introduce by the United kingdom made it difficult at some point for the researcher to travel to collect data and some shops and business were closed due to the government regulation on lockdown.

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Appendix 1: SLR Table

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
<p>Cowling, Liu and Ledger (2012)</p> <p>Web Source: Sage</p> <p>Journal Name: International Small Business Journal. Vol.0(0), pp.1-23.</p>	<p>Small business financing in the UK before and during the current financial crisis</p>	<p>The purpose of this study is to use empirical evidence from the UK to consider how demand for external finance changed as the economy entered recession and whether external finance became more difficult for entrepreneurs to access as the recession progressed.</p>	<p>Empirical</p>	<p>Theory of Entrepreneurships</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New business • Small business 	<p>Research Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ1: Has the demand for credit from the small business sector fundamentally changed in the current recession? • RQ2: Has the supply of credit to the small business sector fundamentally changed in the current recession? • RQ3: How many smaller firms have been denied credit in the recession? 	<p>Data types and range: Annual Small Business Survey in 2007-2008</p> <p>Data Source: Small Business Survey.</p> <p>Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analyses and multivariate regression analyses</p>	<p>This study found out that larger firms and those experiencing declines in sales were more likely to maintain or increase their demand for external finance.</p>	<p>Research Implication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential implications of this study are the way practitioners and policymakers react to a recessionary environment is quite different and not synchronised. It appears that banks cut off lending when small businesses still want to borrow early in a recession, then later as banks relax their lending policies, small firms scale back their demand for credit. • This study suggested that further work could examine why male and female entrepreneurs act so differently in the lending market 	<p>Observation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reported analysis could be use in this research 	<p>United Kingdom</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Deakins et al., (2005)</p> <p>Web Source: Scottish Executive</p>	<p>Minority Ethnic Enterprise in Scotland: A National Scoping Study</p>	<p>The purpose of the scoping study was to provide information on the distinctive issues and distinctive importance of MEBs in Scotland</p>	<p>Systematic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social capital • Human capital • Access to finance 	<p>Variable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks of relationship • Social groups • Knowledge • Attitude • Grant • Black Scottish, Africa, • Asian and all minority ethnic group 	<p>Research Objectives are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map their geographical and sectoral distribution and importance in Scotland. • Examine the nature of distinctive issues with MEBs in Scotland compared to a white control group and MEBs in other areas of the UK. • Investigate the importance of the nature of issues with an interview-based sample with MEB owners across different localities and different sectors, representative of the distribution indicated by the quantitative phases of the study. • Undertake extensive consultation with minority ethnic community leaders, providers of finance, advice and support from both 'mainstream' and specialised agencies 	<p>Data types and range: Secondary 2001 Census, Baseline data and Interview</p> <p>Data Source: 2001 Census is from the General Register Office for Scotland, the baseline data is from British Bankers Association (BBA) and 41 face to face semi-structured interviews with MEB owners also with 32 key informants through e-mails and telephone calls</p> <p>Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analyses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study found out that minority ethnic business owners account for just over 3 per cent of all self-employed in the nation • Glasgow has the highest minority ethnic enterprises in Scotland. MEBs account for 10.6 per cent of the self-employed and 14 per cent of small employers in Glasgow • MEBs in Scotland were not disadvantaged in terms of their actual growth performance. . • There are wide differences between MEB in success in raising external finance at start-up than between white-owned firms. Also in seeking and accessing formal finance, MEB owners had lower success rates than white-owned firms. • There are richness and diversity of MEBs through the range of sectors, different ownership and generation. • In accessing formal finance, the qualitative findings reinforce the quantitative baseline analysis, indicating dependence by MEB owners on personal and informal community sources for finance. • MEB owners tend to be well educated. Some MEB owners have been willing to engage in additional training, although there is some evidence that this could be enhanced. • The key issues of diversification, crime, security, insurance and racism, further highlighting and reinforcing the diversity of MEB experience in different sectors and localities in Scotland. 	<p>Research Implication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are implications of the range of diversity for support agencies as well. • There are also implications for support agencies and other bodies engaged in delivering a service to minority ethnic communities and implications of the legal context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study did not focus on access to business loans • Why the use of self-employment and small employers indicating a proxy for the numbers of minority ethnic enterprises in Scotland • why the use of 2001 census data 	<p>Scotland</p>
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Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Li mitations	Location
Deakins et al., (2007) Web Source: Sage Journal Name: International Small Business Journal. Vol.25(3), pp.307-326.	Ethnic Minority Businesses in Scotland and the Role of Social Capital	The purpose of this study is to examine and builds upon previous research undertaken in the UK and Scotland to investigate the changing importance of issues with EMBs for Scotland.	Qualitative and quantitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social capital 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social group, Networks of relationship 	Objective: to examines the role of social capital and demonstrate that its role is more complex and diverse	Data types and range: Secondary data, Baseline data and Interview Data Source: 2000 Survey, informed consultation with community leaders and key informants as stakeholders in minority ethnic enterprises in Scotland. Face-to-face programme of interview Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied qualitative and quantitative analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMG owners may also rely upon access to business advice through a network of business contacts through their own community. The nature of networks within local communities, provides an important source of advice. Chinese business owners are significantly more likely to access external funding, which is mainly sourced from the commercial banks 	Research Implication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An understanding of the role of social capital will help banks and agencies develop effective policies in achieving their own objectives in building relationships with EMB owners 	Observation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why is the secondary data not sourced from Scottish government 	Scotland

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Deakins et al., (2008) Web Source: Isbe Article Name: Institute for Small Business and Entrepreneurship. Belfast, 5-7 Nov 2018, pp.1-19	SMEs' Access to Finance: Is there still a debt finance gap?	The purpose of this study is to reports an in-depth study into demand and supply side issues relating to access to bank finance by Scottish SMEs and whether there is still market failure associated with good, bankable business cases from SMEs that do not receive finance.	Case study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informational asymmetries 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perfect Information, • Insufficient credit availability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ1: Whether reputational and informational effects can lead to market failure in the provision of debt finance. • RQ2: If market failure exists, what are the circumstances in which sound propositions are turned down? • RQ3: Whether such circumstances can be prevented 	Data types and range: Telephone survey of 51 Scottish SME owner/managers was undertaken during July and August 2007 also Questions on how to access finance from 64 firms having problem. Data Source: Survey of 51 SMEs. Interviewed Bank Managers (RBS and Bank of Scotland) Data Analysis model and tools: Verbal protocol analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certain categories of SME owners will face the greatest challenges in accessing bank finance, based on principles of asymmetrical information • Trading records and the nature of relationship banking 	Implication: there are measures that can be taken by banks and policy makers that can reduce the existence of debt	Why Thematic Approach and not any other approach	Scotland

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Rahman, Ullah, and Thompson (2018) Web Source: Sage Journal Name: International Journal of Entrepreneurs hip and Innovation. Vol.25(3), pp.307-326	Challenges and Issues facing Ethnic Minority Small Business Owners: The Scottish experience	The purpose of this study is to gain a clear understanding of the challenges faced by ethnic minority entrepreneurs starting and expanding their businesses within a city with a limited ethnic population.	Qualitative	Ethnic Entrepreneur	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aberdeen and Mixed Embeddedness • Challenges faced by ethnic minority entrepreneurs – access to finance • Challenges faced by ethnic entrepreneurs - communication skills and the labour market • Challenges faced by ethnic entrepreneurs – regulations and management skills 	Objectives: The study seeks to determine how changes at both at a city and national level have influenced the barriers faced.	Data types and range: Face to face interview Data Source: Face to face interviews with 25 ethnic minority entrepreneurs in Aberdeen Data Analysis model and tools: qualitative data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where the microsphere is thin ethnic entrepreneurs appear doubly disadvantaged. They are unable to access resources, support (practical and moral) and advice that traditionally allow marginal enterprises to survive • Ethnic entrepreneurs mostly depend on co-ethnic part-time student employees limited to working 20 hours per week. Because of the recent immigration laws, fewer students are coming from Asia especially from Bangladesh, India, Pakistan and Sri Lanka • A good credit rating enables ethnic minorities to get financial access from the local bank. For example, a good credit rating helps to get an overdraft, personal loan or credit card 	Implication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies can help bolster the microsphere, which may be effective if linked to training and upskilling • Entrepreneurs and policymakers need to think carefully about the retention, training and recruitment of staff 	Why qualitative and not longitudinal analysis.	Scotland

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Dearman and Bell (2011) Web Source: Advances in Business Research Journal Name: Advances in Business Research. Vol.2(1), pp.194-202.	Business Financing Factors Influencing Entrepreneurs' Decisions to Prepare a Business Plan	The purpose of this study is to investigate factors that influence entrepreneurs' decisions to prepare business plans.	Descriptive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Cognitive Theory 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education Communication Individual knowledge Social interaction 	Hypotheses: H1: Preparation of business plans will be positively associated with initial investment. H2: Preparation of business plans will be positively associated with the proportion of outside investment. H3: Preparation of business plans will be positively associated with the formality of financing arrangements. H4: The incidence of business plan preparation associated with debt financing will not be different from that associated with equity financing. H5: Preparation of business plans will be positively associated with the self-assessment of financial knowledge.	Data types and range: Survey by email to about 1,303 Companies Data Source: Survey from clients of the Arkansas Small Business and Technology Development Center (ASBTDC) Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analysis	1, Factors identified as influencing the decision to prepare a formal business plan in support of financing efforts include greater amount of required start-up costs, proportion of start-up costs raised from outside sources, and self-assessment of financial knowledge	The contribution of this paper is to identify those types of selection or contextual effects that impact the entrepreneurial decision as to whether to prepare a business plan in support of efforts to obtain funding.	Future research should investigate the psychological dynamics related to planning and related management control processes. Of particular interest would be various business contexts and entrepreneurial profiles that mediate or moderate the positive effects of planning on organizational performance.	United State

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Fatoki (2014) Web Source: MCSER Publishing Journal Name: Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences Vol.5(20), pp.94-100.	Factors Influencing the Financing of Business Start-ups by Commercial Banks in South Africa	The purpose of this study is to examine the factors that influence the financing of business start-ups (specifically new small and medium enterprises) by commercial banks in South Africa	Qualitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capital Structure Theories (Modigliani and Miller (1958). The agency theory by Jensen and Meckling (1976) 	Variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Source of finance, Collateral, Value of a firm, Net income 	Research Objective: The objective of the study is to investigate the important factors that commercial banks take into consideration when evaluation credit applications from new SMEs. Understanding the factors banks take into consideration will assist in gaining a better understanding of how to improve the availability of debt finance to new SMEs in South Africa. Solving the problem of finance is important to increasing the creation rate of new SMEs and reducing the failure rate of new SMEs in South Africa	Data types and range: Primary data which is the critical review of the lending requirement and Secondary data which is interview Data Source: The secondary data was obtained through a critical review of the lending requirements on the websites of the four big banks (ABSA, Standard Bank, First National Bank and Nedbank) and a thorough review of the literature on the requirements for lending by commercial banks. Primary data was obtained through the use of qualitative research technique. In-depth interviews were conducted with four bank officials (one from each bank) responsible for credit in Johannesburg. Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied content analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The findings indicated that the availability of business plan, collateral, maintenance of a good relationship, managerial competency and a good credit score are critical lending requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The study recommends that there is the need for small business owners to be proactive and be aware of the lending requirements Commercial banks need to better communicate the lending requirements to small business owners. Government agencies that assist small businesses can also help to create awareness of the lending requirements. 	1, why only four bank officials were interviewed and not more than four bank officials	South Africa

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Haron, et al (2013) Web Source: www.ijbssnet.com Journal Name: International Journal of Business and Social Science Vol.4(15), pp.182-195.	Factors Influencing Small Medium Enterprises (SMES) in Obtaining Loan	The purpose of this study is to examine whether the factors have a significant influence on the loan assessment of the Small Medium Enterprises.	Quasi-experimental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Investment 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nation Capital Stock 	Hypotheses: H1: Presence of character will increase the likelihood of loan approval H2: Presence of capacity will increase the likelihood of loan approval. H3: Presence of collateral will improve the likelihood of loan approval. H4: 2 way interactions between character and capacity will influence the likelihood of loan approval. H5: 2 way interactions between character and collateral will influence the likelihood of loan approval H6: 2 way interactions between capacity and collateral will influence the likelihood of loan approval. H7: 3 ways interaction between character, capacity and collateral will influence the likelihood of loan approval.	Data types and range: Central Credit Reference Information System Report, Questionnaires and Experimental case study Data Source: Economic Census 2011, Questionnaires from Bank Managers and Officer, Report from Central Credit Reference Information System. And Experimental case study Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied multivariate Test, Descriptive statistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The findings supported Hasnah et al.'s study (2012) that shows that character, collateral and capacity are factors that SMEs should equip themselves with when submitting their loans to the financial institutions as the study has proven that all three factors are assessed individually or simultaneously (as shown by 2 way and 3 way interaction effect) when assessing the loan of SMEs. 	The contribution of this study shown that collateral which is a more "objective and tangible measurement" is more important than management/character which is a more "subjective and intangible measurement".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small Sample size why not larger sample size Future studies could also consider qualitative or case study research. 	Malaysia

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Li mitations	Location
<p>Kung'u (2011)</p> <p>Web Source: www.mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de</p> <p>Journal Name: Munich Personal RePEc Archive MPRA Paper No. 66633, pp.1-27.</p>	<p>Factors Influencing SMEs Access to Finance: A Case Study of Westland Division, Kenya</p>	<p>The purpose of this article is to investigate the factors that influence SMEs' access to funding</p>	<p>Descriptive</p>	<p>Financial Constraint</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Firm Characteristics, • Financial Characteristics, • Entrepreneurial Characteristics • Access to Funding 	<p>Research Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the firm's characteristics have an influence on SMEs' access to funding? • Do the financial characteristics influence SMEs' access to funding? 3. What influence do entrepreneurial characteristics have on SMEs' access to funding? 	<p>Data types and range: Questionnaires, Interviews, Journals, Books and Internet</p> <p>Data Source: Primary data was obtained through questionnaire and interviews while secondary data was obtained from journals, books and internet. The entire or target population comprises of 2,870 SMEs as according to the City Council of Nairobi human resource department, 2009</p> <p>Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive statistic and SPSS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The financial characteristics also contribute to the SMEs' access to funding • Having business skills influences access to funding • The Age of the Firm Affects its ability to access funds 	<p>Research Contribution: This research contribute to fill the existing financial gap</p>	<p>Limitation: 1, lack of proper documentation of the operating SMEs in Westlands. 2. lack of conventional definition that distinguishes micro from small, and from medium enterprises 3. time and financial constrains</p>	<p>Rwanda</p>

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<p>Mutoko and Kapunda (2017)</p> <p>Web Source: www.actacommercii.co.za</p> <p>Journal Name: Acta Commercii, Vol. 17(1) pp.1-9.</p>	<p>Factors influencing small, medium and micro-sized enterprises' borrowing from banks: The case of the Botswana manufacturing sector</p>	<p>The purpose of this article is to examine factors that affect SMMEs' ability to borrow money from commercial banks. Empirical evidence was collected from manufacturing SMMEs.</p>	<p>Qualitative and Quantitative</p>	<p>Credit rationing theory by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981)</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limiting by lenders • High Interest rate • 	<p>The main objective of this study is to determine the factors that influence manufacturing small, medium and micro-sized enterprises' (SMMEs) borrowing from banks.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Documentary analysis, Evidence and Questionnaires</p> <p>Data Source: Documentary analysis, Evidence and Questionnaires from registered manufacturing SMMEs in Botswana.</p> <p>Sample of 100 manufacturing SMMEs from a population of 329 registered manufacturing SMMEs in Botswana</p> <p>Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive statistics, Inferential statistics and Multivariate logistic regression estimation, also SPSS was used</p>	<p>The empirical results showed that longevity in position and annual turnover have positive impact on getting access to bank loans, while marital status has a negative effect on access to bank loans</p>	<p>Implication: An understanding of factors influencing borrowing can increase chances of an SMME gaining financing from commercial banks, thus solving the challenge of access to finance.</p>	<p>Future research should look at more theory like the external fund theory</p>	<p>Botswana</p>

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Owen, Botelho and Anwar (2016) Web Source: Enterprise Research Centre Journal Name: ERC Research Paper 53.	Exploring the success and barriers to SME access to finance and its potential role in achieving growth	The purpose of this study is to analyse the characteristics , including growth-related characteristics , of 'successful applicants', 'unsuccessful applicants' and 'discouraged applicants' for finance among respondents to the Longitudinal Small Business Survey (LSBS), using the 2015 panel respondents	Qualitative and quantitative research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information asymmetry Theory 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Making decision Better Information Imbalance of power 	Research Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The UK SME demand for external finance in terms of reasons for seeking, amount and types of finance sought; The level and reasons for borrower discouragement The association between use of external finance and SME growth, and the characteristics of SMEs that are successful, growth oriented and discouraged. 	Data types and range: Survey of 15,502 SME in UK, and Telephone Interview Data Source: Survey from SME in UK and semi-structured telephone interviews with frontline staff Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analysis and Regression analysis	1, There was widespread consensus between the descriptive analytical evidence from the LSBS 2015 and the qualitative business finance support provider interviews that obtaining external finance is significantly associated with SME growth.	The research implication is that government should support external finance for investor.	Future research should investigate the government policy, the LSBS data and Future LSBS research should track the relationship between access to external finance and actual growth performance over time, including assessing how those that seek external finance but are discouraged actually perform.	United Kingdom

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Small bone, et al. (2003) Web Source: Sage Publication Journal Name: International Small Business Journal. Vol21(3), pp291-314	Access to Finance by Ethnic Minority Businesses in the UK	The purpose of this study is to present some initial findings from a large-scale study of access to financing and business support by ethnic minority businesses (EMBs) in the UK	Qualitative and quantitative research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Characteristics of business owners Characteristics of enterprises Access to finance by EMBs 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> African/Caribbean, Pakistani, Indian, Bangladesh, Chinese, All EMBs, White control and all firms 	Research Objectives: Is to try to establish whether or not EMBs face particular difficulties in accessing external finance.	Data types and range: Two large-scale telephone survey, Case study and In-depth interview Data Source: Large-scale telephone surveys of EMB owners, Case studies of new established businesses, In-depth interviews with bankers processing business loan and with business support providers Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analysis and Regression analysis	1, the findings shows the variation between ethnic minority group and white-owned firms. Also ethnic minority group are less successful to access banks loans than white-owned firms.	The research implication is that new finance initiative will be put into consideration	Future research should investigate on why is there no equality when applying for business loans.	United Kingdom
Shikumo and Mwangi (2016) Web Source: IOSR Journal Name: Journal of Economics and Finance. Vol7(4), pp57-63	Determinants of lending to small and medium enterprises by commercial banks in Kenya	The purpose of this study is to explore the determinants of lending to SMEs by commercial banks in Kenya	Descriptive Research	Lending	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lending to SMEs, Bank Size, Credit Risk, Liquidity Ratio and Interest Rate 	Research Objectives: To establish the determinants of lending to SMEs by commercial banks in Kenya.	Data types and range: Census , Annual published results from 2010-2014 Data Source: Census of 43 commercial banks in Kenya. Annual published reports of commercial banks in Kenya Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied descriptive analysis, SPSS and Regression analysis	1, the findings established that bank size and liquidity significantly influences (positively and negatively, respectively) lending to SMEs by commercial banks in Kenya while credit risk and interest rates have no significant influence on lending to SMEs by commercial banks in Kenya.	The research implication is that policies that grow the commercial banks need to be adopted	Future research should be conducted in Micro finance bank or other issuing house.	Kenya

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Shen, et al (2009) Web Source: Elsevier Journal Name: World Development. Vol7(4), pp57-63	Bank size and small- and medium-sized enterprise (SME) lending: evidence from china	The purpose of this study is to examine how bank size in conventional measurement, soft information importance, competition and institutional arrangements affects SME lending in China.	Empirical	Lending	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loans to SMEs, Enterprise loan, Asset size, Market size 	Research Objectives: Is to investigate the relationship between bank size and SME lending under the context that the banks may not be purely profit-maximization financial institutions..	Data types and range: Survey, Questionnaire Data Source: Panel data collected in 2005 from financial ecological environment, questionnaire was administer to banks Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied Regression analysis	1, the total bank asset is an insignificant factor for banks' decision on small- and medium-enterprise (SME) lending.	The research implication is important for long term economic development	Future research should be conducted on how government should be involved in loan decision.	China

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
<p>Tmava, Peci and Luboteni (2013)</p> <p>Web Source: www.ccsenet.org/ijef</p> <p>Journal Name: International Journal of Economics and Finance. Vol.5(3), pp.93-103.</p>	The Role of Banks in Small and Medium Enterprises Financing: A Case Study from Kosovo	The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of firm and entrepreneurship characteristics in small and medium enterprises (SME-s) investment finance through debt (bank loan).	Empirical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> M and M theory (1958) Neoclassical theory of investment. 	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capital Structure Value of the firm Source of finance 	<p>Hypothesis:</p> <p>H1: SME-s which have business plans are more likely to use bank loans than SME-s without written business plans\</p> <p>H2: SME-s that grow faster invest more than those with low level of growth</p> <p>H3: The male owners of firms are more likely to use bank loans than the female owners of firms</p> <p>H4: The higher the internal sources of SME-s, the higher probability to acquire bank loans for investment finance.</p> <p>H5: Owners/managers with high level of education use less bank loans for financing the investment requirements</p>	<p>Data types and range: Questionnaire</p> <p>Data Source: Questionnaire with 150 SME-s in Kosovo</p> <p>Data Analysis model and tools: This study applied the econometric model of linear regression. The data processing was conducted with STATA software.</p>	1. This study confirmed that the key factors are identified as indicators that influence the growth of investment of SME-s in Kosovo	1. The main research implication is that the problems of asymmetric information between owners-managers and creditors (banks) are of particular importance which represents a clear signal for policy makers to create conditions for favorable environment for stimulating the sources of external financing of SME-s in Kosovo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why is this study limited to M and M theory only The problems of asymmetric information between owners-managers and creditors (banks) are of particular importance. 	Kosovo

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Aldén, and Hammarstedt, (2014) Web Source: Linnaeus University Journal Name: Linnaeus University Labour Market and Discrimination Studies, Vol. 2, pp. 1-19	Discrimination in the credit market? Survey based evidence of access to financial capital among self-employed immigrants	The purpose of this research is to present results from a survey regarding access to financial capital conducted among immigrants who are self-employed in private firms in Sweden's retail, trade or service sectors.	Empirical	Discrimination.	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europe, Non-European countries. • Access to financial capital, • Laws and regulations , • Perceived discrimination by customers, suppliers and banks 	Research Questions: whether banks discriminate against certain ethnic groups that apply for loans has received public attention	Research Design: Survey Research and Questionnaire Data Source: Public Registers, Statistics Sweden Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis, OLS, linear probability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results show that non-European immigrants consider access to financial capital as a more serious impediment to their self-employment activities than do native Swedes and European immigrants • Self-employed non-European immigrants report more discrimination by banks, suppliers and customers than do natives and immigrants from European countries • Immigrant owned firms apply for bank loans to a larger extent than do firms owned by natives • Non European immigrants are more likely than natives of having a loan denial and they are also charged higher interest rates on their bank loans than natives are. • The occurrence of ethnic discrimination in the market for bank loans is put forward as an explanation for these results. 	1. The main research contribute to the previous research. And the research implication is discrimination.	1. Why is this study limited to only Sweden's retail, trade or service sectors 2 Why are some information missing on firm and owners characteristics	Sweden

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Ayres, and Siegelman, (1995) Web Source: JSTOR Journal Name: The American Economic Review, Vol. 85(3), pp. 304-321	Race and Gender Discrimination in Bargaining for a New Car	The purpose of this research is to tests and confirm the possibility of race and gender discrimination in bargaining for a new car	Audit Technique	Theory of discrimination	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race • Age • Sex • Human social behaviour • Categorise 	Research Question: The key question in the present context is whether these bargaining costs are correlated with race or gender.	Data types and range: more than 300 paired audits at new-car dealerships Data Source: Consumer Reports and Edmund's Data Analysis model and tools: Econometric analysis OLS	Dealers quoted significantly lower prices to white males than to black or female test buyers	The key research implication is the perceived implication	Why is there no hypothesis	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Ayres, Banaji, and Jolls, (2015) Web Source: The Rand Corporation Journal Name: The Rand Journal of Economics, Vol. 46(4), pp. 891-917	Race effects on eBay	The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of seller race in a field experiment involving baseball card auctions on eBay.	Empirical results	Auctions	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People reactions • Bidding strategy 	Research Question: How racial bias among some or all prospective buyers could affect auction outcomes	Data types and range: Field experiment from eBay Data Source: from eBay website Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis OLS Regression	The key findings show that race effects can persist in a thick real-world market such as eBay.	Research Contribution: this study contribute to exiting literature on internet auctions	Limitations: why is the research limited to only Baseball Cards, why is there no hypotheses	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Blanchard., Zhao, and Yinger, (2005)</p> <p>Web Source: Syracuse University Surface</p> <p>Journal Name: Center for policy research pp. 1-55</p>	<p>Do Credit Market Barriers Exist for Minority and Women Entrepreneurs?</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to examine whether methodological deficiencies in the literature on discrimination in small business credit markets have a significant impact on the estimation of discrimination and provides a preliminary investigation into the causes of discrimination in these market</p>	<p>Experimental Research</p>	<p>Theory of Discrimination</p>	<p>Concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loans denial decision, Interest rate decision, 	<p>Research Objectives :</p> <p>This research objectives is to estimate disparate-treatment discrimination in loan denial and interest rates using the best methodology possible with available data.</p>	<p>Data types and range: 1998 and 1993 SSBF</p> <p>Data Source: from Survey of small business finance (SSBF)</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Model of Discrimination Econometric analysis OLS Regression</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discrimination in loan approval. Application and loan-denial decisions. Also black-owned businesses do face discrimination in interest rates 	<p>Research contribution: This research contributed to the increase of literature on discrimination in small business credit market</p>	<p>Why is the use of 1998 and 1993 data only.</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Blanchard, Zhao and Yinger, (2008) Web Source: Elsevier Journal Name: Journal of Urban Economics, Vol. 63, pp. 467-497	Do lenders discriminate against minority and woman entrepreneurs?	The purpose of this research is to draw on a conceptual analysis of discrimination to improve the methodology for estimating discrimination in small business credit markets and to provide some evidence about the possible causes of discrimination in these markets	Empirical Research	Discrimination	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Denial interest rate, • Credit history, • Credit rating, • Firm characteristics, • Owners characteristics, • Loan characteristics, • Lender characteristics 	Research Objectives : This research objectives is to estimate disparate-treatment discrimination in loan denial and interest rates using the best methodology possible with available data.	Data types and range: 1998 and 1993 SSBF Data Source: from Survey of small business finance (SSBF) Data Analysis Model: Model of Discrimination Econometric analysis OLS Regression	This research key findings are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discrimination in loan approval against black-owned and Hispanic-owned businesses in 1998. • there is no discrimination on in average in interest rates on approval loans. • Black-owned businesses do face discrimination in interest rates when they borrow from finance companies and businesses 	Research implication: some lenders may practice statistical discrimination	Observation: Survey of small business finance (SSBF) may not contain some vital underwriting variables.	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Blanchflower, Levine, and Zimmerman, (2003) Journal Name: The Review of Economics and Statistics, Vol. 85(4), pp. 930-943	Discrimination in the Small-Business Credit Market	The purpose of this research is to examine the existence of discrimination in the small-business credit market.	Empirical Research	Discrimination	<p>Concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credit history of firms/owners, • Selected other firm characteristics, • Characteristics of loan application 	<p>Research Objectives :</p> <p>This research objectives is to estimate disparate-treatment discrimination in loan denial and interest rates using the best methodology possible with available data.</p>	<p>Data types and range: 1998 and 1993 SSBF</p> <p>Data Source: from Survey of small business finance (SSBF)</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Model of loan Model of interest Econometric analysis</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Black-owned small businesses are about twice as likely to be denied credit even after controlling for differences in creditworthiness and other factors 	<p>Research implication: Discrimination in accessing loans</p>	<p>Observation: This study has examined loan denial rates rather than loan default rates</p>	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Bone et al., (2017)</p> <p>Web Source: Utah State University</p> <p>Journal Name: Management Faculty Publications, Paper 366, pp. 1-27</p>	<p>Detecting Discrimination in Small Business Lending</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to highlight the current state of this policy gap in the marketplace relative to minority entrepreneurial consumers</p>	<p>Case Study</p>	<p>Discrimination</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race • Age • Sex • Human social behaviour • Categorise 	<p>Research Objectives:</p> <p>1 To carefully review the current state of public policy, regulation, small business economy and the limited availability of data on small business lending.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Questionnaire and Annual Report</p> <p>Data Source: Questionnaire from Survey of small business finance (SSBF), Annual report from Small business lending in the USA</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis Descriptive statistics</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • African-American testers were asked to provide more information about their businesses and personal financials than Caucasian testers • African American testers were asked if they were married • Africa-American testers where asked if their spouse is employed. • Differences in the level of assistance and encouragement offered to the African American testers. Compared with their Caucasian counterparts, African American testers were less frequently thanked for coming 	<p>Research Implication: Public policy makers need to engage with financial industry, regulators, and to the public at large</p>	<p>Why is interview not conducted with owners of small business.</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Cavalluzzo,, Cavalluzzo, and Wolken, (2002)</p> <p>Web Source: JSTOR</p> <p>Journal Name: Journal of Business, Vol. 75(4), pp. 641-679</p>	<p>Competition, Small Business Financing, and Discrimination: Evidence from a New Survey</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to shed light on some of the factors that influence observed differences in the credit market experiences of small businesses across demographic groups</p>	<p>Experimental Research</p>	<p>Economic theory of discrimination</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race • Age • Credit rational 	<p>Research Objective :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze credit applications, loan denials, and interest rates paid by small businesses across owner gender, race, and ethnicity • Examine data from owners who said they did not apply for credit because they believed that their applications would have been turned down 	<p>Data types and range: Telephone Interview and Annual Report</p> <p>Data Source: Annual report from National survey of small business finance (NSSBF), Telephone Interview from Federal Reserve and the Small Business Administration</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis Descriptive statistics</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No evidence that businesses owned by African Americans, Asians, or females paid more for credit than firms owned by white males. • African American and Hispanic business owners were far more likely to have avoided applying for credit than were white male owners, after controlling for financial characteristics of the firm. • Poor credit history or firm financial conditions were by far the leading reasons, with close to 60% of owners citing these explanations • African American and Hispanic business owners were far more likely to have avoided applying for credit than were white male owners, after controlling for financial characteristics of the firm 	<p>Research Implication: Discrimination need to be eliminated</p>	<p>Observation: Minority business are more effective and are not credit</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Coleman, (2000) Journal Name: Journal of Small Business Management, Vol. 38(3), pp. 37-52	Access to Capital and Terms of Credit: A Comparison of Men and Women-Owned Small Businesses	The purpose of this research is to compare access to capital for men- and women-owned small businesses also examines the terms under which women obtain credit to determine whether they are at a relative disadvantage from that perspective.	Case Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Entrepreneurship 	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to Capital, Minimizing Risk 	Research Objectives: 1. To examine the terms under which women obtain credit to determine whether they are at a relative disadvantage from that perspective	Data types and range: Telephone Interview and 1993 Annual Report Data Source: Annual report from National survey of small business finance (NSSBF), Telephone Interview from Federal Reserve and the Small Business Administration Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis Descriptive statistics OLS regression analysis	This research key findings are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women-owned firms are less likely to use external financing as a source of capital. Women-owned firms paid higher interest rates than men for their most recent loans Lenders do not discriminate against women on the basis of gender in terms of access to capital 	Research Implications: Women-owned firms may not be willing to seek for external credit as well as their perceptions of its availability	Why is the research limited to only men and women led business, why is it not conducted with ethnic minority owners of small business	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Coleman and Robb (2009) Web Source: Springer Journal Name: Small Business Economic, Vol. 33, pp. 397-411	A comparison of new firm financing by gender: evidence from the Kauffman Firm Survey data	The purpose of this research is to compare firm, owner, and financing characteristics by gender using the newly available Kauffman Firm Survey (KFS) data	Case Study	Theory of Entrepreneur	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic condition Economic growth 	Research Objectives: To compare and contrast the financing sources and experiences of women and men firm owners in order to identify financing gaps, specific financial challenges and constraints, and differences in financing strategy.	Data types and range: Interview Data Source: Kauffman Firm Survey Data Analysis Model: Econometric analysis Descriptive statistics OLS regression analysis Multivariate analysis Linear Model	This research key findings are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women start their businesses with significantly lower levels of financial capital than men. Women rely heavily on personal rather than external sources of debt and equity for both start-up capital as well as follow-on investments 	Research Implication: Further research into gender differences in financing sources and strategies and business outcomes.	Observation: Why the use if Kauffman firm survey database. Is the database not doctored	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Fornoni, Arribas, and Vila, (2012)</p> <p>Web Source: Nulan.mdp.edu.ar</p> <p>Journal Name: Discussion Papers in Economic Behaviour DPEB 07/12, pp.1-16</p>	<p>An entrepreneur's social capital and performance: the role of access to information in the Argentinean case</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to analyze the impact of an entrepreneur's social capital on their access to information, and how such access improves the performance of their entrepreneurial project</p>	<p>Empirical Research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Entrepreneur Social capital theory 	<p>Dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social capital, challenges of access to finance, performance, Structural Resources, rational 	<p>Hypotheses:</p> <p>H1: An entrepreneur's social capital facilitates their access to finance</p> <p>H2: An entrepreneur's social capital facilitates their access to markets</p> <p>H3: An entrepreneur's social capital facilitates their access to production</p> <p>H4: An entrepreneur's social capital facilitates their access to information</p>	<p>Data types and range: Questionnaire</p> <p>Data Source: from 282 Argentinean entrepreneurs</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Structural Equations Model (SEM)</p>	<p>This research key findings are: The Performance of an entrepreneurial project depends on an entrepreneur's access to finance, markets and information. Specific dimensions of social capital facilitate access to these resources: the relational dimension facilitates access to information; the resources dimension makes access to finance easier; the structural dimension helps the entrepreneur to access markets</p>	<p>Research implication: This research has managerial and policy implications for generation of dynamic entrepreneurial projects capable of becoming developments drivers.</p>	<p>Observations: The sample is not large enough to analyze difference among specific types of entrepreneurial projects</p>	<p>Argentina</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Freeland and Keister, (2016)</p> <p>Web Source: JSBM</p> <p>Journal Name: Journal of Small Business Management, Vol. 54(1), pp. 210-228</p>	<p>How Does Race and Ethnicity Affect Persistence in Immature Ventures?</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to examine how race/ethnicity, access to supplier credit, and personal financial investment affect three entrepreneurial outcomes: continued engagement, new firm creation, and disengagement</p>	<p>Case Study</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social dislocation, • Theory of Entrepreneur 	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultures • Economic condition • Economic growth • Ethnicity 	<p>Hypotheses:</p> <p>H1: Blacks will have a lower likelihood of obtaining supplier credit than white or Hispanic net of demographic and business controls.</p> <p>H2: Blacks will invest more of their personal funds into their venture than white or Hispanic net of demographic and business controls.</p> <p>H3: Blacks will have a higher likelihood of remaining engaged in an immature venture net of demographic and business controls.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Panel data</p> <p>Data Source: the panel study of entrepreneurial dynamics II</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Regression Model</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compared with whites, blacks were less likely to receive supplier credit and invest more of their own capital, whereas Hispanics did not significantly differ from whites. Blacks were more likely to persist and remain engaged in an immature venture if they did not achieve success after two years in operation, whereas Hispanics were more likely to disengage. 	<p>Research Implication: This study can help policy-makers develop more targeted programs.</p>	<p>Limitation:</p> <p>1 Though they examined the effect of credit and investment on persistence, these factors do not fully explain differential outcomes, suggesting that other processes are involved in differentiating outcomes</p> <p>2. They do not examine personality traits including perseverance, it is possible that cultural differences in perseverance could explain as much, if not more, of the variance in outcomes than structural conditions.</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
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Hubbard, Kuttner and Palia, (2002) Web Source: JSTOR Journal Name: The Journal of Business, Vol. 75(4), pp. 559-581	Are There Bank Effects in Borrowers' Costs of Funds? Evidence from a Matched Sample of Borrowers and Banks	The purpose of this research is to use a matched sample of individual loans, borrowers, and banks to investigate the effect of banks' financial health on the cost of loans, controlling for borrower risk and information costs.	Empirical Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Bank Capital Theory of Financial Intermediation 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquidity Deposit Transaction Cost Asymmetric information Insurance Policy 	Research Questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How Can One Measure Bank Effects? How Important Is Unobserved Borrower Heterogeneity How Important Are Bank Effects? 	Data types and range: Sample data of 11,621 loan agreements Data Source: from the 1993 release of the Dealscan database supplied by the Loan Pricing Corporation (LPC) and cover the period from 1987 to 1992 Data Analysis Model: Regression analysis	This research key findings are: <p>1 Compared with whites, blacks were less likely to receive supplier credit and invest more of their own capital, whereas Hispanics did not significantly differ from whites. Blacks were more likely to persist and remain engaged in an immature venture if they did not achieve success after two years in operation, whereas Hispanics were more likely to disengage.</p>	Research Contribution: This research contribute to the switching costs for the borrowers stressed by the bank lending channel	Observation: Because of data restrictions, they are unable to examine the dynamics of the bank-firm relationship (in particular, the effect of the length of the relationship on the terms of the loan) and consequences of differences in loan covenants.	United State of America

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Kushnirovich, and Heilbrunn, (2008) Web Source: World Scientific Journal Name: Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship, Vol. 13(2), pp. 167-184	Financial Funding of Immigrant Businesses	The purpose of this research is to investigate differences in financial funding between immigrant and non-immigrant businesses and delineates factors influencing financial funding of immigrant businesses	Empirical Analysis	Theory of Entrepreneurship	<p>Concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source of Fund • Ethnic network 	<p>Hypothesis:</p> <p>H1: The scope of funding of immigrant businesses is smaller than the scope of funding of non-immigrant businesses.</p> <p>H2: Immigrant entrepreneurs are more likely to finance their businesses with loans from family and friends than non-immigrant entrepreneurs, such that the share of capital deriving from family and friends in funding of immigrant businesses is higher than that in funding of non-immigrant businesses.</p> <p>H3: Receiving a designated loan is the salient factor influencing financial funding of immigrant businesses in terms of their scope and proportion</p> <p>H4: Immigrant entrepreneurs who deal with co-ethnic clients also use more ethnic sources of capital for financing their businesses.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Questionnaire</p> <p>Data Source: from 214 native Israelis and 153 FSU immigrant entrepreneurs</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Regression analysis</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope of funding of immigrant businesses is significantly smaller than that of non-immigrant businesses • Immigrant entrepreneurs are more likely to finance their businesses from informal sources but they use fewer loans from family and friends than non-immigrant entrepreneurs. • Immigrant entrepreneurs who deal with co-ethnic clients do not use more ethnic sources of capital for financing their businesses: the share of coethnic clients does not influence the ratio of ethnic financial sources for both setting up and expanding immigrant businesses. 	<p>Research Implication: This research is important for public policy and also immigrant will be encourage to do business</p>	<p>Observation: There should be comparative studies between, immigrant and non immigrant.</p>	Israel

Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
<p>Kynn, (2014)</p> <p>Web Sources: www.sba.gov/advocacy</p> <p>Journal Name: SBA Office of Advocacy Issue Brief Number 3, pp. 1-5</p>	Access to Capital for Women- and Minority-owned Businesses: Revisiting Key Variables	The purpose of this research is to examine discrimination in mortgage lending	Empirical Research	Social Capital	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationship • Network • Professional contact 	Research Questions: Whether credit scores are used in a discriminatory manner.	Data types and range: Questionnaire Data Source: from US census bureau survey of small business finance Data Analysis Model: Statistical Model	This research key findings are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • U.S. Census data indicate women are less likely to start or acquire firms with business loans from banks or financial institutions. • Existing business owners are more likely to be homeowners relative to the general U.S. population. U.S. 	Research contribution: this research contribute to the previous research on access to capital	Limitation: The data are limited	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Mitchell and Pearce (2005)</p> <p>Web Sources: www.sba.gov /adve</p> <p>Journal Name: SBA Office of Advocacy Issue No. 257, pp. 1-49</p>	<p>Availability of Financing to Small Firms Using the Survey of Small Business Finance</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to investigate possible restricted access to credit for minority- and women-owned businesses by focusing on two types of credit—“relationship loans” (lines of credit) and “transaction loans” (commercial mortgages, motor vehicle loans, equipment loans, capital leases, and other loans)—from two types of creditors: commercial banks and nonbank lenders.</p>	<p>Experimental Study</p>	<p>Theory of Discrimination</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human social behaviour • Race • Age • Ethnicity 	<p>Research Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do lenders appear to deny loan applications of all kinds from female- and ethnic minority-owned small firms at greater rates than applications from otherwise identical firms owned by white males, or are elevated denial rates limited to certain types of loans? • Do all lenders appear to deny loan applications from female- and ethnic minority-owned small firms at greater rates than applications from otherwise identical firms owned by white males, or are elevated denial rates limited to certain types of lenders? 	<p>Data types and range: Annual Report</p> <p>Data Source: from 1998 survey of small business finance</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Statistical Model Econometric Model Regression analysis</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minority small business owners face some restrictions in access to credit. These restrictions do not appear to uniform across loan to lender type. • Ethnic minority firm owners are more likely to have transaction loans from nonbanks and less likely to have bank loans of any kind. • Discrimination maybe specific to particular segments of the loan market rather than a general problem. • Lenders do not artificially restrict the credit-market access of female and Asian firm owners. 	<p>Research Contribution:</p> <p>This research adds to the literature on discriminatory lending practices by banks and nonbanks in their lending to small US businesses. Although the existing research hints at discriminatory practices along ethnic and gender lines, shortcomings in the data have prevented researchers from drawing definite conclusions.</p>	<p>Observation: Data limitations have prevented the researchers from seeking evidence of discriminatory practices beneath the aggregate level</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Petersen and Rajan, (1994)</p> <p>Journal Name: The Journal of Finance, Vol. 49(1), pp. 3-37</p>	<p>The Benefits of Lending Relationships: Evidence from Small Business Data</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to empirically examine how ties between a firm and its creditors affect the availability and cost of funds to the firm</p>	<p>Empirical Research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand and Supply, • Cost of Capital 	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Money Supply • Money demand • Interest rate • Capital structure 	<p>Research Objectives: This study provides evidence that relationships increase the availability and reduce the price of credit to firms.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Survey data from 1988 and 1989</p> <p>Data Source: from National survey of small business finance</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Statistical Model Econometric Model Regression analysis</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is smaller effects on the price of credit • Small firms borrow a significant fraction of their debt from lenders who provide them informationally intensive financial services. • There is a small effect of relationships on the price charged by lenders. The length of an institution's relationship with the firm seems to have little impact on the rate. Similarly, the rate charged is insignificantly lower when the lender provides the firm financial services. • Firms that borrow from multiple banks are charged a significantly higher rate. 	<p>Research Implication: The policy implication is that these firms may best be helped if lenders can make their claims to the firm's future profits explicit; for instance, regulations prohibiting banks from holding equity could be weakened so that banks have an explicit long-term interest in the firms to which they lend</p>	<p>Observation: The availability of finance from institutions increases as the firm spends more time in a relationship, as it increases ties to a lender by expanding the number of financial services it buys from it, and as it concentrates its borrowing with the lender.</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Roomi, Harrison and Beaumont-Kerridge, (2009) Web Source: Emerald Journal Name: Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development, Vol. 16(2), pp. 270-288	Women-owned small and medium enterprises in England: Analysis of factors influencing the growth process	The purpose of this research is to attempt to understand the nature and activities of growth-oriented women-owned businesses in the East of England by highlighting the problems faced by women entrepreneurs during the growth process.	Case Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Entrepreneurship 	<p>Dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growth process in enterprises Women-owned enterprises and growth 	<p>Research Objectives:</p> <p>The main objective of this study is to contribute to this domain by conducting an in-depth analysis of the determinants of growth in established women-owned enterprises.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Online Questionnaire, telephone and face-to-face Interview.</p> <p>Data Source: from 150 women entrepreneurs based in East of England Development Agency at the University of Bedfordshire. The European Social Fund</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Statistical Model Econometric Model Regression analysis</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research indicates that most do not opt to develop growth-oriented businesses, choosing instead small, non-scalable, locally focused businesses providing services or operating in low-tech industries. Women who are growth-oriented appear to be inhibited due to a lack of access to, and control over such resources as, capital, business premises, information and technology, production inputs, appropriate childcare, qualifications, experience, training facilities and appropriate assistance from business development agencies. Non-effective accumulation and use of social capital hinders access to appropriate decision-making circles, and limits the probability of accessing critical management and financing resources, especially through the venture capital industry. 	<p>Research Implication:</p> <p>This research has implications for government or other business development agencies seeking to understand the growth patterns and problems of women-owned enterprises in the East of England.</p>	<p>Limitation:</p> <p>The geographic scope of this study was limited to the East of England region, comprising the six counties Norfolk, Suffolk, Essex, Cambridgeshire, Hertfordshire, and Bedfordshire.</p>	East of England
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Sepulveda, Syrett, and Lyon, (2011)</p> <p>Web Sources: Centre for Enterprise and Economic Development Research (CEEDR) Middlesex University Business School</p> <p>Journal Name: Entrepreneurship and Regional Development, Vol. 23(1-7), pp. 469-497</p>	<p>Population Superdiversity and New Migrant Enterprise: The case of London</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to contribute towards an improved empirical and conceptual understanding of the recent dramatic growth in migrant enterprise within London</p>	<p>Case Study</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversify. Entrepreneurs 	<p>Dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity and enterprise Understanding new arrival enterprise activities Start up and growth of new migrant enterprises 	<p>Research Question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the nature of this new phase of migrant enterprise and how can it be better conceptualised? How does the interplay of different diversity related variables affect the setting-up and development of migrant enterprises? What are the challenges that this phenomenon poses to existing regulatory and policy frameworks? 	<p>Data types and range: Observational and Interview</p> <p>Data Source: from London Development Agency. The European Social Fund</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Statistical Model</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic related variables are demonstrated to be important to understanding the new arrival enterprise activity, it is also apparent that in many circumstances issues of migratory status or other variables, such as those related to class, education, experience, skills and generation, are key explanatory variables. 	<p>Research Contribution: This paper contribute to the existing research and develop theoretical approaches to understanding diversity and new migrant enterprise</p>	<p>Limitation: Recognition of these limitations of informal provision reinforce the continued need for developing institutional structures that can provide effective engagement with, and support to, new migrant enterprise rooted within increasingly diverse populations.</p>	<p>London</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Asiedu, Freeman, and Nti-Addae, (2012) Journal Name: American Economic Review: Papers and Proceedings, Vol. 102(3), pp. 532-537	Access to credit by small businesses: how relevant are race ethnicity and gender?.	The purpose of this research is to analyze whether there is racial and/or gender discrimination in the credit market for small businesses.	Empirical	Discrimination	Variables: • Race • Age • Sex •	Research Objectives: This research objective is to examine whether the gap in loan denial rate and interest rate charged on approved loans between White male firms and the other groups can be explained by differences in creditworthiness, firm characteristics, and other observable factors that influence loan decisions.	Data types and range: Observational 1998 and 2003. Data Source: from Survey of Small Business Finance. Data Analysis Model: OLS regression analysis.	This research key findings are: • Black-owned firms faced more discrimination in obtaining credit in 2003 than in 1998. • The interest rate paid by Black firms on approved loans was comparable to the rate paid by White male firms in both 1998 and 2003. There was no interest rate gap for Hispanic firms in 1998, but one existed in 2003. • White women firms did not face discrimination in terms of access to loans, and paid a lower interest rate than White male firms in 1998.	Research Contribution: This paper contribute to the existing research on access to credit by small business	Observation: There was no interview or questionnaire conducted to owners of small businesses	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Calcagnini, Ciobini, and Lenti, (2015)</p> <p>Web Sources: Springer</p> <p>Journal Name: Italian Economic Journal , Vol. 1, pp. 193-217</p>	<p>Gender differences in bank loan access: an empirical analysis</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to analyse whether these differences are statistically significant in the case of Italian firms by means of a large dataset on lines of credit provided by three Italian banks over the period 2005–2008.</p>	<p>Empirical</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theory of Entrepreneur • Discrimination 	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race • Age • Sex • Financial Risk • Running a new business 	<p>Research Objectives: To tests whether female- and male-owned firms have the same probability of obtaining a loan, after controlling for their respective credit worthiness by means of a set of firm, loan, and bank characteristics.</p>	<p>Data types and range: 12,663 Observational data from 3 Italian bank from 2005-2008</p> <p>Data Source: from Three Italian banks (Banca di Credito Cooperativo di Fano, San Paolo—Banca Popolare dell’Adriatico (BPDA), and the Banca di Credito Cooperativo di Cesena),</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics OLS regression analysis.</p>	<p>This research key findings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender does not affect the likelihood of obtaining a bank loan, after controlling for loan, firm and bank characteristics • The female-owned sole proprietorships’ probability of obtaining a successful loan application is lower than that of male-owned ones. 	<p>Research Contribution: This paper contributes to the research on the credit access of Italian firms by analysing the role of gender over the period 2005–2008.</p>	<p>Limitation: Why is there no interview conducted.</p>	<p>Italy</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Dolezal, et al (2015) Web Sources: Springer Journal Name: Journal of International Studies, Vol. 8(1), pp. 91-106	Model of the loan process in the context of unrealized income and loss prevention	The purpose of this research is to propose a model for a comprehensive assessment of the credit worthiness of the client and retrospective evaluation of bank lending in terms of unrealized income and loss prevention, resulting from the application of exit strategies in the SME segment.	Empirical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Entrepreneur 	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Credit Technology Traditional Leading , 	Research Questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RQ: Is a standard credit process of a commercial bank in relation to SMEs segment configured properly and if there are opportunities for improvements? 	Data types and range: Model from previous researcher. Data Source: from Internal grant agency Data Analysis Model: Statistical model of linear discriminant analysis.	This research key findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is potentially quite a large group of clients who have problem with the bank ratings There is the possibility of improving the loan process in the SME segment. These options are incorporated in our proposal to the loan process. 	Research Implication: This research may be appropriate for banking theory and practice.	Observation: Interview should be conducted with both the lenders and debtors, and so on	Czech Republic
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Aldrich and Waldinger (1990) Web Sources: Annual Review Journal Name: Annual Review Social, Vol. 16, pp. 111-135	Ethnicity and Entrepreneurship	The purpose of this research is to examine various approaches to explaining ethnic enterprise.	Empirical	Entrepreneurship	Dimensions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An ethnic groups access to opportunities The characteristics of a group Emergent strategies 	Research Objective: To review concepts and research findings from previous researchers	Data types and range: concepts and research findings Data Source: from previous researcher Data Analysis Model: Review	The key findings are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The reciprocal relation between ethnicity and entrepreneurship More careful use of ethnic labels and categories in research A need for more multi group, comparative research and more process-oriented research designs 	Research contribution: This research is contribute to the existing research on ethnicity and entrepreneurship	Limitation: This research is limited to selected number of industries.	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Appleyard (2013) Web Sources: Routledge Journal Name: Regional Studies, Vol. 47(6), pp. 868-879	The geographies of access to enterprise finance: the case of the West Midlands, UK	The purpose of this research is to explore the impact of the 2007 financial crisis on access to finance for enterprise in the UK	Empirical Research	Theory of Entrepreneur	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to finance policy Financial Inclusion of Enterprise 	Research Objectives: To explore how the credit crunch has exacerbated banks' unwillingness to lend to viable commercial and social enterprises there by intensifying financial exclusion of enterprise in the UK and redefining the concept of financial exclusion in the process	Data types and range: 22 Interviews October 2005 till December 2009 Data Source: from previous researcher , UK CDFI, UK Banks Data Analysis Model: Review NVivo.	The Key Findings are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The CDFIs are hybrid financial institutions due to their double bottom line and that a dichotomy between mainstream and alternative finance does not exist. The current economic crisis continues to form new geographies of financial exclusion, yet CDFIs have the potential to provide a partial solution to the increasingly significant finance gap. 	Research Contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on geographic access to finance	Observation: Why was there no interview with business owners	West Midlands
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Basu, (2004) Web Sources: Emerald Journal Name: International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research, Vol. 10(1/2), pp. 12-33	Entrepreneurial aspirations among family business owners: an analysis of ethnic business owners in the UK	The purpose of this research is to explore differences in the entrepreneurs' background that might explain differences in their aspirations and examines whether aspirational differences are related to differences in business behaviour and outcomes.	Case Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrepreneurship Theory Maslow's Theory 	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setup up business Financial risk 	Research Objectives: To understand the intersection between entrepreneurship and family business, by identifying strictly entrepreneurial and other less entrepreneurial or non-economic aspirations of family business owners.	Data types and range: 79 Interviews Data Source: from founders of family-owned businesses and their family members based in London Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	The Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Despite the importance of the family in their businesses, ethnic minority entrepreneurs have diverse aspirations. It is possible to distinguish between those with business-first, family-first, money-first and lifestyle-first aspirations. 	Research Implication: This research imply the diversity in aspirations among family business owners and the complexity of the interaction between ethnicity, culture, class and entrepreneurship.	Observation: Data were collected from only England and not the entire UK	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Beck and Demircug-Kunt (2008)</p> <p>Web Sources: Emerald</p> <p>Journal Name: World Bank Economic Review, Vol. 22(3), pp. 383-396</p>	<p>Access to Finance: An unfinished Agenda</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to summarize recent efforts to measure and analyze the impact of access to finance and discusses the unfinished research agenda</p>	<p>Empirical Study</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of Trickle-Down growth and development Finance and Growth Theory 	<p>Dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to Finance Financial Inclusion 	<p>Research Question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the degree of financial exclusion across countries, and what drives the variation? Does improved access have an impact on individual welfare, enterprise growth, and aggregate economic growth and poverty reduction? What policies are effective in expanding outreach and inclusion? 	<p>Data types and range: Previous literatures</p> <p>Data Source: from Previous researcher</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Review</p>	<p>The Key findings are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory and empirical evidence point to the critical role that improved access to finance has in promoting growth and reducing income inequality The channels through which finance promotes enterprise growth and improves aggregate resource allocation 	<p>Research contribution: This research contributes to the existing research on access to finance.</p>	<p>Observation: Why the use of only previous research. Why not conduct interview or get a report</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Chaganti and Greene (2002) Web Sources: Journal Name: Journal of Small Business Management, Vol. 40(2), pp. 126-143	Who are ethnic entrepreneurs? A study of entrepreneurs' ethnic involvement and business characteristics.	The purpose of this study examined selected characteristics of the individual ethnic entrepreneur and his or her business to verify the degree to which they differ across levels of community involvement	Case Study	Theory of Entrepreneurship. Middleman Minority Theory	Concepts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immigrant Entrepreneurs • Ethnic Entrepreneurs • Minority Entrepreneurs 	Research Question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are his friends primarily from within the ethnic community? • Are her neighbours primarily from within the community? • How many times did the entrepreneur attend meetings of ethnic community organizations during the last year? • How important for this individual is the goal of contribution to the ethnic community? 	Data types and range: 1,000 Questionnaire Data Source: from 112 Asian and Latino Entrepreneurs Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics T-Test	The Key findings are as follows: 1. There are several significant differences between the two groups on variables relating to the entrepreneurs' background characteristics, business-related goals, cultural values, business strategies, and business performance.	Research Implication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic entrepreneurs business has less positive cash flow. • Ethnic entrepreneurs may see to grow profit and sales under the right circumstances 	Observation: Why is the data collection only on Asian and Latino	United State of America
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Deakins, Whittam and Wyper (2010) Web Sources: Routledge Journal Name: Venture Capital, Vol. 12(3), pp. 193-209	SMEs' access to bank finance in Scotland: an analysis of bank manager decision making	The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that affect decision making by bank managers based on real entrepreneur case scenarios of debt funding applications in Scotland.	Case Study	Entrepreneurship Theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding required Size by employees Purpose Credit scored Category risk Outcome 	Research Questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RQ1: Whether informational effects can lead to adverse selection, defined as above, by bank managers. RQ2: If adverse selection exists, what are the circumstances in which sound propositions are turned down? RQ3: Whether such circumstances can be prevented 	Data types and range: Interview Data Source: from banks loan officer Data Analysis Model: Thematic Approach Verbal protocol analysis	Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrepreneurs in the UK in manufacturing sectors face finance credit gaps Banks have standard financial 'models' that are followed in terms of financial requirements, although there may be considerable discretion exercised by individual bank loan officers, dependent on seniority. Certain rural entrepreneurs face difficulties accessing finance 	Research Contribution: This research contribute to the SMEs access to bank finance in Scotland	Limitation: This research is limited to bank manager decision making	Scotland
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Deakins et al (2009) Web Sources: Routledge Journal Name: Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies, Vol. 35(2), pp. 309-330	Minority ethnic enterprise in Scotland	The purpose of this study is to focus on identifying distinctive characteristics of MEBs in Scotland and the issues they face, compared with their white-owned counterparts.	Case Study	Theory of Entrepreneurship	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Business Financial risk 	Research Objective This study identify distinctive characteristics of MEBs in Scotland and the issues they face, compared with their white-owned counterparts also review of the relevant themes from the existing literature	Data types and range: Secondary and Primary data Data Source: Secondary data from the 2001 Census, Primary data from interview Data Analysis Model: Thematic Approach Verbal protocol analysis	Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are great contrasts between the experience of MEB-owners in different locations, sectors and markets MEB-owners in declining sectors and markets have adopted coping strategies that draw upon innovation in service and product provision and in adding value; there is also evidence of successful diversification and breaking into new markets 	Research contribution: This article has contributed to the existing literature and empirical research on MEBs by identifying the main characteristics of the rich diversity of MEBs in Scotland.	Observation: There is no formal engagement MEB and Scottish Government	Scotland
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Deakins, Majmudar and Paddison (1997) Web Sources: Routledge Journal Name: Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies, Vol. 33(3), pp. 309-330	Developing success strategies for ethnic minorities in business: Evidence from Scotland	The purpose of this study to examine issues in ethnic minority enterprise development.	Qualitative Research	Theory of Entrepreneurship	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Business • Financial risk • Sources. 	Research Objectives: This article addresses some of these issues through the identification of success strategies that can be applied elsewhere to enterprise development of ethnic minority entrepreneurs.	Data types and range: 43 Interview Data Source: from 43 interviews with ethnic minority small firm owners and entrepreneurs from the Strathclyde region in Scotland and three more detailed case studies Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	The Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This article reveals that ethnic minority entrepreneurship in Scotland has faced different issues • 2. 	Research contribution: This research contributes to the existing research on ethnic minority entrepreneurs in Scotland.	Limitation This research is limited to only ethnic minority small firm owners and entrepreneurs from the Strathclyde region in Scotland	Scotland
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Deakins, Ram and Smallbone (2003) Web Sources: Journal Name: Environment and Planning, Vol. 33(3), pp. 309-330	Addressing the business support needs of ethnic minority firms in the United Kingdom	The purpose of this research is to examine the provision of enterprise support to ethnic minority businesses (EMBs) in five cities in the United Kingdom.	Case Study	Theory of Entrepreneurship	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Business • Financial risk • Sources. 	Research Objectives: The main focus of this study is on enterprise support provision for EMBs in five cities in the United Kingdom: London, Birmingham, Leicester, Glasgow, and Edinburgh. All five cities do, of course, have important ethnic minority communities.	Data types and range: 43 Interview Data Source: from 43 interviews with ethnic minority small firm owners and entrepreneurs from the Strathclyde region in Scotland and three more detailed case studies Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	The key findings: There are complication by local authority involvement in some cases, such as Glasgow and Leicester; there are also perceived gaps in support provision for EMBs, as well as varied access to external funding regimes to enhance EMB support.	Research Implication: This research implies that there will be need for future support policy for EMBs.	Observation: This research did not cover the entire UK	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Fletcher (1995) Web Sources: Emerald Journal Name: International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research Vol. 1(2), pp. 37-53	Decision making by Scottish bank managers	The purpose of this study is to investigate how Scottish bank managers make lending decisions to small firms and the importance of criteria used to evaluate lending propositions.	Case Study	Decision Making Theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agent Choice • Uncertain decision • Interdisciplinary approach 	Research Objective To investigate the decision that is been made by Scottish bank mangers	Data types and range: Interview Data Source: interviews with bank managers Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	The key findings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was more favourable treatment of the proposition by the Scottish bankers than by the English sample. Two of the Scottish banks appeared to be more consistent in decision making than the third • 2. 	Research contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on decision making by Scottish bank managers	Observation Why did the research not conduct interview with loan recipient	Scotland
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Gine (2011) Web Sources: Elsevier Journal Name: Journal of Development Economics Vol. 96, pp. 16-29	Access to capital in rural Thailand: An estimated model of formal vs. Informal credit	The purpose of this research is to analyze the mechanism underlying access to credit.	Empirical	Contract Theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal Requirement • Asymmetric Information • Incentive 	Research Objective: This research focuses on two important aspect of rural credit markets	Data types and range: Survey Data Source: from Townsend-Thai Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	Key findings: There are limited ability of banks to enforce contracts, more than transaction costs, is crucial in understanding the observed diversity of lenders.	Research contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on access to capital	Limitation: Why is there no interview with the recipient of loan	Thailand
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Hussain and Matlay (2007) Web Sources: Emerald insight Journal Name: Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development Vol. 14(3), pp. 487-500	Financing preferences of ethnic minority owner/managers in the UK	The purpose of this research is to show that while mainstream finance for small businesses has been researched, hard to reach segments of the UK owner/manager population have eluded empirically rigorous investigation.	Qualitative Study	Pecking order theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asymmetric information Source of finance 	Research Objectives: To investigate the financing preferences of owner/managers in small ethnic minority businesses in the UK and examine their access to both formal and informal finance as well as the use of personal funding networks.	Data types and range: Interview and questionnaire Data Source: Face to Face interview and questionnaire from ethnic minority small business owner/managers and a matched control sample of white respondents in the West Midlands region of the UK Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	The Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Family and close associate networks were very important for the support of both ethnic minority and white owner/managers. All the respondents required loans from banks and other financial institutions, both at the start-up stage and in subsequent years. For the ethnic minority owner/managers, the initial importance of financial institutions declined over the years. In contrast, in the control sample, institutional borrowing needs increased considerably Ethnic minority owner/managers showed a preference for less intrusive and more “user friendly” financing options that allow them to remain in full control of their businesses. 	Research Implication: Caution is advised in the use and generalisation of results emerging from qualitative research that involves small samples of respondents chosen from a restricted area of the UK.	Observation: The data collection was centred on West Midlands region of the UK not the entire UK	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Irwin and Scott (2010)</p> <p>Web Sources: Emerald insight</p> <p>Journal Name: International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research Vol. 16(3), pp. 245-259</p>	<p>Barriers faced by SMEs in raising bank finance</p>	<p>The purpose of this paper is to use univariate statistical analysis to investigate barriers to raising bank finance faced by UK small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), specifically the impact of personal characteristics (ethnicity, gender and education).</p>	<p>Qualitative Research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurship Theory • Human Capital Theory • Social Capital Theory • Pecking Order Theory 	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Business • Financial risk • Asymmetric information • Source of finance • Social group, • Networks of relationship 	<p>Research Question :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ1. Do gender, ethnicity and education influence whether owner-managers use specific sources of start-up finance? • RQ2. Do gender, ethnicity and education, in turn, play a direct role in whether owner-managers experience financial constraints? 	<p>Data types and range: Telephone Survey</p> <p>Data Source: Telephone survey of 400 SMEs drawn from the Barclays Bank entire SME populations</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics</p>	<p>Key Findings:</p> <p>It was found that education made little difference to sources of finance, except that those educated to A-level more frequently used friends and family and remortgaged their homes. However, graduates had the least difficulties raising finance. Though statistically insignificant, women respondents found it easier to raise finance than men. The survey confirmed that – and this finding was statistically significant – ethnic minority businesses, particularly black owner-managers, had the greatest problem raising finance and hence relied upon “bootstrapping” as a financing strategy.</p>	<p>Research Implication:</p> <p>The study makes an important contribution to filling a research gap, given the critical need of policy-makers to understand different types of owner-managers. It brings new insights into its field – access to finance – and with respect, especially, to marginalised groups.</p>	<p>Limitation:</p> <p>Why is the survey limited to only SMEs and why did they not conduct interview with bankers</p>	<p>United Kingdom</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam (2010) Web Sources: Sage Journal Name: International Small Business Journal Vol. 28(4), pp. 362-377	Racism: A barrier to entry? Experiences of small ethnic minority retail businesses	The prime purpose of this research is to establish the extent of racial discrimination suffered by SEMRBs in Glasgow	Qualitative Research	Discrimination	Variables: • Race • Sex • Human Social Behaviour • Age	Research Objectives: The main objective of this article is to determine the extent of racial discrimination suffered by SEMRBs and whether this issue constitutes a barrier to entry to the establishment of businesses for the minority ethnic community and thereby reduces the potential of entrepreneurial talent which may have an impact on economic development.	Data types and range: Semi-Structure Interview and Questionnaire Data Source: Interviews were carried out with small retail businesses owned and managed by members of the ethnic minority community in Glasgow. Questionnaire was administer to 120 small retail business owners Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	Key Findings: The research reveals that racism is a problem faced by a majority of the sample of SEMRBs in this research.	Research Contribution This research contributes to the existing research on ethnic minority group.	Limitation: This research is limited to only Glasgow	Glasgow
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Jones and Parry (2011) Web Sources: Emerald Insight Journal Name: International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research Vol. 17(6), pp. 645-662	Business support for new technology-based firms: a study of entrepreneurs in north Wales.	The purpose of this research is to provide insights into key areas of business support used by technology entrepreneurs who start businesses in north west Wales.	Qualitative Research	Theory of Entrepreneurs	Variables: • New Business • Financial risk • Source	Research Objectives: The research objective is to identify a gap in the research of technology-based firms, regional development issues and, research as to the growth and sustainability of these firms.	Data types and range: Semi-Structure Interview Data Source: From eight small technology firms based on and off technology park Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics	Key Findings: Technology entrepreneurs access direct and indirect support including: grants from local and central government; help from, banks and professionals; universities; technology incubation units, and; collaborations and networks. Evidence also confirms some of the challenges that entrepreneurs face in accessing business support.	Research Implication: This research provides clear indications to public sector organisations, universities and business support agencies as being the most important aspects of business support needed for new technology-based firms.	Limitation: This research is limited to North Wales	North Wales
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Kitching, Smallbone and Athayde (2009)</p> <p>Web Sources: Routledge</p> <p>Journal Name: Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies Vol. 35(4), pp. 689-705</p>	<p>Ethnic Diasporas and business competitiveness: Minority-Owned Enterprises in London</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to explore the role of diaspora-based networks in enabling or constraining the competitiveness of minority-owned enterprises, and to offer some policy proposals.</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Theory of Network</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic Relations • Asymmetric relation • 	<p>Research Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How and under what circumstances do diaspora-based networks enable or constrain business competitiveness?. • How might policy support the enabling impact of diaspora-based networks on business competitiveness and limit their constraining impacts? 	<p>Data types and range: Semi-Structure Interview</p> <p>Data Source: From four London minority-owned enterprises,</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Descriptive Statistics</p>	<p>Key Findings :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chinese ethnic group has the highest self employment in London 	<p>Research Contribution</p> <p>This research contribute to the existing research on Ethnic minority business</p>	<p>Limitation</p> <p>This research is limited to only people with and diaspora</p>	<p>London</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
<p>Lee and Drever (2014)</p> <p>Web Sources: Routledge</p> <p>Journal Name: Entrepreneurship and Regional Development Vol. 26(3-4), pp. 337-356</p>	<p>Do SMEs in Deprived areas find it harder to access finance?</p> <p>Evidence from the UK Small Business Survey.</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is to investigate whether firms in deprived areas are more likely to find it hard to access finance than other firms.</p>	<p>Empirical</p>	<p>Theory of Discouraged borrowers</p>	<p>Dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance in deprived area • Problems in accessing finance 	<p>Research Question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) in deprived areas find it harder to access finance than those elsewhere? • Do SMEs run by particular groups in deprived areas find it harder to access finance? 	<p>Data types and range: Survey</p> <p>Data Source: From sample of around 3500 UK small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) from the small business survey 2012</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Regression Model</p>	<p>Key Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They found out that firms in deprived areas are more likely to perceive access to finance is a problem. • They found out that no evidence that they actually do find it harder to obtain. 	<p>Research implication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There will be controlling for SME characteristics, firm growth, credit scores and selection effects • The geographical disparities in access to finance are unimportant for the average firm 	<p>Observation:</p> <p>Why were there no interview conducted from both the SMEs and the lending agencies</p>	<p>United Kingdom</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Levie (2006) Web Sources: Springer Journal Name: Small Business Economic Vol. 28, pp. 143-169	Immigration, In-Migration, Ethnicity and Entrepreneurship in the United Kingdom	The purpose of this research is to examine the effect of origin (migrant status) and ethnicity on propensity to engage in entrepreneurship (defined as new business activity) in the UK.	Empirical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theory of job turnover 	Variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of workers Cost to hire Replacing workers 	Research Objective: The research objective is to develop and test hypotheses concerning the effect of migrant status and ethnicity on propensity to engage in entrepreneurship (defined as new business activity) at the individual level in the UK.	Data types and range: Telephone interview Data Source: From UK GEN Sample Data Data Analysis Model: Descriptive analysis Regression Model	Key Findings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic minorities are also “different”, but this difference manifests itself not in greater levels of entrepreneurial activity because of their ethnicity, but in reduced levels in the first few years after migration. What appears to be greater overall levels of new business activity among ethnic minorities can be explained by the relative youth of the ethnic minority population in the UK. 	Research Implication: This research has positive implications for public policy	Limitation: This research is limited to only Immigration, In-Migration, Ethnicity and Entrepreneurship in the United Kingdom	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Muzrabshovich (2017) Web Sources: Springer Journal Name: International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management Vol. 5(2), pp. 365-372	Small business loans: theory and practice	The purpose of this research is to scrutinize both practical and theoretical issues of business while showing the ways of development for the future studies	Qualitative	Lending Theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lending Money Individual Organization Debt Interest Principal amount 	Research objectives: To investigate and make analyses over small business enterprises and companies that are engaged in various fields of economy	Data types and range: Sample data Data Source: Commercial Bank Data Analysis Model: Descriptive analysis	Key Findings: Commercial banks play a crucial role in credit activities of small businesses in the Republic of Uzbekistan	Research contribution: This research contributes to the existing research on small business loans	Observation: Why was there no interview with small business owners	Uzbekistan
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Piperopoulos (2010)</p> <p>Web Sources: Emerald Insight</p> <p>Journal Name: Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development Vol. 17(1), pp. 365-372</p>	<p>Ethnic minority businesses and immigrant entrepreneurship in Greece.</p>	<p>The purpose of this research is aims to report and analyse empirical data from 391 ethnic minority entrepreneurs and 132 of their family members, from eight different ethnic communities of Albanians, Armenians, Bulgarians, Chinese, Georgians, Indians, Nigerians and Russians in Greece.</p>	<p>Empirical</p>	<p>Theory of ethnic entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural • Block mobility • Opportunity structures • Ethnic resources 	<p>Research objective: This study explores the concept of ethnic entrepreneurship in Greece, and using empirical research data</p>	<p>Data types and range: Interview</p> <p>Data Source: Face to face interview from January 2006 and August 2008 in the regions of Attica and Central Macedonia, Greece.</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Descriptive analysis</p>	<p>Key Findings: The findings of this research point to the fact that the three theories of “block mobility”, “opportunity structures” and “ethnic resources” complement each other in explaining the process of starting up an ethnic minority business and becoming self-employed, while the “cultural thesis” seems to stand on its own.</p>	<p>Research Contribution: The research makes a contribution by presenting empirical evidence of five “White”, one “Asian”, one “Indian” and one “Black” ethnic group.</p>	<p>Limitation: The data collection is only limited to few ethnic group</p>	<p>Greece</p>
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Ram and Jones (2008)	Ethnic-minority businesses in the UK: a review of research and policy developments	The purpose of this research is to assesses key academic and policy developments in the UK, and presents an agenda for future research on ethnic-minority enterprise.	Empirical	Theory of Entrepreneurship	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Business Financial risk Source 	Research Objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To outline the 'conceptual base' that underpins policy initiatives towards ethnic-minority entrepreneurship. To assess the extent to which policy initiatives have kept pace with developments in the evidence base. 	Data types and range: Review Data Source: From previous research Data Analysis Model: Narrative	Key Findings: Chinese group has the highest source of external fund	Research contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on ethnic minority businesses	Observation: Why reviewing research and policy development without doing a systematic review	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Ram and Smallbone (2002)	Ethnic minority business policy in the era of the small business service.	The purpose of this research is to review ethnic minority business policy in the era of the small business service	Empirical	Entrepreneurship	Dimension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Support need of EMBs, Issues and lessons from previous experience Access to finance, 	Research Question: the extent to which such businesses are distinct from the general small firm population; and whether differences can be attributed to other factors, such as size and sector.	Data types and range: Review Data Source: From previous research Data Analysis Model: Narrative	Key Findings: some ethnic minority groups (for example, Chinese, Pakistani) are overrepresented in terms of self-employment and small business ownership compared with the white population	Research contribution: This research contribute to the exiting research on ethnic minority business	Observation: there is no interview with ethnic minority groups	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Ram et al (2003) Web Sources: Routledge Journal Name: Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies. Vol. 29(4), pp. 663-681	Banking on break-out: Finance and the development of ethnic minority businesses	The purpose of this research is to examine the experiences of firms attempting to break out from the cramped range of generally marginal activities historically occupied by South Asian, African-Caribbean and other immigrant-origin entrepreneurs.	Qualitative	Entrepreneur	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Business • Financial risk • Source 	Research Objectives This research focus on the financial experience of ethnic minority businesses	Data types and range: Telephone survey Data Source: From previous research with 28 business owners Data Analysis Model: Descriptive statistics	Key findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no suspicion of discrimination also small businesses cannot get the finance they need to make them grow • Chinese businesses in particular 'are not able to get any external finance for start-up' 	Research contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on ethnic minority businesses	Observation: This research did not cover the major cities in UK	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

Smith and Sparks (2003)	The role and function of the independent small shop: the situation in Scotland	The purpose of this research is to details the roles and functions of independent retail shops as well as the attitudes to the provision	Quantitative Research	Entrepreneur	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Business Financial risk Source 	Research Objective The focus of this research is the independent small shop in Scotland.	Data types and range: Survey Data Source: From previous research and from independent small shops n rural and urban location Data Analysis Model: Descriptive statistics	Key findings: There is a breakdown of trust between retailers and consumers	Research contribution: This research contribute to the existing research on the role and function of the independent small shop: the situation in Scotland	Observation: The areas selected did not cover the major rural and urban location is Scotland	Kosovo
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location
Wilson, et al (2007)	Bank loan officers perceptions of business owners: The role of gender	The purpose of this research is to explore the perceptions held by bank loan officers of male and female business owners	Qualitative	Entrepreneur Theory	Variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Business Financial risk Source 	Research questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What constructs are used by bank loan officers to construe and differentiate male and female business owners? 	Data types and range: Interview Data Source: From Bank's offices in four British cities (London, Bristol, Manchester and Edinburgh) Data Analysis Model: Descriptive statistics	Key Findings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatively few individual gender differences and no evidence of systematic gender discrimination. Bank loan officers generate unique, individualized constructs of business owners 	Research Contribution This research contribute to the existing research on business owners	Limitation: The research results show an emphasis being placed on the character of the business owner and not on any other quality	United Kingdom
Author/s & Year	Study Title	Purpose	Study type	Theoretical Foundation	Concepts/ Dimension / Variables	Research Question/ Objectives/ Hypotheses	Research Design	Key Findings	Research contribution/ Implication	Observation/Limitations	Location

<p>Kariv and Coleman, (2015)</p> <p>Web Sources: Emerald</p> <p>Journal Name: Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol. 22(2), pp. 196-224</p>	<p>Toward a theory of financial bricolage: the impact of small loans on new businesses.</p>	<p>The purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of small loans on new firm performance using data from the second Panel Study of Entrepreneurial Dynamics, a large longitudinal data set of new firms in the USA.</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Asymmetric Information. Bricolage</p>	<p>Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information • Party • Decision • Transaction • Creation • Work • Diverse 	<p>Objectives:</p> <p>The objective of this paper is to explore the relationship between the motivations and characteristics of the entrepreneur, loan size and source, and business performance. In particular, it focusses on the importance of small or microloans as a factor in determining business success.</p>	<p>Data types and range: Panel Data</p> <p>Data Source: From Panel Study on Entrepreneurial Dynamics (PSED II).</p> <p>Data Analysis Model: Descriptive statistics</p>	<p>Key Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results also revealed no significant difference by gender, ethnicity, or employment status in the source of amounts of small loans secured during the first two years of the businesses. Thus, consistent with the theory of financial bricolage, all types of entrepreneurs engaged in seeking out small loans during the early years of their businesses' existence. 	<p>Research Implication:</p> <p>This research results may aid governmental bodies, educational and academic institutions oriented toward entrepreneurs, and small businesses, in constructing programs that will train entrepreneurs to be attentive to the diverse range of potentially available resources, including small loans and different financial sources.</p>	<p>Limitation:</p> <p>The research would have include interview or survey</p>	<p>United State of America</p>
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Appendix 2: Interview Guide

Interview Guide

Questions	Reason for choosing
Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?	This is aimed at discovering if the business owner is aware of the different forms of business loans. This is aimed to answer RO3.
Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?	Discovering what form of loan is easier to access by these owners.
Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loan?	To understand if ethnic minority small business owners face challenges when applying for business loan. This is aimed to answer RO1.
Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?	To find out the challenges faced when applying for business loans. This is aimed to answer RO1.
Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?	Finding out if the ethnic minority owners of small businesses are aware of the types of lenders. This is to answer RO3
Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?	Discovering the easiest types of lenders that are accessible. Aimed at answering RO4.
Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?	Ascertaining if the business owners are made aware of the processes of securing business loan. This question is also aimed to answer RO3.
Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?	This is to identify the terms and conditions in business loans. This question is aimed at answering RO2.
Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?	The purpose of this question is to find out if the ethnic minority owners of small business know the terms and conditions attached to business loans. This question is aimed at answering RO3.
Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?	To discover the challenges the ethnic minority business owners face. This is to answer RO1.
Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?	This is to discover why the business owner chose Scotland and not somewhere else to start up his/her business.
Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?	The purpose of this question is to find out the if the business owner is aware of any Scottish Government support package. This question is aimed to answer RO4.
Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation?	To find out to if the small business creates job opportunities. This is aimed to answer RO3.
Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.	Apperceive where the business owner could access business loan. This question is aimed to answer RO4.

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?	To find out the sources of finance.
Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?	Finding out if the business owners are aware of the various types of small business loans. This question is aimed to answer RO3.
Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?	The purpose of this question is to find out if the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan are encouraging. This question is aimed to answer RO2.
Q18. What do banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?	This is to know what could be done to encourage business owners to access business loan. Aimed to answer RO4.
Q19. Are you a migrant?	The question aims at finding out if the business owner is an ethnic minority.
Q20. Where are you originally from?	This question aims at finding out the nationality of the business owners.
Q21. How do you feel when applying for business loan?	The purpose of this question is to find out how the ethnic minority owners of small businesses feel when applying for business loans. Aims at answering RO2.
Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?	To find out if immigration status is one of the challenges that affect business owners when applying for business loan. This question is aimed to answer RO1.
Q23. Do you know the required information needed to access business loan?	The purpose of this question is to find out if ethnic minority owners of small business know the required information to access business loan. Aims at answering RO3.
Q24. Do you apply directly to the lending agency or do ask someone to apply for you?	To find out if ethnic minority owners of small business normally apply direct to the lending agency or through a third party. This question is aimed to answer RO1.
Q25. Do you go through the contract document before signing the contract?	The purpose of the question is to find out if ethnic minority owners of small business are aware of any hidden charges. Aims at answering RO2.
Q26. Do you disclose all the necessary information to the lending agencies when applying for business loan?	To find out if ethnic minority owners of small business usually disclose all the required information need to access business loan. This is to answer RO1.
Q27. Does the lending agency disclose all the necessary information to when applying for business loan?	The purpose of this question is to know if lending agency usually discloses all the required information need to access business loan. This is to answer RO1.
Q28. What type of business are you running?	This is to find out the kind of business run by these owners.
Q29. Why did you start this particular business?	Its targeted at finding out the reason behind the establishment of the business.
Q30. Who are your target customers?	The purpose of this is to know who the target

	customers are and if there are ethnic minorities.
Q31. Are there easy ways to get business loan?	To ascertain easy ways to get business loan. This question is aimed at answering RO4.
Q32. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?	This question is aimed to find out what could be done to attract more business owners in accessing business loans. This question is aimed to answer RO4.
Q33. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?	The purpose of this question is to know what other ways loan issuers could encourage business owners to access loan. This question aimed to answer RO2.
Q34. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?	This is aimed to find out if there are any options or parameters to attract high number of business owners to access business loan. This is aimed to answer RO4.

Appendix 3: Interview Question

Interview Question

Personal Background Information

Type of Business: Business Location: Numbers of Employees: Time of Interview:
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2.1 Access to Business Loan

- Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?
- Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?
- Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loan?
- Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?
- Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?
- Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?

2.2 Process of Business Loan

- Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?
- Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?
- Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?

2.3 Ethnic Minority

- Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?

2.4 Small Business in Scotland

- Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?
- Q12. Does your business play an important role in job creation?
- Q13. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?

2.5 Types of Small Business Loan

Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?

Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?

Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?

Q18. What do banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?

2.6 Theories and Concepts

Q19. Are you a migrant?

Q20. Where are you originally from?

Q21. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?

Q22. How do you feel when applying for business loan?

Q23. Do you know the required information needed to access business loan?

Q24. Do you apply directly to the lending agency or do ask someone to apply for you?

Q25. Do you go through the contract document before signing the contract?

Q26. Do you disclose all the necessary information to the lending agencies when applying for business loan?

Q27. Does the lending agency disclose all the necessary information to when applying for business loan?

Others

Q28. What type of business are you running?

Q29. Why did you start this particular business?

Q30. Who are your target customers?

Q31. Are there easy ways to get business loan?

Q32. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?

Q33. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?

Q34. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?

Appendix 4: Sample Invitation Letter to Participants

Jonah Udeme Inyang
School of Business and Creative Industries
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
Scotland

The CEO,

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Dear Sir/Madam,

Letter of introduction

I am a doctoral researcher. While studying about access to business loan in Scotland, According to small business Scotland survey only three percent of ethnic minority owners of small business can access business loan in Scotland.

I am currently pursuing a Doctorate Degree at the University of the West of Scotland. My research involves examining access to business loans by ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland. The aim of this study is to investigate the challenges faced by ethnic minority owners of small businesses to access business loans in Scotland. It is in this context that I write to ask you for your assistance in helping me contribute to knowledge in this domain.

From the information obtained from the small business Scotland survey, it appears that you fit the ideal profile to provide the information I require to generate theory in this area. The information obtained show that your business is owned by an ethnic minority

I understand and appreciate that time is always the essence in business. Nevertheless, I would appreciate if you could spare me about thirty five minutes of your time to talk about access to business loans in Scotland. In addition, If you might be concerned about the confidentiality of the information provided, I wish to assure you that all ethical guidelines will be observed and all information collected will be treated in confidence. In addition, the anonymity of your identity is guaranteed. I believe your generous participation will have a significant contribution to the study.

I hope you can assist me and I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours Sincerely,

Jonah Udeme Inyang

Appendix 5: Individual consent from

Research Title: Access to Business Loans by Ethnic Minority Owners of Small Business in Scotland

Title of Research	Access to Business Loans by Ethnic Minority Owners of Small Business in Scotland
Name of Researcher	Name of Researcher Jonah Udeme Inyang
Name of Director of Studies	Dr Ahmed Beloucif
Address for correspondence	Jonah Udeme Inyang, School of Business and Creative Industries. University of the West of Scotland, Paisley Scotland. PA1 2BE
Telephone	██████████
E-mail address	██
Description of the broad nature of the research	To gather data via exploring the experiences of access to business loan by ethnic minority owners of small business in Scotland
Description of the involvement expected of participants including the broad nature of questions to be answered and the expected time commitment	<p>The expected involvement of the research participants is an approximate 1 hour 10 minutes interview.</p> <p>The interviews will be semi-structured and based upon the ethnic minority owners of small business access to business loans</p> <p>All interviews will be recorded with a digital voice recorder and transcribed verbatim.</p> <p>Anonymity will be assured by using codes rather than the names of the participants, organisation on the interview transcripts.</p> <p>Interview transcripts will be emailed or posted back to the respondents to verify the accuracy of the content. Participants are free to make any amendments, deletions or additions to the transcript.</p> <p>Confidentiality will be maintained in terms of storing data securely on a coded external storage and ensuring hard copies are stored in a locked cupboard.</p> <p>All data will be stored securely either electronically on coded external drive or in a hard copy version in a locked cupboard. As part of the data analysis process, hard copies of the anonymised transcripts may be given to the doctoral supervision team to review to ensure that the researcher's analysis is valid. Hard copies will be returned to the researcher and will not remain in the possession of the research participants.</p> <p>Data will be used and reproduced as case studies in a variety of research publications.</p>
Additional information about the research	The data collection timescale of this study is from December 2019 – June 2020

Information provided in this study will be anonymous (i.e. individuals and organisations will not be identified unless this is expressly excluded in the details given above).

Data obtained through this research may be reproduced and published in a variety of forms and for a variety of audiences related to the broad nature of the research detailed above. It will not be used for

purposes other than those outlined above without your permission. Participation is entirely voluntary and participants may withdraw at any time.

By signing this consent form, you are indicating that you fully understand the above information and agree to participate in this study on the basis of the above information.

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

Name of Researcher

Signature

Date

Appendix 6: Pilot Interview Sample

Interview.1

Interviewee: Bobby

Type of Business: Everest Tarnadool (Indian Takeaway)

Business Location: Glasgow, Scotland

Numbers of Employees: 13

Time of Interview: 4pm, 10th Dec 2020

Access to Business Loan

Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?

A1 No.. only house mortgage

Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?

*A2 No easy way for anything..*laughs**

Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loan?

A3 No, no,no

Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?

A4 No challenges.

Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?

A5 Lenders?. No, no,no

Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?

A6 Business loan, normal type.

Process of Business Loan

Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?

A7 no, I have not done that before.

Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?

A8 No

Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?

A9 Don't have idea.

Ethnic Minority

Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?

A10 No challenges.

Small Business in Scotland

Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?

A11 I first came to Scotland, so that is why I am living here.

Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?

A12 No idea, no no.

Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation?

A13 We are only 3 staff, its difficult to get staff in Glasgow. that is different like, no one can make like Indian food like that you know.

Types of Small Business Loan

Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.

A14 No savings, no nothing. Just use money. Coming judging, no much savings.

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?

A15 Yes

Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?

A16 Banks

Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?

A17 Well banks, look at the income, how you can pay loans you know.

Q18. What could banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A18 I don't know, man!

Theories and Concepts

Q19. Are you a migrant?

A19 Yes

Q20. Where are you originally from?

A20 I am Indian

Q21. How do you feel when applying for business loan?

A21 I have not access business loan but if someone want to access it. He can if he can take it, if he needs something to do then he can take it.

Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?

A22 No, I have got a permanent stay residence here, so I don't need this. yea, I have my Indian passport too. Same rights to each passports, can get anything

Others

Q23. What type of business are you running?

A23 It is an Indian Takeaway, fast food

Q24. Why did you start this particular business?

A24 Nothing, I have an experience with this and making food. I first came to Scotland, so that is why I am living here.

Q25. Who are your target customers?

A25 Some Scottish people come here too

Q26. Are there easy ways to get business loan?

A26 No, no, no

Q27. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?

A27 No no no

Q28. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A28 I don't know

Q29. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?

A29 No but the Immigration rules makes it difficult to find experience people to make Indian food. too hard because of legal and some are illegal. So it is hard to get people you know, legal papers you know.

Interview.2

Interviewee: Owoeye Gbenga John

Type of Business: LarryTino (African Shop)

Business Location: Glasgow, Scotland

Numbers of Employees: 14

Time of Interview: 11:30am, 18th Jan 2020

Access to Business Loan

Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?

A1 Yes, yes, yes. We have credit cards though personally I don't have credit cards like I told you, I don't believe in those, I believe if I have £1 it is my money than having £10000 in my account and £9000 is for the bank and £1000 is mine. My wife gets lots of deals from them, so it stressful for me

Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?

*A2 Ah *in agreement* yes, it is easy ,very simple, I don't need to sign any agreement just give me the goods, sell it and return your money.*

Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loan?

*A3 Well, I don't.... *stutters**

Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?

A4 Its not part of my system, you know back home. I am not free with getting a loan, I believe having 10 naira(Nigerian currency) with me, you can use it with whatever is better than having a lot of Glasgow and 90% of it is not mine, so..so I don't believe in loan. Let me put it that way

Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?

A5 No. I won't lie.. I don't I don't.

Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?

A6 Suppliers: I don't need to go for bank loans or credit cards. I get goods from my suppliers on credit then I pay back to them.

Process of Business Loan

Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?

A7 Inflow and Outflow of cash: yes, a business that is genuine and you can pay the money back, this so so amount of money is coming every month and going every month. So they know is genuine business, so if they give you something, you will definitely return it, it is only that we don't believe in the loan system, that's it. We don't trust it, talk less of whether they will give us or not give us.

Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?

A8 I think they check credit notes or what do you call it. I don't borrow money from anybody and I am 100% perfect, I don't take credit or loan so whatever they want to check they check it online. So they don't need to ask me if I have a British passport, I am not British , I'm Nigerian, but I have passport to stay in the country.

Yes I think its based on documentation they will determine what to give you

Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?

A9 The question is difficult to answer, cause I don't have, the only thing is the credit card and my wife has like 2 or 3 and I don't have idea how , they have contacted me and have given me different and I just don't believe in credit card.

I don't know but the credit card part I know They asked my wife about her passport, where she is working and they checked credit rating then by then they know how much they could give her.

Ethnic Minority

Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?

A10 Well, what you don't try, you don't know how possible it is, most times they send letters, even my bank ...erhm.. send letters to us like if you want loans, so they give us offers to us if we want loan.

Yes, I get offers from business banks but as an African we don't believe in loan

Small Business in Scotland

Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?

A11 I studied here and I have my family here so that's why I think I can have my business here as well, so that's why.

Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?

A12 They give but only to Scottish people. Let me not lie to you. Unless they give it direct if you are Scottish or someone who has settled down (permanent residence in the UK)

Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation?

A13 Well, I think so, at least I have people working for me and I think I am helping the community.

Types of Small Business Loan

Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.

A14 Yes, what happens is that there are some level the business in, so some suppliers gives us like credit then after one week we pay them back. So we don't

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?

A15 Yes and credit from suppliers

So what happen is when we start the business, we use our own money to start it but when you are in the business for more than 5 years, they know that you are persisting and that you are not running away. So any suppliers I want to meet now just tell him for the first 6 months I will be paying you after 6 months you will give me the goods first then maybe like you give

me 1 week or 2-3 weeks, despite the fact that I have not finished with your stuff, but after two weeks or one I pay your money back.

Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?

A16 Credit Card: yes I know, like the card payments now , they normally send me letter like they can give me like £5000-10000, if I want to start that business, but like there's no need of taking the money that you don't need. I don't know if you understand. when you take money from somebody and put it in the bank, the business is not very big , in the future when I have something that my hand cannot carry then I may look for people that need but me, the shop is not as big but I believe I can handle it.

Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?

A17 Well...like...no to me, but is not that it's not encouraging, it depends on individual maybe individual belief. Me as a person the only thing I loan in this country is my car which apart from my car all other things is cash. Because it's a car and I can't go to buy car of £10000, i'm not stupid even if I have I will all the money in my business, so its not part of my system to be borrowing much, though then its because the business is too small let me put it that way. So if it gets to that stage then I will cross it.

Q18. What could banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A18 High interest rate: exactly! Not the collateral but the rates. Sometimes you don't get that rates as gain ,Like they give you £5000 and they will tell you to pay 30% every month or 20% every month, so to me doesn't worth it.

Theories and Concepts

Q19. Are you a migrant?

A19 Yeah

Q20. Where are you originally from?

A20 Yeah, I am from Nigeria

Q21. How do you feel when applying for business loan?

A21 Yes, It depends on type of visa too. Because I could remember three years ago, we want to buy our house then we are looking for mortgage, then the visa she got had one year left on it, she went there to talk to them because of her visa stuff, so I think its because of such kind of things. Because they will send you letters that you can get 40-50000 but when you get there and they will be asking you different paperwork and for me its just not worth it. Sincerely to me, some things piss me off and I think they should have sent letters knowing my full situation first and I hate starting something and not finish it. We ended up with our own cash, I don't go for mortgage not because of anything but because of anything. Sometimes they will tell

you, you need 30-40% and they need to request you to have British passport or to be in the country for more than 10 years and I think its such thing that piss me off on going on loan.

Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?

A22 Certain people, they give to them, maybe British pr Scottish, EU..no no no... like still under visa, they would not

Others

Q23. What type of business are you running?

A23 Its African shop,

Q24. Why did you start this particular business?

A24 Because I studied and my family is here

Q25. Who are your target customers?

A25 90% of my customers are usually Africans

Q26. Are there easy ways to get business loan?

A26 The easiest way to get business loan is through credit notes from your suppliers which is very simple and easy , no issue at all. No agreement, no direct debit at all. Very simple, no contract, no credit, nothing nothing, buy sell and return their money.

Q27. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?

A27 Well, uhm .. I don't have advice.

Q28. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A28 It's not encouraging and I hate disappointments that's why it's difficult for me, so if I have a problem we deal with it in the family instead of taking or calling somebody , sometimes people ask me for money and I smile, cause same time they ask, I too, I am in need of money and people look at us cause I don't tell them I have a business going on. Suppliers are sending letters and people are coming to borrow from you, you can't tell them you don't have, this point irritates me off about loans and just going to the bank for loans cause sometimes maybe you need £10000 and they will tell you they can't give you more than £3000 and face the reality. Another thing I can do is if I need like £10000 that I want to use. I can call like my suppliers take goods of like £20000 from them, you understand, before I finish that, by then I will pay them back.

Q29. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?

A29 Well, I don't have anything to say.

Interview.3

Interviewee: Tommy Cheung

Type of Business: Silver Inn (Chinese Takeaway)

Business Location: Glasgow, Scotland

Numbers of Employees: 14

Time of Interview: 4pm, 25th Jan 2020

Silver inn

Access to Business Loan

Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?

A1 No..not really cause I have not had like the need to go have it, you know...

Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?

A2 family

Q3. Do you face difficulty in assessing business loan?

A3 not really...

Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?

A4 I have not really had this problem, cause its like a family run business, mum and dad retired then I took over, so there's not really like loans involved and all that..

Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?

A5 I know but.. I don't go for lenders, I have not had the need to meet them

Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?

A6 Probably business banking.

Yes they give lots of offers...If I wanted to, I can go speak to the bank manager..but never done it before so..

Process of Business Loan

Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?

A7 no, I have not done that before.

Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?

A8 No...no..

Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?

A9 No...no..

Ethnic Minority

Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?

A10 No...not really...no..

Small Business in Scotland

Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?

A11 cause, just stay in Scotland, family business, just do what you know best...

Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?

A12 yeah yeah. I know bits and pieces...I know that small business owners apply for it but like I said I have not tried it.. I don't need it ... so that's all I know.

Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation?

A13 Just one or two staff, it mainly just family

Types of Small Business Loan

Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.

A14 yeah.. family.. savings wee bit..really...yeah

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?

A15 uh uh uh..... Yeah

Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?

A16 No...No

Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?

A17 no.....not interested.

Q18. What do banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A18 I don't think it's got to do anything with the bank, it depends if I need it or not..9 out of 10, but I don't need it, so it doesn't matter what they mail to me...so..

Theories and Concepts

Q19. Are you a migrant?

A19 No, I was born in Scotland

Q20. Where are you originally from?

A20 My parents are from Hong Kong.

Q21. How do you feel when applying for business loan?

A21 I don't think I would feel anything... if you need it.. you need it..

Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?

A22 No

Others

Q23. What type of business are you running?

A23 it's a fast food takeaway

Q24. Why did you start this particular business?

A24 family business

Q25. Who are your target customers?

A25 just locals.

Q26. Are there easy ways to get business loan?

A26 no.. it's not that easy cause you need that reputation.. you have to be in that bank for a wee while..taht kind of stuff

Q27. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?

*A27 *nods head* ...no*

Q28. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A28 probably reduce the interest rate if I was interested.

Q29. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?

*A29 they increase the terms to like 4 years or 5 years.. increases it a wee bit...yea.. increase it a wee bit
also, the collateral instead of you putting your shop or house or landed properties, instead if you putting landed properties, they should to reduce the collateral.*

Appendix 7: Sample of Main Interview Question

Interview Question

Personal Background Information

Type of Business: Business Location: Numbers of Employees: Time of Interview:
--

Access to Business Loan

Q1. Do you know the different forms of loan?

A1

Q2. What form of loan is easier for you to access?

A2

Q3. Do you face difficulty in accessing business loan?

A3

Q4. Can you tell me the challenges you have faced when applying for business loan?

A4

Q5. Do you know the types of lenders?

A5

Q6. What type of lenders can you easily access?

A6

Process of Business Loan

Q7. What are the processes of securing a business loan?

A7

Q8. Do you know what the terms and conditions in business loan are?

A8

Q9. Do you know the terms and conditions attached to business loans?

A9

Ethnic Minority

Q10. What challenges do you face as an ethnic minority business owner?

A10

Small Business in Scotland

Q11. Why did you choose Scotland for starting up your business?

A11

Q12. Are you aware that the Scottish Government gives business loan to small business owners?

A12

Q13. Does your business play an important role in job creation?

A13

Types of Small Business Loan

Q14. Do you get loan from banks, credit agent, family friends or from your savings?.

A14.

Q15. Do you depend on your profits to finance your business?

A15

Q16. Do you know the various types of small business loans?

A16

Q17. Are the lending policies and procedures in accessing business loan encouraging?

A17.

Q18. What could banks do to encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A18

Theories and Concepts

Q19. Are you a migrant?

A19

Q20. Where are you originally from?

A20

Q21. How do you feel when applying for business loan?

A21

Q22. Does your immigration status affect you when applying for business loan?

A22

Q23. Do you know the required information needed to access business loan?

A23

Q24. Do you apply directly to the lending agency or do ask someone to apply for you?

A2

Q25. Do you go through the contract document before signing the contract?

A22

Q26. Do you disclose all the necessary information to the lending agencies when applying for business loan?

A22

Q27. Does the lending agency disclose all the necessary information to when applying for business loan?

A27

Others

Q28. What type of business are you running?

A28

Q29. Why did you start this particular business?

A29

Q30. Who are your target customers?

A30

Q31. Are there easy ways to get business loan?

A31

Q32. What do you think could be done for you to access business loan?

A32

Q33. In what way could the Loan issuer encourage you to gain access to business loan?

A34

Q34. Is there anything else you would like to say about access to business loan?

A34

Appendix 8: Qualitative Data Analysis Template

THEME 1: Business Loan

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Credit Note	Sub-theme 2: Buy Now and Pay Later	Sub-theme 3: Hire Purchase	Sub-theme 4: Reason behind Business Loan
P001	<i>A31 not really sure, it all depends on your information, if your information is all true they will give you. But if you have any mistake like that they make it had for you.</i>	<i>how much is coming in and how much is going out like every month or a year and if you have good money they will give you.</i>	<i>A14.It depends, if I have money I take from my money but if I don't have money I take from my family so it all depends</i> <i>A21 First when you do a business here it is hard for you first time but after you know the rules it will be easy and not difficult and you will know how to connect with people then with</i>	<i>A16 Yes just two, the bounce back loan and the £10,000 loan to pay for rent</i> <i>A29 this is my job, I like this job, I work in a restaurant I don't like it, I work in car wash I don't like it, I work in too many place I don't like it, this is my job, I like it. I enjoy this job</i>
P002	<i>A23 Well, the bank managers will tells you they need xyz, they need company details, they need this they need that, bank statement, income, expenditure, inflow and outflow of cash</i>	<i>A14. At the moment, I don't have a loan, whatever the business making we use it back to the business.</i>	<i>A11 I was born here</i>	
P003			<i>A18 I need to do that I need to do something know some loans from the bank and know some grants but the interest is high so they can give grants,</i>	
P004	<i>A8 it depend the requirement yes I know, I have said it initially it depends on your financial books and on how you've run your accounts and all the business activities on your account and your proposal and your business proposal and the viability of the business you want to get yourself into</i> <i>A11 I have lived in Scotland for years, I use to live in England before because</i>	<i>A3 it depends on individual situation if you are like in a business it is easier for you to access loan depending on your financial book</i> <i>A34 I would have been able to access loan because they wanted to give me a personal loan because</i>	<i>A3 for you to access loan depending on your financial book, your yearly financial book</i> <i>A3 how much is your income and spending and your expenditure</i>	<i>A9 business loan I have said it initially it all depends on the business situation and in terms of business loan in the United Kingdom</i> <i>A10 challenges it depends on what you are providing me as a person that provide my service you need my services you will have to look for me to get my services</i> <i>A13 yes I do, I my previous business I</i>

	<p><i>I believe there is a Scottish government provide some grant for you to start up the business in Scotland it is just a grant which they don't provide in England and I study in Scotland I did my master degree in Scotland which has giving me the opportunity to be able to settle down in Scotland</i></p>			<p><i>use to employ freelance staff I have employ couple at a time 2 or 3 people and some of they've worked for me like several month because it is a freelance employment because of the nature of my business</i></p> <p><i>A17. Definitely they are encouraging yes, but it all depends on what you want to use the business loan for</i></p> <p><i>A21 Accessing business loan in Nigeria is difficult than here, I feel more relax here whenever I go to my bank to ask for a loan and I feel more positive</i></p> <p><i>A34 Yes accessing business loan is depending on the business you know I said it initially before I became psychotherapy before I diversify my business I use to run a private company, I got a removal services so I use to run that in the local area in Dundee where I use to live, removal service have got a van which I use,</i></p>
P005		<p><i>A31 it could be possible but it depends if you've have been long enough in a business and making enough turn over a year then it will be easy for you to get business loan. If your credit score is good then you will get a business loan</i></p> <p><i>A34. Borrowing from your friend you have to set the rules because there is no paper work and if your friend takes you to court without any document he can't prove anything. Because money change people very easy even your brother can</i></p>	<p><i>A23, for example if you have a business that you open last month and this month you try to apply for bounce back loan, you might not get the loan. The business should be in existent before the COVID-19.</i></p> <p><i>A25, Because they already have all your documents, your identification and your company information</i></p> <p><i>A25 for the bounce back loan you don't</i></p>	

		<i>cheat you, so my recommendation is you should borrow money from a friend if you can and second recommendation is to go to the bank.</i>	<i>need to send them the any prove of document</i> <i>A32 If you don't have a good credit score you can improve on that to have a good credit score you need to pay your bills on time, you shouldn't have any bills unpaid and that will improve your credit score. This is Experian credit score, if you register to this company for 14 days you will have a free credit score, what is your credit score, it start from zero to 999 so if you have a good credit score and you always pay your bills in time and you don't left any bills unpaid your credit score can move up to 999 and if you apply for a loan through a private agency they will approve your loan. For example if your credit score is below 540 or 600 they might say no. then to improve your credit score they will tell you what is the problem and what you need to do to improve your credit score. But with the bank this things doesn't work</i>	
P007				<i>A9 Yeah yeah. You need to repay it, if you don't they take your house, business, I have not had to take a business loan for a very long time cause so I'm pretty okay with that aii.</i>
P009		<i>A10. some customers like buy now and pay later which is not a good idea by the end of this month I will have to stop the buy now and pay later because people are abusing it</i>		
P010	<i>A13 Yes, I hire delivery drivers, I hire people who take our orders via telephone and yeah.it depends on our sales, if we are quiet, we can't afford</i>		<i>if you apply for it they will run some check like credit check and background check</i>	

	<i>more people as we do have to work as a team. But if not, we have 6 people work in the kitchen but as average, maximum of 7 and minimum of 2-3</i>			
P011	<i>A6 The Bank, so it all depends on your credit score, if its higher you can easily access business loan if its lower it will be difficult for you to access business loan</i>	<i>A6. To build the credit score once you are 18 years old you will be able to pay your bills on time</i>		
P012	<i>A26. and I don't need to disclose the credit information about myself just ask for the money and that is all</i>			
P013	<i>A15 My profit, £3,000 or £4,000, yes of course, I put in the profit in the business to buy goods. For example first time I buy only normal fanta, I sell it the next time I buy another fanta step by step. Cash and Carry guys are good because they give you goods and you pay later.</i>	<i>A10 My customer respect me I respect them too, sometimes I meet good customers and sometimes bad customers</i>	<i>15. Cash and Carry guys are good because they give you goods and you pay later.</i>	
P014	<i>A34. They need to give more loans</i>	<i>A5 I have never go to anybody else expect the banks. Because every other lenders have a high interest rate. So you just go to the bank because bank will just charge you normal. If you go to the bank they will charge you less but if you go outside they will charge you higher</i>		
P015	<i>A2 Credit note for a month but I normally pay within 3 or 4 days</i>			<i>A32 I think if you are scared innit, see if you are not making any money you may want to but see if you're not making any money, you shut the business down. See if you are running a business and you need money, what you need to do is to change the business to an LTD take in some business loans and shut the company down because its an LTD and now open a new company</i>

				<i>with a different name, that's what Donald Trump did, Cashly Ashley did, that's what they did, they buy a small company they take 20 to 50 thousand what of business loans and they liquidate the company, company goes they keep the money they pay a pound to an honor or something like that.</i>
P016			<p><i>A4 if you went to the bank and ask them of business loan they will look at your bank statement and your transaction history because you are a new business then you want to buy this, you want to improve your business for example now I want to get a loan to do my approval, documentation SIA approval all this I could not get a loan for the past 2 years, it is only Government loan now that will help me. That help me now just because government make it relax now it help my business and my business is pushing forward</i></p> <p><i>A18 The bank should make it simple, banks should not be using any credit history but they should make it simple and there should be fair credit checking. The credit check should not be thorough, they should not see a young business like a business that has no future, assuming the banks can help us my business is almost 7 years and I am still looking for money if the bank has help us I would have employed up to 15 or 16 people bust because there is no much job so I am just using my own personal money you know, business required money</i></p>	
P019			<i>A5 I know about the bank and I know</i>	<i>A2. I want to expand my business and</i>

			<p><i>about Capital one and one other one funding circle but</i></p> <p><i>A7 Not really, I have an accountant but they never help with this anything even the furlough I had to call them up and I then chase it up, even the bounce back scheme my accountant never sent it to me to say this is happening so it is always just been us figuring things our self and he is getting pay a lot, he get up to £2,000 per year for doing nothing and that is a lot because I found out later and now I am working to hand over to another accountant he is not really doing that, he will tell me I will do this I will do that and now he knows that I realize that I am not getting the best service but at a time I thought I was, so I don't know much on loan I could access</i></p>	<p><i>I was going to be a long process but I did not see the business manager, I had to call I had to go to the branch so I got put off half way so I never.</i></p>
P020		<p><i>A18 now there is no business manager only branch manager, they just seat there and you can't see the face to face, Edinburg is the head office if you want anything you will have to make a call and wait for 1 or 2 hours you know, it is not encouraging its discouraging you</i></p>		

THEME 2: Business Challenges

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Accountant Fee or Agency Fee	Sub-theme 2: Relationship with Bankers	Sub-theme 3: Lack of Information
P001	<i>A3. to help you to speak to the bank</i>	<p><i>A2 I think is like from the bank or personal is more easier</i></p> <p><i>A6 I think Bank of Scotland is batter, I bank with them</i></p> <p><i>A7 I don't know about this I think you can get a loan for the business, I think £50,000 the maximum is £50,000 but you know your income should be very high, if you don't have income</i></p>	<p><i>A1 No, Yes I get you, I know there are too many different kind of loan</i></p> <p><i>A21. You just need time to know the rule before you can do business.</i></p> <p><i>A27 To be honest I don't know about the information but I think they tell my Accountant. My Accountant act on my behave so he speak with them and he knows what to do</i></p>
P004		<i>A4. I have been in relationship with my personal banker which I operate premier banking with my bank and I have been with my bank for several years for close to 17 years now I have been with my bank so in my own situation I don't have challenges in accessing business loans because of the good relationship I have with my bank and the kind of account I am operating with my bank</i>	<i>A17. I don't know</i>
P005		<p><i>A7 If you are in a business then the process is more easier than taking a personal loan because if you have business banking they will check your account but I don't know how long it will take but it's easier to trace</i></p> <p><i>A10 As for my nationality, I don't think it has to do anything to do with nationality, if you have a business and you go to a bank for loan it doesn't have anything to do with the nationality with loan. Even if you are foreigner, European, international it doesn't matter, if you are doing business that is what the bank check, they don't check nationality</i></p> <p><i>A18 You don't have to encourage people, Depending on the bank you know the banks need many people to take loan, The more business they make they might lose. I think bank don't have to encourage people to take business loan. You need to struggle but if need be, you must take a loan from the bank</i></p>	

		<i>A23 You must have a business account before you obtain a loan from the bank otherwise they will not give you the loan. For the bounce back loan it's a very small procedure they don't look for much information as long as you have a business account with them automatically they will check that, I think they will check how long you've been in business with them and the bounce back loan will be approved if you have long enough,</i>	
P006	<i>A3 I don't really have much information on that, I think my Accountant has much information about that.</i>	<i>A1 Hmmm credit card, going to the bank to get a loan A5 Hmm banks, hmmm I think dose who lend money, like private loans, working shops you can lend money from.</i>	
P008			<i>A16 I don't really know the various kind of small business loan but my Accountant has a wider knowledge about this</i>
P010	<i>A25 Yes I do have to read it, I go over and over again before signing and sometimes I do ask for professional advices before signing the document</i>		
P012	<i>A29 Because like the gain or profit from grocery exceed sometimes like 50%, and there is like policies of returning stuffs back</i>	<i>A26 It depends on how responsible the lender is so if the bank which is not a personal lender its an institutional organization so I can give them any information they will need. So if I am going to ask a friend it is a personal issues and I don't need to disclose the credit information about myself just ask for the money and that is all</i>	<i>A25 It depends if the contract papers are so many, I will try to find a way to sign straightway but if its two papers, I will have to go through them.</i>
P013	<i>A5 I don't know but some lawyers will come here and ask me to give them £5,000 so they could apply form for a loan for me, I tell them no</i>		<i>A3 Yes, I applied for a loan like three month ago and up till now no response, no single email or phone call. COVID 19 is Grant. But I applied for a loan for my shop</i>
P014		<i>A2 See loan is easier if I have to go to the bank, I have to go to them and asking them about loan, that my business is not running good, I need some small loan depending on the manager, the manager is going to say yes or no.</i>	
P015		<i>A10 No, nothing like that. They've known my dad for many years, so based on that trust and relationship</i>	
P016		<i>A32 requirements should be a little bit less for a business loan</i>	
P017			<i>A33 During this period it is very simple to get a loan. I just go online and check what the</i>

			<i>government says we should do then I apply directly to my bank</i>
P019	<p><i>A5 only one I was able to get because it was accessible to everyone. I also got the furlough pay. And another thing is this, I have an accountant who is Scottish and I am genuinely and I am about to switch my accountant as well, I feel like when you are also ethnic minority rather than them having or help you grow they look for ways to make sure all your earnings go to the government because already you are paying your staff, you are paying so much to run a business but I found my accountant always not on my side rather than to look for more money for the government if that make sense and I personally believe also because I am from an ethnic minority, There is been need for expansion for a long time but of course and you need to make money save money, I couldn't even access the start up fund when I started my business, I couldn't get the £50,000 start up fund and I have just graduated from the University which I thought that would have been an easy way</i></p> <p><i>A6 I think it will only be the bank, I can only trust my bank because of the APR like I said because I have also, I don't even hold a credit card because it is wrong but like I said the APR always put me off. Finance has just been something not always on the best way, I run a business's but I am a cook and I have been able to learn so if only I could have a financial adviser it could have been a very very good thing for me</i></p>	<p><i>A4 so I just didn't see it through and I feel personally that when it come to ethnic minority they require a lot more guarantee before you can get a loan, they should make it easier because the first impression if you work into a bank like really do you deserve it, you need to prove to us that you worth it, do you understand that was the first impression I got, the only good thing for me that made me see through to some extent was that I have know the bank manager for like few years and he was nice and unfortunately he was not in charge of business loan, so the business sector is different and this is just a general branch manager, I had to speak to someone and they will send you to..In fact they will not even advice you on the things you could access that is another thing I notice because I knew that I have one business manager assign to me (Amanda Hull) but she wasn't really available and she was explaining to me that now that your business has reach 2 years you can actually think of doing this, it was the general manager who told me but the process put me off so I left and I have been in business for more than 4 years</i></p>	
P020		<p><i>A14. At the moment I have my family friends they support me and Cash and Carry give me loan because I have good credit and good relationship with them, Cash and Carry give me £10,000, £20,0000, £30,000 and £40,0000 loan</i></p>	

THEME 3: Source of Fund

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Family and Friends	Sub-theme 2: Credit Agency	Sub-theme 3: Grant	Sub-theme 4: Bank
P001	<i>A33 like how much you get if you can pay it back they will give you, just to make sure that all information about your business or company, how much is coming in and how much is going out like every month or a year and if you have good money they will give you. If you don't have enough money maybe you can't pay it back</i>	<i>A33 just to check about your income</i>	<i>A7. Depending on your income. A8 I think the first year they don't take any money, when you take the loan the one year is like free, after the one year you have to payback, that is the bounce back loan from the government,</i>	<i>A18 I think Clydesdale Bank and Bank of Scotland this two do give loan</i>
P002	<i>A10 We provide a service that makes them come here and a lot comes down to personality and how you deal with people. A18 the payment time should be as long as you need it</i>	<i>A5 Well you have the private lenders and the banks A6 easier for us and easier for them and beside private equity firms they want something like a share in your company a share in your investments and sometimes it might look good, they are high risk enough</i>	<i>A9 So it takes may be 6 months for your cash to go okay, so once its 6 months you don't pay us nothing but probably you still have 6 month of interest to pay A12 yes, that's like a grant but it is for certain sectors so whether it is given for ethnic minority or not, I don't know, the accountant dealing with my application on business interruption loan.</i>	<i>A4 But if they don't have money they won't give you, so it all depends on the time and what has happened. A6 but for the bank you are a lot safer A7 the process we only go through is maybe a business manager, we have a dedicated business manager, someone in the bank so he is like an account officer who does that</i>
P003	<i>A14 from my daughters and sometimes from my daughters and government</i>		<i>A3 For equipments, for some other stuffs, most importantly for the clients</i>	
P004				<i>A4 challenges in loan I have told you it depends on customer situation, there are some customers that they have bad credit rating and they are some that got good credit rating, A6 some are under the building society like Santander can lend you money, Barclays, Lloyds A27 before 2009 financial regulation</i>

				<i>and they said they should pay all mis sold insurance back to all the customer that</i>
P005	<p><i>A2 if it is a small amount maybe its better to borrow from my friend because you don't have to pay any interest</i></p> <p><i>A4 It depends on the friends you've got, if you got rich friends it is always easy, A friend is always good. I will recommend you to try a friend. It depends the loan and the amount of money</i></p> <p><i>A28 Family business (Café Restaurant)</i></p>	<p><i>A15 Yes, everything I generate I will use it to buy things or stock the shop</i></p> <p><i>A27 the lending agency will approve you loan through your credit score system. Before they approve you the loan they will send you name and request all credit agency to check your credit score and if you have a good credit score they will approved the loan</i></p>	<p><i>A17. No its not encouraging to give loan, Nobody will encourage you to give you loan, even if you apply for bounce back loan you still have to meet some regulations as well before they approve you the bounce back loan, even if the government said nobody can get refuse, they might refuse you.</i></p> <p><i>A33 The loan issuer will not encourage you either the banks won't encourage you. The only encouragement that could be done is only if you buy a car for example and pay monthly for it the company will encourage you to do that and they will be so fast to give you, even if you want to take a phone they will give it to you quickly</i></p>	<p><i>A2 If it's a big amount of money its always better to borrow from bank</i></p> <p><i>A12 Yes, The Bounce Back Loan, there are different ones but the better and best loan is bounce back loan because they give you one year free interest and after one year the additional fee is only 2.5% interest rate on top of what every you borrow from them which is one of the best loan</i></p>
P006	<p><i>A14. Hmm so I have my family supporting me and just the little form my savings so we are still hoping that with time it will grow</i></p>			<p><i>A33 it is like what I said before now, they should allow even if the person haven stay in the UK for up to 5 years as long as they have legal documentation they should be able to access it also they should not put as much interest on the loan because it will be discouraging, at lease if they can out a certain number people will be encourage to take a loan although I understand that the banks too will want to make their gain or profit but if they could reduced the money that will be better</i></p>
P009	<p><i>A11 Because my families are here and you cannot compare Scotland and India</i></p>			

P011		<i>A6 you don't have any debt outstanding and you need to have money coming in and going out from your account.</i>	<i>A12 If you apply it will depend on the size of the business they can grant you £10,000 to £15,000</i>	
P012		<i>A26 It depends on how responsible the lender</i>		
P013			<i>A31. There no easy way. Its always difficult, but applied for the grant it was easy and straight forward, because it was funded by the city council, they require just your name and your shop address and the reference of your business rate, that's all</i>	<i>A18. The easy bank is Bank of Scotland, Royal Bank of Scotland, Halifax all Lloyds group is very good including Nat West bank. They could reply my email and get back to me on time</i> <i>A23 for business loan you just need a company house and bank business account, the statement of business account</i>
P014			<i>A8 You need to have money to run the business. You go to bank to get a loan you use the money to run your business after sometime the money runs, £20,000 or £30,000 is nothing, you can spend it in one day.</i>	<i>A3 Yes, sometimes they don't trust, see the small business they don't give them the loan they required anymore</i> <i>A8 It depend on the bank rate, sometimes what is happening right now business can fold up. See if you have staff you need to give them wages.</i>
P016		<i>A4 if you go for private agency its too much interest they charge, private companies charge too much interest than the bank. But when you go for a loan, you need to go to the bank because the credit card people is too much. Some company charge more than 30% interest which is too much, it those not matter the time you return the money it will be the same interest, if I pay off within three month I have to pay the full interest. They don't care.</i>	<i>A25. Yeah. I got a Barclays personal loan with Barclays bank</i>	

		<p><i>A7 securing business loans with guarantee, business loan should be without guarantee but they ask many of things</i></p> <p><i>A8 yeah after 5 years they give a loan. Something like steady income for 5 years and you have to have a business.</i></p>		
P018			<p><i>A2 Just now, just now believe it or not...I am having an issue with the COVID19 grant</i></p>	
P019				<p><i>A34 I just think more information will be good less APR and less requirements especially if it is very personal I think they should try to use business credibility rather than personal</i></p>
P020				<p><i>A4. Area manager are just useless to be honest, business manager at the local branch you know that's what help a lot you know if there is any problem they can solve it right at the spot</i></p> <p><i>A5 Lenders are too many in the market you know and they will charge you a lot of money, there is no point you know, if you are doing the legal business there is no point putting the lenders, just go straight away to the bank, any bank to ask for money, if they ask for legal document which if you are paying the tax they will issue out the loan.</i></p> <p><i>A7 You need to have insurance, business insurance, that is to sure your business</i></p>

THEME 4: Terms and Condition

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Contract Document	Sub-theme 2: Payment Period	Sub-theme 3: Charges/Fees	Sub-theme 4: Sensitization
P001	<p><i>A9 I don't know, I only know the bounce back loan</i></p> <p><i>A17. I am not really sure, I think is like the application you do it online and you get like loan just like the £10,000, you do the application and you will get it, if you got Accountant he will do it for you.</i></p>	<p><i>A3 see if you are going to payback or not.</i></p> <p><i>A4 I think there is no problem but they will tell you we will try to give you £5,000 and if you pay back we will give you more. So the problem is the limit of the money, how much amount you can get</i></p>		
P002		<i>A33 Make things simple</i>		<i>A33 do a lot of seminars, advertise a lot, be a little bit more friendlier when discussing it with people</i>
P003			<i>A33 reduce loan</i>	<i>A4 I don't know too much but someone told me about loan from government, first year you don't need to pay interest but that's very good. I'm not sure, but something like that</i>
P004	<i>A32 all the necessary document of your company</i>	<p><i>A8 it depend the requirement yes I know, I have said it initially it depends on your financial books</i></p> <p><i>A27 they told me that there is no mis sold because in some situation there is some mis sold insurance which is called payment protection</i></p> <p><i>A27 they lend loan and mortgages and credit cards however I approach my bank and I told my bank I hope there is no payment insurance on the loan I am accessing and they told me there is nothing like that because I don't want to be mis sold</i></p>	<p><i>A2 they are business and individual loan</i></p> <p><i>A25. Yes I went through the contract document yes I check the APR and the interest rate over the year</i></p> <p><i>A27 Yes because due to 2009 financial regulation that they shouldn't mis sold to customers so I was aware of that so I had to ask my bank that there is no mis sold ppi insurance</i></p> <p><i>34 they use to see my income and transactions over the years and I have build a lot of trust with my bank which</i></p>	<i>A32 just to do all your proper research</i>

			<i>has give me more opportunity to access whatever I want from them.</i>	
P005	<i>A25 For bounce back loan you don't need to go through the document before you sign it. You make the application but if you open the business recently they might refuse it, they will ask your for proof of income and expenditure, the bounce back loan is use for only the period of COVID</i>	<i>A6 you can fix better terms with your friends A34 No, more or less nothing but the best recommendation is if you want to open a business today the best is for you to borrow money from your friends, if you have good friends you can set a target and pay them bit by bit, for example you can borrow £50,000 and you tell them you will pay £2,000 each month depend on the kind of business you have for me for example when I open my café I borrowed £45,000 from my friend,</i>	<i>A2 from the bank, depending on the amount,</i>	
P006	<i>A4 my accountant did all the paperwork A18 they should look at the document if the documents are legal and if the document is complete then they should be able to give loan regardless of whether you have stayed in the UK for up till 5 years or not as long as the papers and the document you provided are all legally bound the person should be able to access loan. I not saying that they should ignore, the time frame, instead of putting a specific number of years before you can access loan if your documentation is legal what every you are bringing to them is legal then they should be able to give you the loan whether you have stayed in UK for up to 5 years or not</i>	<i>A9 possibly paying back when due and not defaulting. A10 I tried to get a credit card before I was rejected because I haven't stay in the UK for up till 3 years</i>	<i>A17. If you borrow from somebody and if they ask for interest you will pay, the thing is instead of, you have to pay so that you don't pay the late fee charges because they do charge, for my credit card they charge me like 12% if I don't pay the minimum payment in a month, so if I pay the minimum payment they won't charge me the £12 for late fees so the earlier I pay the better for me. As long as you keep using the card to make purchases they are certain charges that are accrued to the card as well so if you are buying something £50 now they will put a charge now interest on that £50 maybe like let say £2 on it so if you are going to pay minimum payment that is £38 pounds you have to increase it, if you keep on making that payment the interest will increase on the card, you will have to make at lease more than that minimum payment whether you pay</i>	

			<p><i>minimum payment this month</i></p> <p><i>A27 no they will tell you, even the credit card that I have, all the document that they send to me via email it will show that if you did not make any payment there is a charge, if you make or buy anything there is a charge, if you use the card at certain pay point to withdraw money there is a charge so everything is on the documentation that they send to me via email so I don't think they hide anything</i></p>	
P007				<i>A9 Yeah yeah. You need to repay it, if you don't they take your house, business</i>
P008		<i>A9 I know few things like the charges and the repayment period</i>		
P009	<p><i>A22 Not really, but sometimes they ask unnecessary questions</i></p> <p><i>A27 I think they use to hide some information until after you have sign the contact they will now tell you some things</i></p>	<p><i>A9 Yes, because some banks or lenders will tell you what you need to payback and the time frame and the charges if you refuse to pay in time</i></p> <p><i>A17 the time frame to payback need to be increased</i></p>		<i>A7 I could remember first of all you need to meet all the requirement, you need to have a registered company, you need to have good inflow of cash,</i>
P011			<i>A27 No they hide a lot, the interest rate will change, like after a year the interest rate will go up. They will tell you we will keep it the same but it will go up next time, that is what they will do to make more money</i>	<i>A31 The government website is one of the easy way</i>
P012		<i>A32 The same like a good credit history and the capability of myself to pay back</i>	<i>A9 You have to pay some kind of fixed interest, like the interest rate will rise upon the due payment and I don't think the bank and the lender will think of anything else aside the money. Just to increase the interest and if you agree with it that's it and nothing else</i>	<i>A18 Like to reduce the interest rate, I think so and give more timeframe and also I think those are the two most important point.</i>

P013				<p><i>A9 I know about HSBC bank, I went there they ask me to give them my passport, visa, one address for the last five years and your credit and everything. I gave them everything they asked and I don't know why they did not give me the loan. See sometime two people will be fighting here in the road, I will phone the police and they will not come on time because I am not Scottish but if it's Scottish person they will be here in two minutes. Sometimes some Scottish people will come here to take drinks and cigarette if I ask them for money they will say fuck off. My friend parked his bike cost £1,300, they stole the bike even with CCTV. We call the police and police said we don't have a time. My neighbor sale off license, He sales alcohol till 12 midnight normally you need to stop selling by 9pm because he is Scottish. This is real I know it is not easy.</i></p>
P014	<p><i>A27. Yes, they disclose all the necessary information to me. They don't hide any information</i></p>			
P015	<p><i>A3 Cash and carry is fine because they know me I go in everyday because if I go ask from the bank they won't give me just because of the question they will ask and the paper work is too much just because you need money they will ask you to sign a lot of paper</i></p> <p><i>A18 Banks charge higher interest rate and cash and carry do consider small businesses and they consider your</i></p>		<p><i>A4 I just walk in and I will pay it tomorrow and is based on what you are bringing in as well and they give you a month to pay without interest and after a month you are told to pay interest. But I have been able to get away with it for 2 to 3 months.</i></p> <p><i>A12 They don't really give you, You need to meet up all the ticks or more than all the ticks, there's something</i></p>	

	<p><i>business but to be honest at the start they want to know and the ask security questions. See like credit cards their interest rate is like 50, 60%, for cash and carry it is like 0.03%</i></p> <p><i>A25 I'll look at it, depends on what you are applying, if I know all the stuff, I'll just sign but if I don't I'll read through.</i></p> <p><i>A27 They don't disclose all the information, they put in the little imprints (this is 500% interest rate), see if you have a business, just do it yourself. And if you have savings just do it</i></p>		<p><i>attached, the tax involved and the criteria and I have never applied for it. cause I don't need to.</i></p>	
P017	<p><i>A25. I don't go through it oh, I just sign because the contract is too much, they should make a contract simple</i></p>		<p><i>A27. They don't really tell you, they will just say this this and that is all, they don't hide the interest rate but some time you discover that they hide something like that you know if you are paying off your loan if you want to pay it off early you will discover that you need to pay £50 extra and they will not tell you until when you want to pay off the loan they will now tell you it is remaining £50.</i></p>	
P018			<p><i>A24 No, we generally deal with the bank directly. Accountants have their charges as well</i></p>	<p><i>A2 I have recently applied for the bounce back loans, that seem it is not went through but the process seems pretty straight forward I am still waiting on the outcome of what they will sa, but the grant I have applied three or four times and they've not been back and they gave me two reasons and the two reason do not apply to me so I am trying to find out why and they issues is that you only have now till Friday.</i></p>

				<p><i>A8 Basically, with the bank because I have got a personal account with the bank so my loan is set to my house if I was to default it could affect it indirectly to your residential property basically it is not mandatory for the loan but it is easier to get the loan if you can link it, if you default they will get a hold of your house, so it is like a collateral, so like I said it is not mandatory but it is easier for the loan process, so if I am seating in my house and they ask if I want to secure a loan with my house and if I turn round to say no they say why his he not doing that they might think he has intention for not paying the loan back, they might still give it to me but it might be a little harder and higher interest. Normally I tell them no problem because I have every intention to pay, if you apply for £100,000 they might give you £70,000 or £50,000 because they will do a risk assessment on how much you are making and how much you can afford so there is no point on giving you £100,000 and there is no way for you to pay it back so they need to cover their own back</i></p>
P019				<p><i>A6 if I default on the payment then I am in debt rather I will pay upfront for what I may need so I don't know much lenders apart from the other two I told you earlier funding circle because they keep writing me and the other one, there was the other one I mention capital one and then my bank</i></p>

THEME 5: Scotland

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Environment	Sub-theme 2: Government	Sub-theme 3: Support	Sub-theme 4: Role of Job Centre
P001	<i>A11 I move from Cardiff to here. I like Scotland than Cardiff, people are more friendly here in Scotland and I have my family also here</i>	<i>A12 Yes you mean like loan, yes they give loan to all business, all small business, the government gives two loans, one they give you like £50,000 and they give you £10,000 for the small £10,000, I think you don't need to pay back, its like to help you to pay the rent and other things</i>	<i>I business as well, but this</i>	
P002		<i>A4 the ways they lend money especially the Royal Bank of Scotland the government took over and they have been very very conservative on how they actually give out the loan now. So it all depends on what the banks want to do, if the banks got a lot of money they will give you money to do anything.</i> <i>A9 yeah, they are just incentives, you know what I mean basically is just to attract the customers, if you start a business for the first times, the first few months cash is always hard to come by, cash flow problem</i> <i>A18 Free money and they will get plenty of business, Zero percent interest, free money</i>	<i>A3 Based on that you may want a £100,000 and they may turn around and say £50,000.</i> <i>A4 currently, I don't have any challenges but in the past I had challenges due to the credit crunch period</i> <i>A12 Scottish enterprises yes</i>	<i>A10 in business, everything is a challenge, it doesn't matter what ethnicity you are from. If you are asking me about today I will give you a different answer if you are asking about the 80's I will give you a different answer. So a lot has changed over the years.</i>
P003			<i>A18 if they can reduce the interest it will be better</i>	
P004	<i>A8 on how you've run your accounts and all the business activities on your</i>	<i>A34 I was trading has a sole proprietor so since I have register a company as a</i>	<i>A12 the Scottish government they give grant to small and medium enterprises</i>	<i>A6 it all depends on loan adviser or financial adviser which you can</i>

	<p><i>account</i></p> <p><i>A33 just to do more publicity and to reduce as I said the interest rate to be low for a new business to be able to grow</i></p>	<p><i>limited company my bank knows</i></p>	<p><i>grant for you to start of a business so if you are starting up a business because of the population the government give out incentive they want a lot of business to settle down in Scotland and I am aware of it</i></p> <p><i>A18 actually to reduce the interest rate and to do more publicity to let customers know that oh this thing is accessible and they can increase the loan term</i></p> <p><i>A34 I did not register a limited company if I had registered a limited company I would have been able to access loan</i></p>	<p><i>access all the smaller one because those smaller one they don't operate in the public that makes it difficult for people to get loan from the smaller ones</i></p>
P005	<p><i>A6 Borrowing from a friend is easy and you will get free interest</i></p>			<p><i>A25 It's a special kind of loan its not any other kind of loan.</i></p>
P006	<p><i>A15 Yes, I depend on my profit to finance my business, if we don't make profit should we still be open, profit, making profit is why we open the business.</i></p>	<p><i>A17 It is encouraging if you borrow money you will have to pay it with interest</i></p>		
P007	<p><i>A11 Cause I live here... *laughs</i></p> <p><i>A22 No they did not have too.. just ID, obviously I am born here</i></p>			
P008	<p><i>A3 Yes I do, sometimes I feel maybe because I am not originally from here. Some people use to look down on my shop and they don't know we generate a lot of money in this hope that could pay the wages of 2 or 3 bankers</i></p>	<p><i>A32. I think the loan issuer should not be so pick, I mean selective on giving loan as far as you have a legit business and your paying your tax and you have enough income, also they should not look down on small store like my shop</i></p>	<p><i>A12 I did not know on till this corona virus period. My accountant was able to apply for my shop to be able to get the bounce back loan and the furlough pay</i></p>	
P009		<p><i>A4 so I went to another branch lucky I meet a banker who is from Indian and he</i></p>	<p><i>A32 I thnk government need to let people know about the grant and also</i></p>	

		<p><i>gave me the requirement for business loan so took my time to go through the requirement I now found out that I meet all the requirement so I went back to the other branch and I met the Indian man and he gave me the application which I filed and I attached all the necessary document and I got the loan.</i></p> <p><i>A17. I don't think so, I think they should work on the policy and procedure because the interest rate should be reduce</i></p>	<p><i>the same procedure on how to get the bounce back loan should be adopted for all the other loans</i></p>	
P010		<p><i>A9 yeah.. you pay after an X number of years at an X percentage of the loan. The interest is on your total sum of loan, so the more you pay the less interest you pay</i></p> <p><i>A21 it does not make a different when applying for business loans, If you are set up as a business they do look at your business numbers, I don't think they would care where you are originally from if your numbers are good man. But I feel like they look at income, what is your turnover, how much are you paying things and if that matches the person that had family here for thousands of years here then there is no different in a business settings because they are doing business. i only applied for loan during this coronavirus period and it was successful</i></p> <p><i>A33 I don't know, I don't really believe in business loan unless you really need it, like I said I do not take one if not for</i></p>	<p><i>A3 NO, not at the moment, prior to this COVID-19 situation, it may be hard for businesses to get loans but now I feel like this is easy now cause of the situation of COVID-19 we had to close for three weeks, we had to fit the screen and purchase personal protective equipment but loans are easier and accessible now.</i></p>	

		<i>this COVID-19 period we have to spend more money on obviously like staffs, fitting in more screen, buying more personal protective equipment, buying more delivery bags. Buying more hand sanitize and writing the signs for 2 meter gap.</i>		
P011	<i>A13 At this moment and time yes, a lot of people don't have job, I have got 6 new staff</i>		<i>A12 Yes I am aware, they have the bounce back loan, they have the catering loan, I can't remember all from the top of my head. The catering loan is only for small business with up to 18 seat or not more than 18 seat</i> <i>A16 Not really, just the bounce back loan, if your company was created before the 17th of March 2020 they will give you the bounce back loan, if you apply for it. The bounce back loan was available until after the 27th of July 2020. And you can also claim wages from the government, the bounce back loan and the wages are not the same. I have got my Accountant, he helps me to apply for everything, that's why I don't have too much ideal about everything</i>	
P012	<i>A11 Because it is safer environment and people are so friendly than any part of European country</i> <i>A21, In the beginning, there was like a cultural shock in terms of language and different cultures</i>	<i>A27 Well its vice versa, at least they have to enclose or attach terms and conditions in separate papers and there is like comment I did not mention like you know the Islamic loans don't put interest. So they have to consider this.</i> <i>A34 Yeah for sure, Like I mention before they have to consider kind of Islamic terms of loans because many or so many Muslims are into the business and they</i>	<i>A29 It is kind of a risk support between me and the cash and carry like main warehouses</i>	

		<i>don't even ask for loans because it doesn't fit into the Islamic concept also like, if you want to buy house they will ask you to locate this as a mortgage this doesn't fit Islamic religious a thing like this maybe for them to consider but not an obligatory issues.</i>		
P014	<i>A13 it's a small business we don't have so many people working here, we only have 3-4 people working here. We can't afford to employ more than 4 or 5 workers. Within 200 meters we have 6 shops with the same business.</i>		<i>A8 . I think the Government need to increase the loan from £20,000 to £50,000 or £100,000 for small business. You can imagine water bill is £720 for one year, electricity and gas bill is like £2,000, you see the £20,000 is nothing compare to the expenses.</i> <i>A32. I don't think the government is going to do anything, see if the business fold they will not do anything, even the banks don't care, they don't even support you.</i>	
P016	<i>A11 Glasgow is flexible and have more chances to grow the business.</i>	<i>A18 dependent on their policies, no strict regulations or policies on how much money coming how much money you are saving</i>	<i>A25 with Barclays bank they say three month you don't have to pay but you have to pay interest, you can't stop paying interest.</i>	
P017			<i>A34 Well in other to make this economy grow the bank should make the business loan easy, The bank should not target the big company they should come down for the small company like us but the bank don't want to see us so they pay that money to big company</i>	<i>A30 Well most of my client is private sector, I don't really get a job from Scotland they don't give it to immigrant they give it to their own people, I get contract from England direct</i>
P018		<i>A3 So the bounce back loan that was no problem like I said I don't know what the outcome is going to be but the other one I have had issues with it. I think it would be more clearer and better. So if they refuse the application, a reason should</i>		

		<p><i>be given on how to rectify the issue and because of the current issues now we can't talk to them because there is no body there, so there is an email and I have emailed them to let them know can you tell me what is wrong but that was three days ago and I am still waiting on their reply, I will probably get a reply on Monday, like I said Friday is the cut-off date, so I have been applying maybe for the last 6 weeks, if they had told me at the start what the problem was maybe I would have sorted it out so now I am waiting for them to tell me what the problem was but I think by the time they will tell me I think it will be too late.</i></p>		
P020			<p><i>A32 see for me this time is the government should give offer to the bounce back loan at a very low rate because in five or six years you just need to pay £3,000 extra, that's very good opportunity if anybody want to start business or any other thing, because it is a very low rate, low rate is the main thing you know, the government should continue with the bounce back loan because already 20% of the economy is fucked, if they did not have issue like this stuff, it will be more fucked and in coming days and coming years it is going to affect a lot</i></p>	<p><i>A12 I cannot remember the name of the loan because its more than 4 years now. I know I went to job center and job center directed me to the Scottish government office that they can issue me the loan you know, I have been there and they said we can issue you loan £80 a week. I told them £80 is just one game for my son you know, they said you can give it to your son. I left there I never go back there again</i></p>

THEME 6: Challenges Affecting Ethnic Minority

Participants	Sub-theme 1: Language	Sub-theme 2: Staffing	Sub-theme 3: Trustworthy	Sub-theme 4: Other Barriers
P001	<i>A10 Yes with the Language, the language is difficult, if you don't know the language, if you don't understand one word it's like you can't speak, you know if you don't understand the sentence, if you can't understand one word then you can't understand the sentence. My main problem is the language because you can't connect with the people. It is very hard, I can speak Arabic but if I want to speak English it is very hard for me.</i>		<i>A3 I think they will give you like £5,000 and if your pay back they can give you £10,000</i>	<i>A22 No I don't think so</i> <i>A23 Yes, they will check your back account and your income, if there is money coming out and going out</i> <i>A27 To be honest I don't know about the information but I think they tell my Accountant. My Accountant act on my behave so he speak with them and he knows what to do</i> <i>A30 Yes they are more local</i>
P002		<i>A29 I have been in the food business for a long time</i>		
P003				<i>A3 of course, always problem, always people want some funding, some finances to do something after the virus.</i> <i>A7 like my business, you undertsnad, I have been unemployed for long time and government has been encouraged us to do something. That is the reason why I start this business</i> <i>A10 Mainly Client don't know about my medicine, my English is not good and they (British) do not know about Chinese medicine</i>
P004				<i>A15 No because of the kind of business I provide is servicing so I don't need capital, the only capital I need then when I started was an office so that people will know where</i>

				<i>to locate me</i>
P005			<i>A10 As for my nationality, I don't think it has to do anything to do with nationality, if you have a business and you go to a bank for loan it doesn't have anything to do with the nationality with loan. Even if you are foreigner, European, international it doesn't matter, if you are doing business that is what the bank check, they don't check nationality</i>	<i>A18 You don't have to encourage people, Depending on the bank you know the banks need many people to take loan, The more business they make they might lose. I think bank don't have to encourage people to take business loan. You need to struggle but if need be, you must take a loan from the bank</i> <i>A25 the bounce back loan is use for only the period of COVID 19 to help the business struggling this time. The business must be in operation before March 2020.</i>
P006			<i>A4 It was really much straight forward, My Accountant only ask me some personal question and I answer and that was it,</i>	<i>A10 I haven't stay in the UK for up till 3 years and with the business when I try to begin the business it was also an issue because I haven't stay in the UK for up to 5 years and above so I think staying or haven't live in the UK is needed for you to start up a business or have a business so you have to stay for like a particular number of years before you can access anything</i> <i>A20 I am from Nigeria</i> <i>A21 How do I feel, it's a hustle because I am not from here, when I finally get it. I feel okay, I feel good but trying to get it is a problem, it is stressful</i> <i>A23 you have to be resident in the</i>

				<i>UK for I think it is 5 years and above then you have to..i think that is the only one I know</i>
P008			<i>A10 some Scottish and eastern European people will come to this shop to steal things like shop lifting and if I call the police they will take a lot of time before they come here and at times I will just ignore them and carry on with my business</i>	<i>A14.I get my loans from banks and sometimes if it is a small amount of money I normally ask my friends and family to lend me and I pay them back</i> <i>A17.I think so because when my Accountant applied it did not take a lot of time. The time frame is encouraging and the requirement is okay</i> <i>A18 I think they should simplify the process for foreigner and they should not look down on some people</i> <i>A22 sometimes they look at my passport and they will tell me you are not qualified to apply for this fund</i>
P009		<i>A10 I face a lot of challenges for example during this covid 19 period my business have been down, I don't use to make much profit also like getting a reliable staff is another problem, some customers like buy now and pay later which is not a good idea by the end of this month I will have to stop the buy now and pay later because people are abusing it</i>	<i>A3 Yes I do, sometimes.. some people don't trust foreigners</i>	
P011				<i>A18 some business owner don't know how to access business loan, you can imagine the next barber shop have been closed for more than 6 months and they did not know how to access</i>

				<p><i>business loan</i></p> <p><i>A32 there should be more flexibility on how to get it.</i></p> <p><i>A33 they could help with the form and with the application because they have all your details so you don't need to stress yourself to go to the bank or contact them, as soon as you register your company they all have your details</i></p>
P012	<p><i>A5 usually people who start these business aren't people who are actually educated so they are not totally aware of what is going in the banks and how can we get loans</i></p>	<p><i>A8 Like you have to be like a resident in the place that you are asking money from, for instant if you are like a student and you have just like leave to remain for many couple of years so the visa you are left doing may like give you like small option to work like limited time like 20 hours per week and you are not allowed to have any money from the bank, some conditions like this and also you have to have a good credit history. So I think this are the most two common ones you have to be a resident and have a good credit history</i></p>		<p><i>A3 Yes for sure, if I'm going to ask a friend for money, he has to arrange to cut-off this amount of money from his budget, so I think the issue of time to get the money is the main issue, and for the bank is the interest rate.</i></p> <p><i>A4 I think the allowance time for me to pay back and also the limited amount of money I will be allowed to take, sometimes you go to the bank and ask the bank for £10,000 they will just give you £5,000 this is your allowance.</i></p> <p><i>A5 small business owners or managers of small shop like this doesn't tend much to get money from banks, the friend at first instance and sometimes use their savings to put it in their business</i></p> <p><i>A21, In the beginning, there was like a cultural shock in terms of language and different cultures and background of the people here, but</i></p>

				<p><i>with time I have got the flavor and started to accept the situation and started to explore everything here.</i></p> <p><i>A22 What do you mean like immigration affecting, I don't think so because I am a resident here in the UK, so according to my visa so different kind of immigration visa can be granted and for some students can't start their own business otherwise they will go to the jail, we can like accommodate what immigration affect all of us, I can own small business, I can fit in student to work as a part time.</i></p>
P013				<p><i>A4 I applied for the bounce back loan and they did not give me, Because I am not Scottish, I am not British and I'm refugee, I applied for small money I did not apply for £50,000, I applied for £25,000 just small money for my shop</i></p> <p><i>A5 I don't know but some lawyers will come here and ask me to give them £5,000 so they could apply form for a loan for me, I tell them no, I will apply online and it's free</i></p>
P014		<p><i>A8 You either reduce the number of staff in other not to pay wages and you work more hours. You cannot seat at home and wait for people to work for you. The best is for you to employ one person and also work in the shop but if you employ 2 or 3 people in the shop you will not make more money because you will have to pay the 3 staff their wages.</i></p>	<p><i>A3 they required anymore, maybe they are afraid that they will not payback</i></p>	<p><i>A3 Because they will say we want to see your account, we want to see this, we want to see that, they ask a lot of questions. So if you apply for a loan it still depends on the manager.</i></p> <p><i>A4 Yes it depends on the manager, because if it's a small business and they feel I will not be able to pay back the loan, because small</i></p>

				<p><i>business generate small profit, if it is a big business they think it is going to do good.</i></p> <p><i>A8 You can imagine water bill is £720 for one year, electricity and gas bill is like £2,000, you see the £20,000 is nothing compare to the expenses.</i></p> <p><i>A12 Yes, I know, sometimes they give loan and sometimes they don't give, see like what is happening now, if they see colored guys they will not want to give them loan. Even if you have British passport or everything in this country, if they don't want to give you the loan they will not give you, and they will not tell you the reason why they don't want to give you the loan.</i></p>
P017				<p><i>A21 Well some bank because if you want to borrow they will just go and look at your history when they discover that something nationality like this they will start to turn you down I feel bad sometime</i></p>
P018				<p><i>A4 like to myself I'm okay I know about online you most have been to a lot of shop with older generation half of them don't know how to use the internet, like my uncle for example he has the old Nokia phone with no camera and internet not because he can't afford it because he can't operate it because of new technology so to ask him to do anything online is like asking him to go to the moon, see if you ask my uncle what is your</i></p>

				<p><i>email address he will tell you what the fuck. A lot of Asian shop within the should there are a lot of older generation.</i></p> <p><i>A33 Better rates and less kind of set up fees because they have a set up fees and interest rate as well so if that was lower maybe I could access or maybe do it more because right now I only do it often when I need it, you know I don't just do it for the sake I need it .</i></p>
P019				<p><i>A1 Just a little, I just know about business loan like loans to help your business but to be fair since I started the business I haven't look in to loan because I always look at them as debt but look back now I found out that I was wrong, as long as the business is growing loan will definitely boost them, I would have too into them more but I have always been avoiding Credit Card because I have seen them as debt</i></p>
P020				<p><i>A10 Not really, because they are lazy basted, you know they can't do up to 16 hours job so we do up to 16 hours job, if anybody say anything I can bounce them on the spot, you know</i></p>